
ON-MERRIT

Observing and Negating Matthew Effects in Responsible Research and Innovation Transition

Description of Action (detailed project plan) 1st Oct 2019

List of participants

Participant No. *	Participant organisation name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	Know-Center GmbH	AT
2	The Open University	GB
3	Technische Universität Graz	AT
4	Universidade do Minho	PT
5	Georg-August Universität Göttingen	DE

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1 Excellence

Success in research and innovation should primarily build and depend on merit, on clarity of thought, innovation of ideas, and integrity of processes, rather than on external factors like personal characteristics, prior reputation or levels of resources. **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)**, and especially **Open Science** (including Open Access to publications and research data), **public participation**, and **gender equality**, hold the promise to make scientific endeavours **more inclusive, participatory, understandable, accessible and re-usable** for large audiences, especially beyond the ivory towers of universities and research institutions. However, the potential for the RRI agenda to realise these promises of “inclusive and sustainable research and innovation”¹ depends heavily on the drivers and barriers to implementation imposed by a diverse range of institutions and individuals. **Making processes open will not *per se* drive wide re-use or participation unless also accompanied by the capacity (in terms of knowledge, skills, technological readiness and motivation) to do so.** Absorptive capacity² and ability to capitalize on knowledge resources vary considerably across institutions, businesses and populations. Such differences are further intensified by other factors like geographic location, language abilities, technological skills, educational levels and access to basic equipment (e.g., Internet access). Although advantages in RRI capabilities cannot be assumed to be further reinforced via Matthew effects in every circumstance, nonetheless, **to the extent that those in possession of such capacities potentially benefit from an advantage, RRI’s agenda of inclusivity is put at risk by conditions of “cumulative advantage” (the so-called “Matthew effect”³).**

1.1 Objectives

ON-MERRIT (Observing and Negating Matthew Effects in Responsible Research and Innovation Transition) recognises this threat to be urgent. In response, our interdisciplinary consortium deploys a cutting-edge combination of qualitative (surveys, questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, case-studies) and computational (scientometrics, text and data mining, social network analysis, predictive analytics) methods that use stakeholder participation and co-design to engage researchers, industry, policy-makers and societal stakeholders generally to broaden the SwafS knowledge-base in three key respects:

1. **Analysis of beneficiaries and dynamics:** ON-MERRIT will deepen understanding of who stands to benefit from current implementation strategies for key pillars of RRI like Open Science, Public Engagement and Gender Equality, as well as how and why this is so. How might current policy interventions designed to achieve these laudable aims actually drive new inequalities or exacerbate old ones? The project’s novel interdisciplinary approach will yield a rich evidence-base which facilitates answers to these questions from multiple dimensions.
2. **Synthesis of a portfolio of indicators:** Applying critical concepts from RRI research and Science and Technology Studies, ON-MERRIT will synthesise these multifaceted findings to provide a comprehensive portfolio of information which will allow conclusions about the persistence of Matthew effects in RRI to be drawn across domains and for different stakeholder groups.
3. **Recommendations for counterbalancing adverse effects:** Based on this new evidence-base and synthesis, ON-MERRIT will analyse gaps and blind-spots in current RRI implementation guidelines and measures (i.e., MoRRI indicators) and make policy recommendations for their future enhancement, extension or revision applicable to a range of stakeholders.

These questions will be directed towards examining barriers, drivers and incentives for RRI practices for all four stakeholder-groups in the “quadruple-helix” model of innovation:

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

² Cohen, W.M & Levithal D.A. (1990) Absorptive Capacity: A New Perspective on Learning and Innovation. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 35, No. 1p 128-152. DOI: 10.2307/2393553

³ Merton, R.K. (1968) The Matthew Effect in Science: The reward and communication systems of science are considered. *Science* 159, 56–63. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.159.3810.56>

1. **Research:** How do levels of uptakes of RRI practices vary across different researcher demographics, including by gender, location and institution? How does availability of training and support activities determine uptake? How can we facilitate the transformation from traditional “publish or perish” science to open responsible science while ensuring equitable results? How is this structurally shaped by existing and emergent reward factors?
2. **Industry:** What are the factors that influence the ability of economic actors to obtain and use scientific knowledge (absorptive capacity), including by gender? How do different economic actors make use of Open Science resources and how can we increase absorptive-capacity amongst economic actors?
3. **Policy:** How are Open Access resources used in policy-making? Do the RRI elements investigated (see Figure 1) reshape how voices of various actors, including by gender, are incorporated into policy-making?
4. **Society:** Does Open Access to publications and research data facilitate public participation and engagement with scientific knowledge and in debates? Which public actors actually contribute to evidence-based RRI policy-making and how?

Figure 1 ON-MERRIT scope and objectives

ON-MERRIT will balance broad investigation of the state of RRI in general with deep analysis, where research focuses in on the *gender dimension* as well as three specific scientific domains, chosen for their tangible relevance for the achievement of the UN’s sustainable development goals: *Agriculture*, *Climate*, and *Health*.

Synthesising this evidence to reveal the extent to which Open Science, Public Engagement and Gender Equality in scholarship, despite their key aims of inclusivity, are subject to the “rich get richer” logic of the Matthew effect, ON-MERRIT will then be able to move Responsible Research and Innovation beyond the current state-of-the-art to better incorporate self-reflexive critique of the consequences of policy interventions. Relating these findings to specific RRI indicators (e.g., MoRRI⁴) will then reveal gaps and deficiencies in current policy measures and enable ON-MERRIT to make evidence-based policy recommendations (validated via stakeholder-workshop) on how Research Performing (RPOs) and Funding Organisations (RFOs) and other stakeholders should amend indicators and reward/incentive schemes to

⁴ MoRRI project (2018) The evolution of Responsible Research and Innovation in Europe: The MoRRI indicators report. http://www.technopolis-group.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/D4.3_Revised_20022018_clean.pdf

address and/or mitigate these factors, thus breaking new ground for equitable Responsible Research and Innovation.

1.2 Relation to the work programme

ON-MERRIT addresses the call topic SwafS-20-2018-2019 *Building the SwafS knowledge base*⁵ within the 2018-2019 *Science with and for Society* H2020 Work Programme. Its work to develop a more open, participatory, and gender-sensitive framework for research and innovation has particular relevance for the following specific challenges of the text of that call:

Challenge 1: Understand the evolution of science and society to aid proactive and anticipatory policy making

ON-MERRIT analyses and systematically gathers evidence on the effects of a key set of RRI elements (open science, public engagement, gender and governance) on quadruple helix stakeholders (academia, civil society, industry, government), to provide a portfolio of cases where existing policy measures might increase (or migrate) effects of cumulative advantage and inequality of opportunity. It then synthesises this knowledge and models alternative policy/incentive scenarios to provide evidence-based guidelines and recommendations to improve institutional and governmental policies. By demonstrating and highlighting the existence of any such effects, ON-MERRIT will raise awareness of the unintended consequences of policy in this area for a range of stakeholders and demographic. Providing recommendations will then enable proactive and anticipatory RRI policy-making. Moreover, through its wider investigation of models of participation in science, industry and policy-making, ON-MERRIT will assist in understanding the barriers to participation for disadvantaged actors in science and society dialogues, thus aiding understanding of means to achieve equality of opportunity in these areas. This analysis, while examining these issues for all stakeholders, will maintain a particular focus in each research exercise upon issues related to gender and specific disciplines linked to the UN Sustainable Development Goals, thus aiding understanding of these elements of the evolution of science and society in particular.

Challenge 2: Reward achievement in RRI in its various dimensions to signal organisational awareness

ON-MERRIT focuses at its very core on questions of incentives, benefits and rewards for practising RRI. It will analyse the results of the case studies, the variability and dynamic of RRI applications in different research and disciplinary sectors and recommend concrete changes to existing policies and current recommended practices that will lead to fairer, more transparent and equitable reward mechanisms in science and encourage the application of RRI principles in science by rewarding collaboration with the quadruple helix stakeholders. ON-MERRIT's dissemination and participation strategy includes continuous communication (including blog posts, briefing papers, etc.) which will acknowledge and highlight best-practice achievements amongst stakeholders in the various domains investigated.

Challenge 3: Illuminate the implications of deep changes in science and innovation and their interactions with society and the economy, as well as resultant changes in the relationships between science and society

⁵ <http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/opportunities/h2020/topics/swafs-20-2018-2019.html>

Good science is not necessarily science that performs well under bibliometric indicators; it is science performed with integrity to produce replicable results that stand up to scrutiny, is based on equality of opportunity for the scientist, and is directed towards improving the lives of quadruple helix stakeholders. ON-MERRIT will scrutinise the extent to which the RRI agenda as currently constructed will lead to a more equitable scientific system. This reflexive research will provide additional evidence in order to strengthen the case for adoption of the RRI principles. Studying the interaction of societal-actors, industry and policy-makers with new forms of RRI knowledge will provide new insight into deep ways the RRI agenda forges realignment of the relationship between science, society, economy and policy. In particular, our investigations of information-seeking behaviours and uptake of Open Science resources (including research data) in industry will illuminate how Open Innovation and Open Science are increasingly intertwined, and point the way ahead for further interventions to stimulate activity in this direction. Case-studies of the gender aspect and specific disciplines will yield rich data. Meanwhile, our investigations of the interface between science and society in participatory policy-making will enhance understanding of the extent to which public engagement initiatives thus far have been successful as regards enabling opportunities of participation.

Challenge 4: Focus on blind spots of research and innovation in relation to people's needs and concerns and in any of the areas or dimensions covered by RRI

ON-MERRIT's primary focus is an urgent blind spot in RRI: the extent to which current RRI policy interventions and innovation models might exacerbate inequalities due to the Matthew effect's logic of cumulative advantage. Spotlighting this issue and related detrimental effects, collecting new knowledge, presenting successful experiences and providing recommendations on how to improve this condition will be of crucial value for protecting the interests of all quadruple helix stakeholders. In addition, the agenda of inclusivity underlying much RRI and Open Science activities can itself be considered an underexplored area. By enabling reflection on the systemic barriers that cumulative advantage to participation in RRI and Open Science themselves present, ON-MERRIT will enable a new phase of self-reflexive critique for these important agendas. This will enable primary RRI indicators such as MoRRI and SDG indicators to be critically assessed in light of a heretofore unconsidered dimension.

Challenge 5: Examine how societal actors, including young people, behave, understand, react to and interact with science and scientific developments, and their motives for engaging in science-related activities.

ON-MERRIT's analysis of public engagement in evidence-based policy-making will enhance the understanding of conditions that determine which societal actors are able to make their voices heard in some of today's most important societal challenges and techno-scientific developments. This will aid in identifying barriers and excluded groups and assist in understanding how the public engages with scientific issues, including those relating to key sustainable development goals. The intention is to increase the public's engagement with reliable and compelling science and consequently extend equality in the public participation in science. As throughout ON-MERRIT, gender will be a key issue in each analysis. Meanwhile, ON-MERRIT's focus on the motives and practices exhibited by economic actors in interacting with scientific developments and outputs in the age of Open Science will further inform understanding of the interaction of science and society in the broadest sense.

Challenge 6: Investigate how science and technology studies and different disciplines and multi/transdisciplinary approaches can help explain interactions between science and society.

ON-MERRIT will harness a complex and innovative mix of social and computational investigative methods to better understand the links between motivations, capacities, incentives, policies and technologies for a range of societal, economic and scientific actors in the co-creation of knowledge. Methods will include

theoretical sociology (science and technology studies), data-driven social inquiry (surveys, interviews and expert workshops), text and data mining, bibliometrics/scientometrics, and social network analysis. On the basis of these results, ON-MERRIT will synthesise state-of-play case-studies on gender issues and specific disciplines of acute relevance to achieving UN Sustainable Development Goals. ON-MERRIT will then computationally model new policy interventions and indicators to be able to deliver best-evidence recommendations for institutions and governments in mitigating Matthew effects in RRI and Open Science transition. With this innovative, iterative combination of computational and sociological approaches, ON-MERRIT will hence address the unintended consequences of scientific policy interventions to clarify interactions between science and society, and in so doing not only provide a more complete picture but also enable a self-reflexive, participatory and evidence-based approach to RRI policy-making.

1.3 Concept and approach

The existence of a “Matthew effect” (a feedback loop where (dis)advantage tends to beget further (dis)advantage) in science has long been recognised. In 1968⁶, Merton proposed that already successful scientists tend to receive disproportionately high recognition or rewards in comparison to their less-famous counterparts. Since then, studies have identified the ways in which effects of cumulative advantage in research play out at the level of article citations⁷, journals⁸, institutions⁹, departments¹⁰, and countries¹¹, as well as the individual attributes of researchers including race¹² and gender¹³. These effects are known to be at work across a range of scientific activities, including peer review¹⁴, public engagement¹⁵, and funding acquisition¹⁶.

Scientific knowledge is a key resource for achieving societal and economic goals. RRI promises to fundamentally transform scholarship to bring greater transparency, inclusivity and participation to research processes, and increase the academic, economic and societal impact of research outputs. It is a cross-cutting agenda that stands to contribute to most of the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals, as well as being a central pillar of the European Commission’s Digital Single Market strategy. Yet access to scientific products and processes is not made uniform simply because they are made available via the Internet. How equitable is implementation of the RRI keys across a range of stakeholder categories, and in particular for those at the peripheries? Might RRI interventions in some cases actually deepen socio-economic inequalities (digital

⁶ Merton, R.K. (1968) The Matthew Effect in Science: The reward and communication systems of science are considered. *Science* 159, 56–63. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.159.3810.56>

⁷ Wang, J. (2014) Unpacking the Matthew effect in citations. *J. Informetr.* 8, 329–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2014.01.006>

⁸ Larivière, V., Gingras, Y. (2010) The impact factor’s Matthew Effect: A natural experiment in bibliometrics. *J. Am. Soc. Inf. Sci. Technol.* 61, 424–427. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.21232>

⁹ Langfeldt, L., Benner, M., Sivertsen, G., Kristiansen, E.H., Aksnes, D.W., Borlaug, S.B., Hansen, H.F., Kallerud, E., & Pelkonen, A. (2015) Excellence and growth dynamics: A comparative study of the Matthew effect. *Sci. Public Policy* 42, 661–675. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scu083>

¹⁰ Weakliem, D.L., Gauchat, G., & Wright, B.R.E. (2012) Sociological Stratification: Change and Continuity in the Distribution of Departmental Prestige, 1965–2007. *Am. Sociol.* 43, 310–327. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12108-011-9133-2>

¹¹ Bonitz, M., Bruckner, E., & Scharnhorst, A. (1999) The matthew index—Concentration patterns and Matthew core journals. *Scientometrics* 44, 361. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02458485>

¹² Hofmänner, A. (2011) The African Eve Effect in Science. *Archaeologies* 7, 251–289. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11759-011-9160-1>

¹³ Rossiter, M.W. (1993) The Matthew Matilda Effect in Science. *Soc. Stud. Sci.* 23, 325–341.

¹⁴ Squazzoni, F. & Gandelli, C. (2012) Saint Matthew strikes again: An agent-based model of peer review and the scientific community structure. *J. Informetr.* 6, 265–275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2011.12.005>

¹⁵ Woods, J., 2015. The Op-ed Sociologists: The Matthew Effect in Op-ed Publication Patterns. *Am. Sociol.* 46, 356–372. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12108-015-9269-6>

¹⁶ Zhi, Q. & Meng, T. (2016) Funding allocation, inequality, and scientific research output: an empirical study based on the life science sector of Natural Science Foundation of China. *Scientometrics* 106, 603–628. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1773-5>

divide) and be at conflict with wider sustainable development goals? How do geographical, socio-economic, cultural and structural conditions lead to peripheral configurations in the European knowledge landscape? What factors are at play and what can be done (at a policy level) to foster absorptive capacity and enhance uptake and contribution to the production of scientific knowledge by wider societal, political and economic actors?

ON-MERRIT will deploy an innovative mixed-methodology approach that harnesses scientometrics and science and technology studies to answer these questions in new qualitative and quantitative ways to reach concrete conclusions and recommendations. The project will follow an RRI approach “that anticipates and assesses potential implications and societal expectations with regard to research and innovation, with the aim to foster the design of inclusive and sustainable research and innovation”¹⁷. It will take advantage of unique perspectives and knowledge by involving multiple stakeholders in participatory co-creation, consultation and validation processes. In so doing, it will bring critical self-reflection to the RRI agenda, moving it beyond the current state-of-the-art, to facilitate evidence-based policy-making.

1.3.1 *Matthew effects and research cultures*

Matthew effects pervade modern scholarship. Academia is a prestige economy, in which peer recognition plays a central role. But recognition first requires attention, and attention is everywhere a limited resource. Attention must be invested wisely, but how to determine what (or who) is most deserving? Harriet Zuckerman points to the empirical difficulties in determining relative levels of reputation and merit between two or more researchers.¹⁸ The same applies to research works. Such judgements often hence rely on secondary attributes: visibility, connections, history, affiliations, publishing venues, metrics, for example. In the academic attention economy, then, the potential for network effects is acute and hence Matthew effects flourish as attention flows more freely to the visible.

It is important to note that for Merton, Matthew effects were a consequence of a situation of imperfect information.¹⁹ Here, he viewed the Matthew effect as largely a functional element that aids determination of the credibility of sources.²⁰ But while the Matthew Effect in its various forms might therefore be functional at the system level, it has the effect of advantaging and disadvantaging the contributions of individuals, as well as the individuals themselves, based on secondary attributes. For Merton, differential allocation of attention was functional; it was the differential allocation of rewards that was problematic.²¹ Contrary to Merton, ON-MERRIT argues it is impossible to separate the latter from the former. As said at the start of this section, academia is an attention economy – rewards often are based largely on recognition, which in turn is often heavily shaped merely by one’s place and role in the network.

To a certain extent, this is unsurprising. If someone has a good profile, it is reasonable to think their next work may also be of quality. Yet, what is a “good profile”? The right qualifications, the right institutions, the right style of publications in the right kinds of journals? None of these factors are guarantors of quality in themselves; and demographic attributes are certainly not – yet Matthew effects seem to operate also at the level of region, gender, race, and language. It is not simply the *merit* of your ideas, theories, or experiments that counts, but often where you work, where you publish, who you know, which demographic groups you represent. Cumulative advantage is hence crucially important in determining outcomes.

Moreover, given that prestige is often a determining factor in the allocation of resources, the system becomes self-perpetuating. Besides symbolic and material rewards for (successful) research, the Matthew effect

¹⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

¹⁸ Zuckerman, H. (2010). The Matthew effect writ large and larger. A study in sociological semantics. In: Berliner Journal für Soziologie 20, 309-340.

¹⁹ Merton, R. K. 1973. The Matthew Effect in Science. In: Robert K. Merton. The Sociology of Science. Chicago, London: The University of Chicago Press, 439-459.

²⁰ Lamont, M. (2009). How Professors Think. Inside the curious world of academic judgement. Cambridge, MA, London: Harvard University Press.

²¹ Strevens, M. (2006). The role of the Matthew Effect in science. In: Studies in the History and Philosophy of Science 37, 159-170. DOI: 10.1016/j.shpsa.2005.07.009

shapes opportunities (i.e., the allocation of money, people, infrastructures) for doing research itself.²² The application of particularistic standards is therefore especially perilous for early-career researchers who have yet to build a “profile” and often do not yet have many achievements (publications, grants) beyond their alma mater.²³ By using citation metrics to evaluate research contributions, the Matthew effect leads to the self-reinforcement of initial positive feedback.²⁴ More recent work on the “entrepreneurial university”²⁵ suggests that performance indicators such as the impact factor are highly reactive²⁶ and therefore exacerbate a quasi-monopolization of resources (prestige, recognition, money) in the hands of relatively few institutions and individual researchers.

Reforming this rigged system to enable more inclusive and participatory research for all stakeholders (both inside and outside the ivory tower) can be seen as a core aim of RRI elements like gender equity and Open Science. Fecher and Friesike’s review found that there were 5 key aims underpinning Open Science, three of which directly support this thesis: (a) “Making knowledge freely available for everyone”; “Opening up the process of knowledge creation”; and “Making science accessible for citizens”.²⁷ Yet, so far, the extent to which the aims of inclusivity in RRI and Open Science policy might be endangered by Matthew effects has not been thoroughly examined in policy or research domains. We need not scratch very far below the surface to find such effects at play. We next present the theoretical grounding for our approach to investigate these potential Matthew Effects in the discrete areas of research, industry transfer and policy-making. It is important to note, however, that in spite of this pragmatic separation of foci, in line with our recognition of the essential interconnectedness of the quadruple helix, which emphasises interaction dynamics and knowledge flows between all these stakeholder areas, intimate links between each of these strands of work will ensure that they are treated holistically.

1.3.2 *Matthew effects in RRI and Open Science practices*

Open Access (OA) to publications and data is a key pillar of RRI. It is now commonly accepted that widespread OA brings considerable economic, social and academic benefits²⁸, and OA is now a mainstream policy in the EU, both at the European Commission and at the national levels. Starting from the FP7 OA pilot in 2008, Europe has come a long way, to the current all-inclusive OA mandate for all peer reviewed Horizon 2020 publications. Key support mechanisms like OpenAIRE’s infrastructure and network of OA desks across European member and associated countries and the forthcoming Open Research Europe publishing platform²⁹ assist in this regard. Most recently, in early September 2018, a group of national research funding organisations, with the support of the European Commission and the European Research Council (ERC), announced the launch of “cOAlition S,” an initiative that strives to make full and immediate OA to research publications a reality. It is built around “Plan S,” whose key target is that from 2020, “scientific publications on the results from research funded by public grants provided by national and European research councils and funding bodies, must be published in compliant Open Access Journals or on

²² Merton, R K. (1988). The Matthew Effect in Science, II. Cumulative Advantage and the Symbolism of Intellectual Property. In: *ISIS* 79, 606-623.

²³ Merton, R K.; Harriet Zuckerman. (1973b). Age, Aging, and Age Structure in Science. In: Robert K. Merton. *The Sociology of Science*. Chicago, London: The University of Chicago Press, 497-560.

²⁴ Wang, J., 2014. Unpacking the Matthew effect in citations. *J. Informetr.* 8, 329–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2014.01.006>

²⁵ Münch, R. 2014. *Academic Capitalism*. London, New York: Routledge.

²⁶ Fleck, C. (2013). Impact Factor Fetishism. In: *European Journal of Sociology* 2, 327-356. DOI: 10.1017/S0003975613000167

²⁷ Fecher B. & Friesike S (2013) Open Science: One Term, Five Schools of Thought. In: Bartling, S. and Friesike, S. (Eds.), *Opening Science*. New York, NY: Springer, 17–47. <http://hdl.handle.net/10419/75332>

²⁸ Tennant J.P., Waldner F., Jacques D.C. *et al.* (2016) The Academic, Economic and Societal Impacts of Open Access: An Evidence-Based Review [version 3; referees: 4 approved, 1 approved with reservations]. *F1000Research*, 5:632 (doi: 10.12688/f1000research.8460.3)

²⁹ <https://etendering.ted.europa.eu/cft/cft-display.html?cftid=3418>

compliant Open Access Platforms.”³⁰ Plan S iterates a further 10 principles which include further conditions including that all authors retain copyright, Open Access journals and platforms meet robust criteria, capped fees for article processing charges (APCs), and alignment of policies.

At present, however, implementation varies for funders and institutions in different regions or domains. There is a tendency to promote gold OA (via APCs) in the UK and Netherlands for example, while the rest of EU countries favour the green route (self-archiving in repositories), or a combination of both. Such differences at the policy-level are beginning to have effects upon choice of authorship venues. Although in theory the removal of paywalls as a barrier to access to knowledge should benefit less well-resourced institutions, the large-scale shift to the “Gold” model of Open Access, whereby works are made available in Open Access mode by the publisher immediately upon publication, usually in return for a one-off payment by authors (APCs) in fact merely constructs a new paywall at the other end of the publication pipeline. There is already evidence that diversity in availability of funding for APCs is driving a new stratification of publishing access, with authors at higher-ranking (and thus presumably better resourced) institutions less likely to publish in closed/paywalled outlets, and more likely to pay APCs, as well as also being likely to pay more (i.e., publishing in “more prestigious” highly-priced journals)³¹. This situation might be expected to worsen as resource-rich research countries push “big deals” which enable them to publish in gold ‘hybrid’ journals³² at limited or no extra cost above subscriptions (c.f., DEAL³³, COUPERIN³⁴ negotiations). How does this stratification of access to publication venues based on resources impact the visibility and impact of researchers from less well-resourced institutions, especially given the seemingly established “OA citation advantage”, where OA publications gather more citations?³⁵

Soon after the publication of ‘Plan S’, a discussion on possible unintended effects started. One issue was its focus on APC-based OA and the potential to push the scientific publishing system further in this direction, and the effects this may have on the rest of the world where access to funds for APCs is more limited. The combination of an OA mandate which focuses on OA journals and platforms (the latter is not fully defined yet) with the ceasing of support for hybrid OA, meanwhile, has been argued by some as an intervention into academic freedom, in the sense that it restricts the range of (mandate-compatible) journals where researchers can publish their work. This particularly may affect researchers which strongly rely on highly specialized society and commercial subscription journals. For example, Chemical Sciences researchers recently issued a public statement and open letter to indicate that this funder approach is potentially detrimental to their careers, in particular for early career researchers.³⁶ Early career researchers from the Global Young Academy (who have provided a Letter of Support for ON-MERRIT) have further pointed out that Plan S is rather vague on many points, and outline two scenarios, one with great opportunities, another with a strong increase in inequalities and harm to researchers’ careers and Europe as a whole.³⁷ Another core aspect which may inhibit the implementation of Plan S is the increasing concentration of the publishing sector and the lack of

³⁰ <https://www.scienceeurope.org/coalition-s/>

³¹ Siler K, Haustein S, Smith E, Larivière V, Alperin JP. (2018) Authorial and institutional stratification in open access publishing: the case of global health research. *PeerJ* 6:e4269 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4269>

³² A “hybrid journals” is a subscription journal which makes some of its articles OA, typically based on a fee.

³³ <https://www.projekt-deal.de/about-deal/>

³⁴ <https://www.the-scientist.com/?articles.view/articleNo/52208/title/French-Universities-Cancel-Subscriptions-to-Springer-Journals/>

³⁵ Sotudeh, H., Ghasempour, Z., & Yaghtin, M. (2015). The citation advantage of author-pays model: The case of Springer and Elsevier OA journals. *Scientometrics*, 104(2), 581-608. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1607-5>

³⁶ Kamerlin, L. et al. A Response to Plan-S from Academic Researchers: Unethical, Too Risky! In: Schneider, L. (2018, September 11). Response to Plan S from Academic Researchers: Unethical, Too Risky! – For Better Science. Retrieved November 5, 2018, from <https://forbetterscience.com/2018/09/11/response-to-plan-s-from-academic-researchers-unethical-too-risky/>; Research Community. (2018, November 5). Reaction of Researchers to Plan S (Version 1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1477914>

³⁷ Global Young Academy: Young Academies Release Statement in Response to ‘Plan S’ on Open Access of Scientific Output, 15 October 2018, <https://globalyoungacademy.net/young-academies-release-statement-in-response-to-plan-s-on-open-access-of-scientific-output/>

transparency in pricing as well as the asymmetry in negotiation power between research institutions and publishers.³⁸

Concerns about the potential for Matthew effects extends to many other areas of Open Science (including open data), which depend to a large extent on the availability of local training and support, as well as infrastructure and resources. Yet as reported by the MORRI³⁹ project, the readiness-levels of such training and support infrastructure amongst nations and institutions across Europe are highly diverse. How are these differing readiness levels already driving new forms of inequalities in research and access across Europe? How could policies and the MORRI indicators, which focus on driving institutional change, be amended to incentivise and prioritise such infrastructures?

Over the last decade institutions have stepped up their efforts in support of Open Science, in terms of building basic and enhanced infrastructures (including OA repositories for publications and research data), and by providing support to researchers for compliance with funder policies and mandates. All these efforts are based on public funding, that is, those institutions which have access to additional third-party funding will also be able to invest more in supporting infrastructures (and may use overheads from these projects to fund technical infrastructures and related services). Increasingly, projects build in budgets for OA publishing as well as data management while the latter is more challenging as the full costs of data management are difficult to assess. Tenopir et al. note several differences at institutions based in the U.S. regarding investment in research data services and strategies for development of staff capacity, e.g. libraries at institutions with high enrolments, those with large faculty, and those at research institutions were more likely to have already reassigned or to be planning to reassign existing staff than other institutions.⁴⁰ There were both differences in terms of when libraries take up such opportunities for development of support as well as to what extent. A follow-up study which concentrated on European research libraries found that by geographic region there are also substantial differences, e.g. the West and Nordic regions are most active in training colleagues on research data services (with over 60% of responding libraries) than other regions.⁴¹ Currently there are no similar comprehensive studies covering the current state of services related to RRI or Open Science practices available.

McKiernan et al.⁴² have pointed out that the main arguments used to promote policies may not address the practical barriers involved in changing researchers' behaviour, such as the common perception that open practices could present a risk to career advancement, closely investigated the concerns (related to publishing, funding, resource management and sharing, and career advancement) and suggested that the benefits of open practices outweigh the potential costs. In particular, training of researchers early in their careers is fundamental. At all career stages, acknowledging and supporting incremental steps is a way to respect researchers' present circumstances, and produce a gradual culture change from closed to open research.

At the same time, such practices depend on implicit or explicit reward and incentive structures. At the institutional level, these incentives are most visible when embedded in recruitment or promotion criteria. To date, only very few institutions have embedded Open Access practices in the researcher review and promotion process, moreover, there are less examples relating to researchers' being rewarded for applying

³⁸ European University Association. (2018, November 6). Scholarly publishing: EUA asks European Commission to investigate lack of competition. Retrieved November 7, 2018, from <https://eua.eu/news/188:scholarly-publishing-eua-asks-european-commission-to-investigate-lack-of-competition.html>

³⁹ <http://www.technopolis-group.com/report/evolution-responsible-research-innovation-europe-morri-indicators-report-d4-3/>, page 73

⁴⁰ Tenopir, C., Sandusky, R. J., Allard, S., & Birch, B. (2014). Research data management services in academic research libraries and perceptions of librarians. *Library & Information Science Research*, 36(2), 84–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lisr.2013.11.003>

⁴¹ Tenopir, C., Talja, S., Horstmann, W., Late, E., Hughes, D., Pollock, D., ... Allard, S. (2017). Research Data Services in European Academic Research Libraries. *LIBER Quarterly*, 27(1). <https://doi.org/10.18352/lq.10180>

⁴² McKiernan, E. C., Bourne, P. E., Brown, C. T., Buck, S., Kenall, A., Lin, J., ... Yarkoni, T. (2016). How open science helps researchers succeed. *ELife*, 5, e16800. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.16800>

other Open Science practices⁴³. In some cases, the reference is actually negative, e.g. a warning to researchers to refrain to publish their work in low-quality OA journals. There is hence an urgent need for work to define how to embed Open Science at an institutional policy level to ensure its wider adoption from researchers and demonstrate its benefits to researchers and the advancement of research. To address these issues, ON-MERRIT will undertake:

- **An investigation of uptake of types of Open Access:** ON-MERRIT will assess who is included and excluded in OA publishing, including based on gender. Desk research will detail the policy landscape regarding funding for Article Processing Charges (APCs) at the European, national and institutional levels. The project will use large scale statistical studies, big scholarly data and social network analysis to create computational models of publication behaviours and then relate these results to the policies in place. (Corresponds to Task 3.1, 3.2)
- **An investigation of training and support mechanisms for Open Science practices:** ON-MERRIT will identify broad trends in current Open Science training and support mechanisms (whether institutional or jointly organized with external parties) and compare these with levels of uptake of Open Science across different domains and demographics (including gender), combining this with stakeholder surveys and interviews, to create a holistic qualitative and quantitative picture of how uptake of RRI and Open Science relate to training/support measures. (Task 3.1, 3.3)
- **An investigation of current review and promotion criteria, and a proposal for RRI and Open Science metrics:** ON-MERRIT will identify, collect and analyse recruitment/promotion guides from academic institutions in sample countries in the project's focus areas. Based on this, a sample will be chosen for close analysis to produce a checklist of criteria for embedding RRI practices in such policies, as well as a comparison chart. Next, the project will propose new metrics and evaluation criteria which take into account the totality of RRI and Open Science practices. (Task 6.1)

1.3.3 *Matthew effects in the uptake of RRI and Open Science resources in industry*

Spurring growth and innovation in SMEs is a key goal of policy-makers. A commonly stated advantage of Open Access to publications and data is greater return on investment for funders, as results are made reusable to industry. According to the EC's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, for instance, "Open Access to research results [is] the springboard for increased innovation opportunities, for instance by enabling more science-based start-ups to emerge."⁴⁴ For SMEs in particular, open innovation is of paramount importance since "these firms usually lack the resources to effectively develop, produce, and commercialize their innovations".⁴⁵ SMEs therefore seek external collaborations to balance missing innovation.⁴⁶ Is open research data actually being taken up by industry, though? The scarce studies that address this issue show that although businesses see much potential for research re-use (e.g., for application development or process efficiency) and even though "access to research results has clear advantages for a range of industries,"⁴⁷ uptake thus far remains low.⁴⁸ This result is surprising given the inherent need for external inputs, especially for SMEs. Research points towards an effect of firm size on the ability to innovate, putting SMEs at a

⁴³ O'Carroll, C. et al. (2017). Evaluation of Research Careers fully acknowledging Open Science Practices: Rewards, incentives and/or recognition for researchers practicing Open Science. https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/os_rewards_wgreport.pdf

⁴⁴ Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. "Open Innovation, Open Science, Open to the World." Digital Single Market. 2016. <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3213b335-1cbc-11e6-ba9a-01aa75ed71a1>

⁴⁵ Colombo, M. G., Piva E., Rossi-Lamastra C. (2014). "Open innovation and within-industry diversification in small and medium enterprises: The case of open source software firms." In: Research Policy 43, 891.

⁴⁶ Van den Vrande, V, de Jong J P J, Vanhaverbeke, W, de Rochemont, M. (2009). „Open Innovation in SME's: trends, motives and management challenges. In: Technovation 29, 423-437.

⁴⁷ Tennant J.P., Waldner F., Jacques D.C. et al. (2016) The Academic, Economic and Societal Impacts of Open Access: An Evidence-Based Review [version 3; referees: 4 approved, 1 approved with reservations]. F1000Research, 5:632 (doi: 10.12688/f1000research.8460.3)

⁴⁸ Giovani, B. (2017) "Open Data for Research and Strategic Monitoring in the Pharmaceutical and Biotech Industry." *Data Science Journal* 16, no. 0 (April 4, 2017). <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2017-018>.

disadvantage. The safest strategy for SMEs is extensive networking to increase the ability to utilize external knowledge.⁴⁹ Here, we should distinguish the aims of Open Innovation and Open Science. While the former is about finding ‘private’ solutions to ‘public’ problems, Open Science is about ‘public’ (and often publicly financed) solutions for “public” problems⁵⁰. Research results and research data, then, can be seen as public goods, especially where the research was publicly funded. This fact has large implications for industry and SMEs on at least two counts: On the one hand, much industry research is at least partly financed by public sources (e.g., the EC’s Horizon framework programmes). Yet economic actors fear that making research data/results public can put them at a competitive disadvantage. On the other hand, Open Innovation practices account for diversification of business models in SMEs,⁵¹ affect the ability of SMEs to innovate and can – depending on the context – contribute to their competitive advantage.⁵² For instance, the most comprehensive literature on Open Science in industry exists on the industry uptake, development, and use of open source software and the motivations of practitioners to contribute.⁵³ Open source software can have considerable advantages for industry, e.g. lower cost, a logic which has successfully been deployed to other domains as well, e.g. renewable energy.⁵⁴ There might therefore be good reasons for SMEs to utilize Open Science resources. Thus, it is to be expected that SMEs are at least somewhat ambivalent about the potential of RRI and Open Science, even if they are aware of it.

Ability to draw on scientific resources (absorptive capacity) enhances competitiveness and employability⁵⁵ and has been associated with increased returns on investment.⁵⁶ With regard to knowledge intensive economies, it is essential to understand how to obtain scientific knowledge and how to deploy it in practice. On the other hand, industry actors might have a justified interest in not making their research public. Not so long ago, many large firms were amongst the most vocal advocates of Intellectual Property Rights. Without strong IPRs, e.g. IBM contended, there would be no incentive for firms to invest in software development.⁵⁷ In recent years, however, many (though certainly not all) large companies have switched to models which include both open and proprietary elements. How does RRI (especially Open Science) impact industry research, especially since industry research is often publicly funded?⁵⁸ ON-MERRIT recognises that evidence to answer this question is sparse. Research is thus needed to assess the extent of uptake of RRI practices and resources across the picture, to discover inequalities and the barriers/drivers that create them. What allows different economic actors to draw on open research outputs (or not)? Providing answers to such questions is urgent to realise the true economic potential of RRI and Open Science. To accomplish that, ON-MERRIT will undertake:

- ***Investigation of readiness to exploit Open Science resources amongst economic actors:*** To what extent do industrial actors make use of scientific resources, and how does Open Access change or enable these behaviours? How do levels of uptake differ amongst varieties of economic entities (including based on scale, domain, geography and primary language)? What factors increase

⁴⁹ Bradshaw A., Pulakanam V., Cragg P. (2015). “Knowledge Sharing in IT Consultant and SME Interactions”. In: *Australasian Journal of Information Systems* 19, 197-217.

⁵⁰ Balasegaram M., Kolb P., McKew J., et al. (2017). “An open source pharma roadmap”. In: *PLoS Medicine* 14(4): e1002276. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1002276>

⁵¹ Shutyak, Y. (2016). “Open innovation practice: a case study of university spin-offs”. In: *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Innovation* 12(1), 75 (16).

⁵² Mohsam, F., van Brakel, P.A. (2011). “Information and knowledge sharing trends of small and medium-sized enterprises in the Western Cape, South Africa”. In: *SA Journal of Information Management* 13(1). DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajim.v13i1.462>.

⁵³ Bonaccorsi, A., Rossi, C. (2006). “Comparing Motivations of Individual Programmers and Firms to Take Part in the Open Source Movement: From Community to Business. In: *Knowledge, Technology, & Policy* 18(4), 40-64.

⁵⁴ Buitenhuis, A. J., Pearce, J. M. (2012). “Open-source development of solar photovoltaic technology”. In: *Energy for Sustainable Development* 16, 3779-388.

⁵⁵ Cohen, W.M. & Levinthal, D.A. (1990) “Absorptive Capacity: A New Perspective on Learning and Innovation.” *Administrative Science Quarterly* 35, no. 1: 128–52. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2393553>.

⁵⁶ Beagrie N., Houghton, J. (2014). “The Value and Impact of Data Sharing and Curation. A synthesis of three recent studies of UK data research centres”. URL: <http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/5568/>

⁵⁷ Samuelson, P. (2006). “IBM’s pragmatic embrace of Open Source”. In: *Communications of the ACM* 49(10), 21-25.

⁵⁸ Arzberger P., Schroeder P., Beaulieu A., et al. (2004). Promoting Access to Public Research Data for Scientific, Economic, and Social Development. *Data Science Journal* 3(29), 135-152.

absorptive capacity? How could it be improved? What role do demographic factors (including gender) play? Through direct, participatory consultation with industrial actors, ON-MERRIT will identify gaps in provision of support to drive re-use of open scientific publications. (Task 4.1, 4.2)

- ***Investigation of Open Science practices in European patent literature:*** ON-MERRIT will use scientometric techniques to discover the extent of re-use of research data in the three key ON-MERRIT scientific domains (Agriculture, Climate, and Health) as revealed in the patent literature of Europe and other regions. Do economic actors make use of open research data, and how does the scale of individual organisations influence such use? Do different industry actors make use of other Open Science products (e.g., software)? (Task 4.1, 4.2)

1.3.4 Matthew effects in policy-making and public engagement

In the complex relationship between science and society, a number of developments are crucially relevant for understanding the ways in which contemporary public policies aim at conditions of mutual benefit. Since at least the 1960s, the ideal of the ivory tower has been called heavily into question.⁵⁹ Beginning with questions of societal relevance of science, environmental concerns became more prominent during the 1970s. Especially, active resistance towards recombinant DNA technology with its first wave in the US during the 1970s,⁶⁰ and its recurrence in Europe during the 1990s^{61,62} called traditional arrangements between science and society into question.⁶³ Today, there is a broad understanding that technological actors can no longer merely delegate concern about impact to government agencies and societal actors.^{64,65}

As a response to such scientific controversies, many European countries have taken active steps to advance policy-making. “Inclusive governance” has become an important goal for the European Commission since at least the early 2000s.⁶⁶ During the first decade of the millennium, large amounts of funding were invested into genome research accompanied with research into ethical, legal and social aspects.^{67,68} Nanotechnology is another field in which new approaches in public-policy were developed and ideas regarding responsible research and innovation began to materialize.^{69, 70, 71}

⁵⁹ Rip, A. (2014): The past and future of RRI. In: *Life Sciences, Society and Policy* 10 (1), S. 17. DOI: 10.1186/s40504-014-0017-4, p4.

⁶⁰ Seifert, F. (2006) Local steps in an international career. a Danish-style consensus conference in Austria. In: *Public Understanding of Science* 15 (1), S. 73–88. DOI: 10.1177/0963662506058383.

⁶¹ Krimsky, S. (1982) *Genetic Alchemy*. Cambridge/MA & London/UK: MIT Press, 70-80.

⁶² Schomberg Von, Rene (2013) A vision of responsible innovation. In: Richard Owen, John R. Bessant und Maggy Heintz (Hg.): *Responsible innovation. Managing the responsible emergence of science and innovation in society*. Chichester: Wiley, S. 51–74.

⁶³ Gottweis, H. (1998) *Governing Molecules. The Discursive Politics of Genetic Engineering in Europe and the United States*. Cambridge, MA & London, UK: The MIT Press.

⁶⁴ Rip, A. (2014) The past and future of RRI. In: *Life Sciences, Society and Policy* 10 (1), S. 17. DOI: 10.1186/s40504-014-0017-4, p8.

⁶⁵ Stilgoe, J. (2013) Foreword: Why Responsible Innovation? In: Richard Owen, John R. Bessant und Maggy Heintz (Hg.): *Responsible innovation. Managing the responsible emergence of science and innovation in society*. Chichester: Wiley, S. xi–xv, pxii.

⁶⁶ European Commission (2003): *Report from the Commission on European Governance*. Luxembourg: European Communities. Online verfügbar unter http://ec.europa.eu/governance/docs/comm_rapport_en.pdf.

⁶⁷ “Branching out from responsible development of nanotechnology, and its precursor in the Human Genome Project’s ELSI component, and ELSA studies more widely, there is now also consideration of responsible synthetic biology and geo-engineering, with or without reference to RRI.” (Rip 2014: 8)

⁶⁸ Zwart, H. & Nelis, A. (2009) What is ELSA genomics? In: *EMBO Reports* 10 (6), S. 540–544. DOI: 10.1038/embor.2009.115.

⁶⁹ Rip, A. (2014) The past and future of RRI. In: *Life Sciences, Society and Policy* 10 (1), S. 17. DOI: 10.1186/s40504-014-0017-4.

⁷⁰ Fisher, E. & Rip, A. (2013) *Responsible Innovation: Multi-Level Dynamics and Soft Intervention Practices* (Wiley Online Books).

⁷¹ Owen, R., Macnaghten, P., Gorman, M., Fisher, E. & Guston, D. (2013): *A Framework for Responsible Innovation*. In: Richard Owen, John R. Bessant und Maggy Heintz (Hg.): *Responsible innovation. Managing the responsible emergence of science and innovation in society*. Chichester: Wiley, S. 26–50.

One important element of these new approaches of “inclusive governance” was the engagement of civil society in various forms of knowledge production, contributing to a wider and more inclusive process of research and innovation as well as political decision-making. Clearly, the challenge is to make such integrated, robust, transdisciplinary, responsible knowledge effective beyond the context in which it was produced – or as René von Schomberg put it: “The most crucial advancement of RRI will be dependent on the willingness of stakeholders to work together toward socially desirable products.”⁷² Valuable insights into the long history of the governance of science and society lead to questions of whether there is a need for new forms of public engagement.⁷³ What can be done in order to advance outcomes of such comprehensive knowledge production and deliberation?⁷⁴ How, and to what extent, do principles and practices of RRI and Open Science impact policy-making? How are existing power structures in the construction of public policy altered by these trends? How can we find a way forward when, in the words of Stilgoe, “tools such as public dialogue, constructive technology assessment, foresight or code of conduct [cannot] be taken as panacea”?⁷⁵ ON-MERRIT will address these issues to discover the conditions for the advancement of public engagement and responsible innovation to maximise the integration of open forms of knowledge production in policy-making. It has been suggested that EU policies might serve as a catalyst,⁷⁶ but little is known about uptake in policy making practices of the member states. Which innovation models do policy agents and practitioners use and how do these mental models (in the words of Bessant) “shape what decision-makers pay attention to, what they commit resources to, and how they manage the process”.⁷⁷ To address these issues, ON-MERRIT draws on Science and Technology Studies and combines qualitative and quantitative approaches to study in-depth the interactions between forms of inclusive knowledge production and (deliberative) policy-making. In particular, it will study the ways in which governments and public administration make use of RRI and Open Science resources and participatory processes in creating policy. ON-MERRIT will undertake:

- ***An investigation of the knowledge basis of governmental policies:*** ON-MERRIT will investigate information-seeking behaviours within governments and parliaments to determine the ways in which open and inclusive forms of knowledge production are included in policy-making. Methods of social inquiry will be used to analyse how scientific resources in general, as well as Open Access and Open Science resources, are in use within policy-making. (Task 6.1, 6.2)
- ***An investigation of structural aspects of public participation in policy-making:*** Using desk research and Qualitative Inquiry, ON-MERRIT aims to gauge levels of transparency and accountability in policy-making and the structural grounds for open and inclusive forms of knowledge production and application. Through expert workshops and other methods of stakeholder engagement, ON-MERRIT will focus on selected disciplinary cases (Agriculture, Climate, and Health) to determine the ways in which civil society actors influence policy in these key scientific debates, and whose voices are heard on these matters of crucial importance for the Sustainable Development Goals. Gender will be a specific element of analysis, and particular emphasis will be placed on the extent to which current indicators, including MoRRI and the SDG indicators, foster change to counteract Matthew effects in this regard (Task 6.1, 6.3)

⁷² Schomberg Von, Rene (2013), p71.

⁷³ Stilgoe, J. (2013) Foreword: Why Responsible Innovation? In: Richard Owen, John R. Bessant und Maggy Heintz (Hg.): Responsible innovation. Managing the responsible emergence of science and innovation in society. Chichester: Wiley, S. xi–xv.

⁷⁴ Sykes, K. & Macnaghten, P. (2013) Presponsible Innovation - Opening Up Dialogue and Debate. In: Richard Owen, John R. Bessant und Maggy Heintz (Hg.): Responsible innovation. Managing the responsible emergence of science and innovation in society. Chichester: Wiley, S. 85–108.

⁷⁵ Stilgoe (2013) p xiii.

⁷⁶ Fisher, E. & Rip, A. (2013) Responsible Innovation: Multi-Level Dynamics and Soft Intervention Practices (Wiley Online Books), p169.

⁷⁷ Bessant, J. (2013) Innovation in the Twenty-First Century. In: Richard Owen, John R. Bessant und Maggy Heintz (Hg.): Responsible innovation. Managing the responsible emergence of science and innovation in society. Chichester: Wiley, S. 1–25, p10

1.3.5 Cross-cutting themes: Gender and the sustainable development goals

ON-MERRIT will specifically address issues related to gender as well as investigating in-depth selected scientific disciplines of acute relevance for achieving the UN sustainable development goals (Agriculture, Climate, and Health). These areas will cut across all ON-MERRIT research activities, forming central issues of interest throughout ON-MERRIT's investigation of the various potential effects of cumulative advantage in RRI and Open Science transition across research, industry and policy/civil society. Allowing these cross-cutting issues to be investigated within each research activity will deliver a wealth of data about the extent of inequities related to these issues in the areas of research culture, industry and policy-making. These issues will cut across all research activities such that a wealth of diverse findings will allow in-depth case-studies to be constructed for each issue.

1.3.5.1 Gender

ON-MERRIT will tackle the dimension of gender during all its stages. Gender is one of the key components of RRI as well as of the EC's overall approach to promoting a culture of openly sharing information among researchers, innovative industries and citizens. Acknowledgement of gender-related disparities in research is slowly growing, but at different rates in different domains (life and social sciences seem more advanced than engineering and technologies, for instance). This is at least partly due to traditional performance metrics that are often blind to gender differences. For instance, EC-funded research has shown that bibliometric analyses often fail to consider career-breaks due to maternity-leave.⁷⁸ Gender-related inequalities persist in the areas of hiring, earnings, funding, satisfaction and patenting.⁷⁹ ⁸⁰ Inequalities of gender are especially pertinent to evaluation of researchers as individuals, but also to the evaluation of research outputs themselves. Such disparities can be clearly related to the Matthew effect. In the 1990s, Margaret W. Rossiter coined the "Matilda effect" to describe disparities in the levels of recognition accorded the research work and achievements of women compared to men.⁸¹ A more recent study finds that although the situation has now improved with respect to overt discrimination, "women continue to be disadvantaged with respect to the receipt of scientific awards and prizes, particularly for research."⁸² ON-MERRIT will investigate how changes in RRI and Open Science policy and practices affect this situation, for better or worse. Gender is a core part of the RRI agenda, but might other RRI pillars (and the indicators used to measure their progress) conflict with the aims of gender parity? For instance, how are female authors affected by the transition to Open Access in scientific publishing and the stratification effects discussed above? Are there gender differences in levels of uptake of RRI and Open Science practices? Are there gendered aspects to current publication/dissemination practices which have been overlooked (e.g., author order on papers is an indicator of contribution in many disciplines but is at the same time a matter of negotiation) and could be amended by RRI and Open Science practices? How do reconfigured online social networks impact the visibility and influence of women scientists? More generally, are there gendered aspects to the impact of innovative dissemination tools on building online research communities and networks? How might RRI metrics and indicators be preferentially beneficial based on gender (as with the case of bibliometrics cited above)? Are there gender aspects to the uptake of open and reproducible research that might affect outcomes? Are there gender differences in information-seeking behaviours and skills that affect the uptake of Open Science resources in industry? How does gender impact participatory policy-making? How does gender correlate with involvement with public-sphere policy discussions about scientific issues? And how might all these factors feed into the cumulative disadvantage that seems to be suffered by women in research? Recognising these questions to be vitally important, gender analysis with respect to cumulative (dis)advantage will hence

⁷⁸ European Commission (2012). Research and Innovation Meta-analysis of gender and science research. https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_gender_equality/meta-analysis-of-gender-and-science-research-synthesis-report.pdf

⁷⁹ Van der Lee, R., Ellemers, N. (2015). „Gender contributes to personal research funding success in the Netherlands”. In: PNAS 112(40), 12349-12353.

⁸⁰ Zhou, C. D., Head, M. G., Marshall, D. C. et al. (2018). “A systematic analysis of UK cancer research funding by gender of primary investigator. In: BMJ Open 8, e018625. DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2017-018625

⁸¹ Rossiter, M.W. (1993) The Matthew Matilda Effect in Science. Soc. Stud. Sci. 23, 325–341.

⁸² Lincoln, A.E., Pincus, S., Bandows Koster, J., & Leboy, P.S. (2012), The Matilda Effect in science: Awards and prizes in the US, 1990s and 2000s, Social Studies of Science, 42 (2): 307–320, doi:10.1177/0306312711435830

be an integral component of ON-MERRIT, running through all research activities (WP 3, 4, 5) as a cross-cutting theme and synthesised in a specific case-study report in WP 6. Based on this work, related recommendations and policy reports will be produced for avoiding Matilda effects⁸³ in RRI and Open Science transition. As ON-MERRIT tackles the dimension of gender during all its stages, this will be also taken into account when applying the contextual inquiry methods. On the one hand, we aim at promoting a gender balance when selecting interview partners and focus group participants. On the other hand, we will analyse the results gained in surveys, questionnaires, interviews and focus groups according to gender-related disparities.

1.3.5.2 Disciplines of relevance for the sustainable development goals

In 2015, the United Nations adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a collection of 17 global goals set by the United Nations General Assembly to provide guidance and targets for global, stakeholder-led sustainable development by 2030.⁸⁴ The 17 goals cover a wide array of often interconnected issues, as can be seen in Figure 2 below.

These 17 goals relate to 169 individual targets, and progress towards these targets is to be monitored by over 230 indicators (this number continues to grow, and many more have been proposed).⁸⁵ In ON-MERRIT, as described in section 2.1.1 (Expected Impacts) below, we aim to address multiple SDGs including “gender equality” (see previous section), “decent work and economic growth,” “industry innovation and infrastructure”, and “reduced inequalities”. In addition, however, in our investigations into scientific cultures and practices we have chosen to focus in-depth on three particular disciplines that will be vital in achieving specific SDGs, namely Agriculture, Health and Climate, which address (respectively):

- **SDG 2 Zero Hunger:** End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture
- **SDG 3 Good Health and Well-Being:** Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages
- **SDG 13 Climate Action:** Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts

⁸³ Rossiter, M.W. (1993) The Matthew Matilda Effect in Science. In: *Social Studies of Science* 23, 325–341.

⁸⁴ <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/>

⁸⁵ Zinkernagel, R., Evans, J., & Neij, L. (2018) Applying the SDGs to Cities: Business as Usual or a New Dawn? *Sustainability* 10, 3201.

Figure 2 UN Sustainable Development Goals

ON-MERRIT will hence obtain a wealth of data about inequities in research culture, uptake of Open Science outputs in industry and participation in policy-making in each of these three SDG/scientific discipline pairs (Agriculture/SDG 2, Health Sciences/SDG 3, and Climate Science/SDG 13). By then synthesising this data into three case-studies on the state-of-play in each discipline across research, industry and policy, ON-MERRIT will provide a comprehensive picture of the threats of Matthew effects in each area. Doing so will enable informed reflection on how current indicators and incentives shape practice. This will give pause for reassessment towards reshaping systems to promote equitable research and innovation which allows the best research ideas to flourish, thus contributing to the efficient performance of essential research work, stimulation of economic growth and greater stakeholder participation in policy-making.

1.3.6 Synthesis and recommendations

As a final step, the ON-MERRIT team will work to synthesise the rich findings gathered during the various phases and strands of research undertaken in ON-MERRIT. This knowledge of the extent of the threats posed by Matthew Effects in relation to current RRI and open science policy interventions will enable the modelling of alternative scenarios regarding possible incentives and indicators (including the MoRRI indicators), with the aim of producing practical guidelines and policy recommendations targeted to stakeholders including EU, national and institutional policymakers. All recommendations and suggested policy interventions will be devised with the involvement and critical feedback of key stakeholders, and validated via a range of channels, including a final ON-MERRIT stakeholder workshop in month 28 of the project. The final aim will be to produce practical guidelines, checklists and policy briefings for EU, national, and institutional policy-makers and other stakeholders.

1.3.7 Linked research

ON-MERRIT starts from an advanced level of knowledge and expertise, obtained as a result of many years of experience in conducting projects and activities within the various areas of concern. The consortium partners are hence well-embedded within diverse networks of knowledge and action across research, industry and policy. Engaging these networks will enable ON-MERRIT to draw, from the very start, on external expertise and data-sources, to initialise ON-MERRIT's collaborative co-design methodologies and to draw attention to project activities and outputs. As detailed below in section 2.2.3, the next step in our *stakeholder engagement strategy* will be to extend our network to new institutions and individuals (a process already begun in dialogues as a result of this proposal, and reflected in the range of Letters of Support received). An overview of the most relevant initiatives to which ON-MERRIT will be linked is given compiled below. This table will be continuously updated throughout the project as new initiatives and liaison opportunities are

identified. The particular connection to ON-MERRIT as well as the individual relevance of each organisation has been highlighted.

Table 1 National/international research and innovation activities to which ON-MERRIT will be linked

Project	Description	Relevance for ON-MERRIT
CORE	127m metadata records, 87m abstracts, 10.5m full text papers for text/data mining.	ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use CORE's dataset - academia focus - to collect and analyse scholarly datasets with the aim to identify and measure the extent of Matthew effects in science and how they are influenced by the application of RRI and Open Science principles. • CORE's dataset in the scientometric and text/data mining experiments.
Data Market Austria	Service-ecosystem for secure data markets, cloud and data-centred innovation in Austria.	ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate DMA's findings on barriers/drivers to data re-use in industry • Investigate the work conducted in the Lighthouse Project to ensure re-use of data with regards to interoperability, community building, data archiving and storage • Follow the project's pilots that demonstrate reuse of data and services
Eurodoc	European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers - A federation of 29 national organisations of PhD candidates, and young researchers from 28 EU countries	ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seek advice and input from Eurodoc members (e.g., via ON-MERRIT advisory board membership, review of deliverables, co-creation activities) • Engage Eurodoc's EU network for dissemination (especially to target surveys to global young researchers), stakeholder participation and validation activities • Collaborate on policy-related activities
European Cluster Observatory	Clusters are groups of specialised enterprises – often SMEs – and other related supporting actors that cooperate closely together in a particular location.	ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage clusters identified via the European Cluster Observatory, a single access point for information and mapping of clusters and cluster policy in Europe, for dissemination (especially to target surveys to SMEs), stakeholder participation and validation activities
FIT4RRI	Skills for RRI and Open Science practices. 4 co-creation experiments on RRI and Open Science	ON-MERRIT will use: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings from FIT4RRI's co-creation experiments • Existing RRI and Open Science training materials, such as resources and courses, for the promotion of the RRI and Open Science concepts
FOSTERplus	H2020 training/advocacy effort for Open Science in Europe and beyond	ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build on FOSTER analysis and assess use and uptake of FOSTER resources • Use FOSTER's courses to explain Open Science concepts relating to this project • Locate Open Science advocates from FOSTER's trainers' directory • Review FOSTER's toolkit courses on Open Access and Open Science policies, impact and citations

GENDERACTI ON	H2020 CSA to foster gender equality in the ERA through policy and training actions	ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Build on GENDERACTION policy and training resources and assess their use and uptake ● Collaborate with GENDERACTION to engage their network for dissemination, stakeholder participation and validation ● Seek advice on gender aspects of research deliverables (especially in reviewing the gender case-study in WP6)
Global Young Academy	Organisation for outstanding young scientists around the world which enables international, interdisciplinary, and inter-generational dialogue with the goal to make global decision-making evidence-based and inclusive.	GYA's priorities of "focus on science and policy, the research environment, and science education and outreach as well as the cross-cutting theme GYA and the UN Sustainable Development Goals" all relate directly to ON-MERRIT's research aims. To foster collaboration, ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seek advice and input from GYA members (e.g., via ON-MERRIT advisory board membership, review of deliverables, co-creation activities) ● Engage GYA's global network for dissemination (especially to target surveys to global young researchers), stakeholder participation and validation activities
LIBER	Professional association of national and university research libraries in Europe with membership > 400 organizations	ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Exploit close working relationships with LIBER to engage their network of research libraries in the construction and dissemination of survey/interview instruments ● Work to disseminate information regarding the risks of Matthew effects in RRI and Open Science
MoRRI / SUPER_MoRRI	RRI scientific evidence, data, analysis and policy intelligence to support DG-RTD	ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Link to ongoing activities of the recently announced SUPER_MoRRI project ● Review the project's outcomes and analytical reports relating to RRI and Open Science, metrics and indicators ● Assess the soundness of the MoRRI/SUPER_MoRRI conceptual framework ● Take into consideration MoRRI/SUPER_MoRRI's reporting on barriers to innovation, regulations and standards, policies and programmes
NewHoRRIzon	Aims at further integrating RRI in the research and innovation systems on national and international levels	ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Collaborate with and learn from NewHoRRIzon's 19 Social Labs and co-created pilot actions ● Build upon and critically incorporate NewHoRRIzon's concept of Societal Readiness of Technology (= Societal Readiness Levels) ● Assess NewHoRRIzon's policy advice on how to better integrate RRI into the next European Framework Programme ● Engage NewHoRRIzon's RRI Network (incl. national funding agencies) and RRI community (esp. RRI Ambassadors programme) for dissemination, stakeholder participation and validation activities
OCSDNet	Investigates institutional and value contexts of OS, especially in the Global South	ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Build upon OCSDNet findings on how RRI and Open Science contribute to development goals ● Consult the outcomes of the project reports ● Review the project's outputs relating to Open Science and research processes

OpenAIRE	H2020 infrastructure interconnecting repositories and journals	EU OA and	ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use OpenAIRE’s data for scientometrics • Engage its national OA desks for outreach, dissemination and engagement of stakeholders across Europe.
OpenMinTeD	Open cloud e-Infrastructure for Text and Data Mining (TDM) of scholarly content		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ON-MERRIT will benefit from OpenMinTeD’s tools, guides, online tutorials and infrastructure for mining scholarly data
OpenUP	OpenUP investigates innovative review/disseminate/assess methods and policies		ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use OpenUP’s RRI finding • Re-use its openly available survey datasets • Follow research methods (especially for validation and synthesis of findings) • Build upon policy outputs/recommendations.
ORION	RRI and Open Science in research and funding organizations in life sciences/ biomedicine		ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build upon ORION’s outputs, especially its “co-creation experiments” • Review project outcomes on RRI stakeholders • Investigate the RRI and Open Science components in relation to the ON-MERRIT project
Project funded under SwafS-04 call	“Encouraging re-use of research data generated by publicly funded research”		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ON-MERRIT will establish links to the project funded under the call “Encouraging the re-use of research data generated by publicly funded research projects” to avoid overlaps and synergise efforts in tasks assessing data re-use in industry
RRIng	Aims to bring RRI into the linked up global world to promote mutual learning and collaboration in RRI.		ON-MERRIT will <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link up to RRING’s community network and contribute to its OA RRI knowledge base • Seek advice from and collaborate with RRING on alignment of RRI with the Sustainable Development Goals
RRI Tools	Digital resources to advocate, train, disseminate and implement RRI under Horizon 2020		ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilise RRI’s extensive resources on applying RRI concepts and strategies in particular contexts and within specific areas • Build upon RRI Tools’ self-reflection tool: https://www.rri-tools.eu/self-reflection-too
RRI-Practice	Aims to understand the barriers and drivers to the successful implementation of RRI		ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build upon RRI-Practice’s results and network • Review and consult the project’s national workshop reports, policy briefs and national case studies on the areas relating to the ON-MERRIT project
Research Data Alliance	Promotes open sharing of data across technologies, disciplines, and countries.		ON-MERRIT will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborate with RDA on metrics, dissemination and policy issues relating to research data • Review the project’s supporting outputs, specifically in relation to best practices and gap assessment in the areas where ON-MERRIT explores • Explore RDA’s adoptions and recommendations
YEAR network	YEAR (Young		ON-MERRIT will

	European Associated Researchers) is a non-profit international organization which gathers professionals from European Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seek advice and input from YEAR members (e.g., via review of deliverables, co-creation activities) ● Engage YEAR’s EU network for dissemination (especially to target surveys to global young researchers), stakeholder participation and validation activities ● Collaborate on events and policy-related activities
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1.3.8 Methodology

ON-MERRIT will employ an innovative constellation of methods combining empirical social enquiry and computational approaches to investigate phenomena from multiple angles and obtain a holistic assessment. Principles of co-design and participatory research will be used to involve stakeholders in the construction of data collection instruments, the synthesis of results, and validation of policy recommendations. Findings will be continuously validated via their early release on the ON-MERRIT blog, feedback from stakeholders via social media channels and at a final ON-MERRIT stakeholder validation forum. To achieve its ambitious research aims, ON-MERRIT’s cross-disciplinary team will employ the following methodological tools:

- **Desk research:** Background research will define the state-of-the-art and provide context for future findings. It will also inform the conceptual frameworks and base-knowledge for the construction of the survey and interview instruments, as well as dataset collection and preparation for computational tasks, in the work across all research foci (research, industry, policy-making). Drawing further on the literature, conceptual analysis will then be carried out to study the ways in which RRI and sustainable development goals are integrated in the examined material. Finally, the relation of specific indicators (including MoRRI and SDG indicators) will be mapped to specific ON-MERRIT research questions.
- **Stakeholder survey and questionnaire:** ON-MERRIT will employ these instruments to assess attitudes and experiences amongst a range of stakeholders at all levels. Specific questions will be developed in a co-design model, gathering and incorporating feedback and ideas from stakeholders to inform instrument design.
- **Qualitative inquiry (QI):** Focus groups will help to gather deeper insight into interactions between the actors and stakeholders of the quadruple helix. In-depth interviews are used to understand motivation and disincentives of engagement with open science practices and how different actors make sense of open science practices in relation to personal and institutional goals. Special focus will be on early career scientists (discovery of new talents) and young entrepreneurs as well as on gender aspects.
- **Scientometrics and Text Mining:** ON-MERRIT will make use of big scholarly data resources, including scientometric data (usage and citations data) as well as full text mining, for example to identify research data and source code sharing, to understand patterns of participation and collaboration in knowledge-creation, and the relationship of impact and RRI practices. ON-MERRIT will collect and analyse several scholarly datasets to study the uptake of RRI practices and to model how the uptake of RRI practices relates to the Matthew effects in science. Where appropriate, ON-MERRIT will utilise text and data mining techniques to merge these datasets and enrich the them with gender, seniority, OA type, and other information.
- **Social Network Analysis (SNA):** ON-MERRIT will study the representation, distribution and centrality/marginality of various actors and stakeholders in the contribution and uptake of RRI resources (e.g., publications, data, software, repositories). ON-MERRIT will model structural properties of networks to identify attributes that favour or bear the potential to mitigate the Matthew effect and hence simulate a range of possible policy interventions.

Figure 3 ON-MERRIT's map of methods

ON-MERRIT's ultimate objective is to provide a set of validated practical policy and implementation recommendations and guidelines for EU, national and institutional policy-makers to support the transition to equitable RRI. They will be a valuable tool in supporting decision makers to evaluate needs for and prioritisation of supportive actions. The project will achieve this by implementing a dedicated work-package which synthesises evidential findings and maps them against current policies/indicators on European and national levels.

This will include synthesis of results from activities across the project to create **in-depth case studies** investigations of distinct groups and communities of particular relevance to RRI. Gender will be a data-point in every research task such that a wealth of data regarding the negative effects of cumulative advantage in promoting gender equity can be described from a variety of perspectives. This data will be synthesised into a comprehensive **Gender Case-Study** report. Focus across all activities on Matthew effects in RRI and Open Science transition in three key scientific disciplines of direct relevance for the Sustainable Development Goals (Agriculture, Climate Science, Health Sciences), meanwhile, will enable the construction of a further **three Disciplinary Case-Studies**. Collecting findings in this way will enable ON-MERRIT to deliver concise briefings of relevance for specific stakeholders and enable domain-specific policy recommendations.

These results will then be validated using participatory feedback mechanisms, including a final stakeholder workshop, to produce final policy recommendations for advancing a more inclusive, equitable, open and gender-sensitive science system. To raise awareness and action in response to these findings, ON-MERRIT will produce a range of resources for institutional self-assessment whereby institutions will be able to check their own status against ON-MERRIT indicators and receive tailored recommendations for improvement.

This work will take place in 3 key phases:

- **Phase 1 Background and preparation (months 1-8):** Literature research; construction of data-collection instruments; collection and preparation of datasets
- **Phase 2 Active research (months 6-24):** Conducting surveys, interviews, workshops; performing data experiments; analysing results; writing up
- **Phase 3 Synthesis and recommendations (months 22-30):** Distilling findings into case-studies; conducting validation and policy modelling activities; creating final recommendations

1.3.9 Primary research questions

Table 2. Matrix of ON-MERRIT research questions

Key: Blank = Method not used; “+” = secondary method of analysis; “++” = primary method of analysis		M e t r i c s / T D M	S N A	D e s k r e s e a r c h	S u r v e y	Q u a l i t a t i v e i n q u i r y	C a s e s t u d i e s
Research cultures	R1. Who is included and excluded with regard to a variety of RRI and Open Science elements? (Task 3.2, OU lead)	++	+	+	+		+
	R2. How does uptake of RRI and Open Science relate to training/support measures? (T3.3, UMINHO)		+	+	+	++	+
Innovation and industry	I1. How do industry actors seek information and engage with RRI and Open Science resources? (T4.2, KNOW)	+		+	++	++	+
	I2. What are levels of use of Open Science outputs in industry as revealed by patent literature? (T4.3, UGOE)	++		+			+
Policy and society	P1. How are Open Science outputs used in policy-making? (T5.2, UMINHO)	+		+	++	+	+
	P2. Which societal actors participate in RRI and Open Science policy-making? (T5.3, TU GRAZ)			+	+	++	++
Synthesis	S1. How are current RRI and Open Science incentive structures constructed at the promotion/tenure stage? (T6.1, OU)	++	+	+	++		+
	S2. What models for incentives and indicators will lead to more equitable RRI and Open Science transition? (T6.2, KNOW)		++	+			+
	S3. What is the state of play regarding RRI and Open Science Matthew effects in gender issues and three scientific disciplines directly of relevance to the sustainable development goals? (T6.3, UMINHO)	+	+	+	+	+	++
<p>ON-MERRIT recommendations (T6.4, KNOW)</p> <p>Assessment of Matthew effects in relation to current indicators (including SDGs and MoRRI)</p> <p>Suggested corrective policy actions</p> <p>Self-reflection materials for institutions and individuals</p>							

1.4 Ambition

Ground-breaking objectives: ON-MERRIT will move beyond merely enabling access and participation in principle, to systematically describe and address cumulative barriers relating to the uptake of scientific knowledge across a variety of stakeholders. ON-MERRIT will reveal any systemic drivers and consequences of cumulative advantage in current approaches to RRI and Open Science implementation. Based on these findings, it will promote viable strategies to render horizontal changes and behavioural shifts. It will go beyond the state-of-the-art by determining the core absorptive capacities required for multiple stakeholders to engage and interact with open research outputs and participative knowledge creation processes. It will create a revised framework for open and gender-sensitive inclusion, assessing roles and skill-profiles to enable individuals and organisations to best adapt to the emergent RRI landscape.

Cutting-edge approaches: ON-MERRIT will employ an ambitious, interdisciplinary methodology mixing state-of-the-art sociological investigation, such as stakeholder surveys and qualitative enquiries, with cutting-edge computational approaches, such as scientometrics, text mining and social network analysis, to examine the Matthew effect in RRI in-depth across a range of scientific disciplines and for all “quadruple helix” stakeholders. In so doing, it will improve the means of measuring the integration of RRI in science and innovation by providing evidence of blind spots and making specific policy recommendations to mitigate such factors, including new or improved indicators.

New models for inclusive policy implementation: ON-MERRIT will enable a new dimension of recursive RRI policy assessment, which remains alert to the unintended consequences of science policy actions and the systemic factors which can subvert policy intentions. Scrutinising the RRI agenda in this way speaks to the core aims of RRI itself – critical enquiry that takes account of the sociological nature of scientific endeavours and the possible unintended consequences of science policy interventions to seek the right mix of drivers and incentives to enable optimal levels of opportunity and integrity in knowledge creation.

Potential basis for new products: ON-MERRIT will produce revised and improved self-assessment tools for RRI-awareness (building on work conducted in the FP7 RRI Tools project) which will be based on the findings and conclusions of the ON-MERRIT project. Its primary research will lead also to evidence on the basis of which new approaches/indicators for RRI implementation can be further developed, updated or improved. Once these new approaches and indicators are in place, they will open a space in which new products can be developed - analogous to the way the conversation about article level metrics led to the creation of new start-ups specialising in “altmetrics”.

Sustainable and inclusive RRI and Open Science: ON-MERRIT will shine new light on the unintended consequences of policy interventions, with a special focus on how these issues relate to disciplines central to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals and Gender Equity.

2 Impact

2.1 Expected impacts

2.1.1 Expected impacts as set out in the work programme

ON-MERRIT will investigate an urgent blind-spot in RRI policy, the possible negative effects of cumulative advantage as a result of RRI and Open Science policy interventions. Creating a broad base of new evidence into these effects, across a range of societal actors and scientific domains, will clarify threats to equity and spotlight any such issues where they exist. Doing so will enable a reflexive, evidence-based appraisal of existing incentives and indicators for RRI and Open Science, upon which basis, recommendations for revised indicators and policy actions tailored to all regions and areas of research can be offered. This will support the transformation towards more equitable and open scholarship across Europe and beyond.

Through these activities, ON-MERRIT directly addresses the challenges as outlined in the Work Programme 2018-2019 Science with and for Society, under the Topic *Building the SwafS knowledge base* (SwafS-20-2018-2019). In relation to these challenges, a significant impact on several sectors and layers is expected: academic communities, researchers, research performing organisations, research funders, industry, policy-makers, as well as the general public will derive benefits. Moreover, ON-MERRIT will also assist in leveraging the defragmentation of European cultural and science policies. In the following, we respond explicitly to the Call text, summarising how ON-MERRIT will meet and exceed the expected impacts as set out under the relevant work programme topic. In addition, we highlight further areas of impact not foreseen in the topic description, but of high relevance for the SWAFS programme generally and this call topic in particular.

Work programme impact #1: Consortia should choose a basket of indicators to measure their work against. In particular, consortia should contribute to one or more of the MoRRI indicators and/or to the Sustainable Development Goals.

ON-MERRIT will directly contribute towards multiple UN Sustainable Development Goals:

- **SDG 4 Quality Education: *Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning for all:*** ON-MERRIT will contribute to these goals by enhancing understanding of incentives and barriers to participation in higher education careers. ON-MERRIT will investigate research cultures and the incentives relating to recognition and advancement, present the findings and propose changes to improve the current status quo (WP 3, 6).
- **SDG 5 Gender Equality: *Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls:*** ON-MERRIT will investigate effects of cumulative advantage related to gender at every level of its investigations across academia, industry and policy-making. The rich data accrued will enable a detailed case-study which allows a range of recommendation for action to counter gender inequality (WP 3, 4, 5, 6).
- **SDG 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth: *Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all:*** ON-MERRIT will foster economic innovation and enhance return on investment for research funding by increasing awareness and understanding of the potentials of re-use of FAIR research data and other Open Science outputs in industry (especially amongst SMEs) (WP4).
- **SDG 9 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure: *Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation:*** ON-MERRIT will highlight the extent to which scientific outcomes in adoption of RRI and Open Science are reliant on access to basic infrastructure, including technologies (tools, platforms, research equipment) and training/support services. Doing so will reveal which institutions are best placed to take advantage of the new wave of RRI and Open Science research, including which specific economic actors. Based on this, actions

to promote equity in access to scholarly infrastructure can be proposed, thus enabling new groups in academia and industry to take advantage of RRI and Open Science processes (WP 3, 4).

- **SDG 10 Reduced Inequalities: *Reduce inequality within and amongst countries:*** ON-MERRIT will assist in reducing inequality by directly addressing the causes and effects of cumulative advantage in research and innovation. ON-MERRIT will aid in the transformation towards better and more open scholarship across Europe. Its main impact shall be the selection and implementation of more transparent quality assurance and impact measurements that can be applied to all areas of research (all WPs).
- **SDG 16 Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions: *Promote just, peaceful and inclusive societies:*** ON-MERRIT will help foster reflexive awareness of potential unintended consequences of science policy and ensure that participation in the world of research and innovation depends only on merit (all WPs).

In addition, the three ON-MERRIT case-study disciplines (Agriculture, Health, Climate) have been chosen specifically for their relevance to the Sustainable Development Goals. By undertaking research into barriers to participation in and exploitation of open scientific outputs, ON-MERRIT will hence enable more equitable and efficient research to address:

- **SDG 2 Zero Hunger:** End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture
- **SDG 3 Good Health and Well-Being:** Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages
- **SDG 13 Climate Action:** Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts

ON-MERRIT will also directly contribute towards promoting and refining multiple **MoRRI indicators**⁸⁶:

- **Governance GOV1-3:** ON-MERRIT will contribute to the responsible oversight of the RRI agenda by testing whether current efforts impact inequalities across a variety of stakeholders/domains (academia, industry, policy-making) (WPs 3, 4, 5). The project will contribute to understanding and developing governance mechanisms for RRI within research-performing organizations (academia and industry) (WPs 5, 6). By enhancing understanding of RRI mechanisms, ON-MERRIT will promote the standing of academia and research in relation to policymakers and the general public and point towards strategies of mitigating extant inequalities (WPs 3, 4, 5, 6)
- **Open Access/Open Science OA1-6:** ON-MERRIT stands to help achieve key Open Access goals by highlighting the extent to which uptake of research results correlates with support, training and policy measures (WP3, 6). Outlook reports and targeted policy briefs will inform key stakeholders of the outcomes (WP 2, 3, 4, 5, 6). Work on stratification in Open Access publishing and FAIR data-sharing will enable any needed corrective policy measures and enhance understanding of barriers and incentives for Open Access and Open Science
- **Gender GE1-5:** ON-MERRIT will strengthen awareness and implementation of gender-sensitivity across a range of areas. It will support active policy-making to counter horizontal gender segregation of researchers by enhancing understanding of gender-related barriers to participation in academia such as unequal opportunities for promotions, research funding, and visibility of research outputs. It will examine gender-aspects of industry and societal uptake of RRI and Open Science resources (WP 4, 5). ON-MERRIT will thereby contribute to the glass ceiling index (all WPs).
- **Public Engagement PE1-4:** ON-MERRIT will contribute to understanding the structural barriers to societal engagement and participation of societal actors in research, innovation and policy-making. It will develop and enhance existing models of public participation (WP 5). ON-MERRIT will enhance understanding of information-seeking behaviours of societal stakeholders and their participation preferences, engage relevant (civil-society) stakeholders via surveys, workshops and co-design activities as well as contribute to the R&I democratization index (PE9)

⁸⁶ MoRRI project (2018) The evolution of Responsible Research and Innovation in Europe: The MoRRI indicators report. http://www.technopolis-group.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/D4.3_Revised_20022018_clean.pdf

- **Science literacy SLSE2-3:** ON-MERRIT will provide data on how RRI-related aspects in training relate to the success of young researchers (WP 3, 6). It will enhance understanding of the familiarity of researchers with RRI and Open Science principles (WP 3). Through disciplinary case studies on Matthew effects related to RRI the project will contribute to understanding science communication culture

Work programme impact #2: Research and Innovation outcomes should help build effective cooperation between science and society

ON-MERRIT will strengthen the understanding of public engagement with science and technology by studying the bonds between research, the public and policy-making (WP 5). This will be linked to specific case-studies on RRI in scientific controversies that have immediate relevance for the SDGs (Agriculture, Climate, and Health). ON-MERRIT will enhance understanding of Matthew effects related to public participation in policy making and assess levels of reuse of RRI knowledge amongst multiple societal stakeholders to gauge current uptake (WP 3, 4, 5). ON-MERRIT's transdisciplinary approach (inclusion of quadruple helix actors in co-design of experiments, knowledge production and assessment of barriers and rewards/incentives) will ensure broad outreach and engagement with multiple civil-society stakeholders.

Moreover, the Lisbon Treaty states in Article 11 par. 1 “*The institutions shall, by appropriate means, give citizens and representative associations the opportunity to make known and publicly exchange their views in all areas of Union action*”. Opening policy research and providing methods and tools (i.e. “appropriate means”) to participate will contribute to the compliance with Article 11. Par. 1. “Institutions” means the European Institutions Parliament, Council and Commission. ON-MERRIT will contribute to this objective by developing a more complete scientific evidence-base on barriers for citizens and civil society to participate in research and policy making in WPs 3 and 5 as well as through developing recommendations in WP 6 and engaging with multiple stakeholders throughout in WP2. In general, by ensuring a reflexive transition to RRI and Open Science based on recursive reflection on the extent to which such policy measures might unintentionally exacerbate existing inequalities, ON-MERRIT will contribute to an RRI system most responsive to the needs of society.

Work programme impact #3: Research and Innovation outcomes should foster the recruitment of new talent for science

ON-MERRIT will identify policy and support measures that will aid in achieving a more equitable scientific system that rewards based on merit rather than cumulative advantage (WP 6). As such, a long-term aim is to make scientific careers more attractive by understanding the needs of new talents for science, especially women, early career researchers, and young entrepreneurs (WP 3). Facilitating co-creation activities will harness stakeholder ideas and energy to drive excellence in ON-MERRIT. Promoting the re-use of research by all societal and economic actors will further help science escape the ivory tower and broaden science as a subject for all.

Work programme impact #4: Research and Innovation outcomes should pair scientific excellence with social awareness and responsibility

Social awareness and responsibility are at the heart of ON-MERRIT. The project will ensure scientific excellence via interactive research methods that allow stakeholder co-design and participation (WP 2). All actions will bespeak the highest standards of ethics and research integrity. Openness is built into ON-MERRIT with consortium members strongly rooted in RRI and Open Science communities and multiple synergies with existing RRI and Open Science initiatives (OpenUP, FIT4RRI, OpenAIRE, OpenMinTeD, FOSTER). Gender issues with respect to cumulative (dis)advantage in academia are studied throughout the project (WP 2, 3, 4, 5, 6) and will be a key part of the recommendations/indicators that are developed (WP

6). Moreover, ON-MERRIT's case-studies focus on disciplines directly related to key Sustainable Development Goals (WP 3, 4, 5, 6). Finally, through implementing meta-research on the impact of RRI while adhering to its principles, ON-MERRIT will contribute to a reflexive approach to RRI transition which remains alert to the possible unintended consequences of policy interventions and will contribute a high-level understanding of the barriers and incentives for participation in research and barriers to research and innovation more generally.

In addition to the goals listed above, Open Science and RRI will benefit from a demonstrated extension of research on Matthew effects in science, thereby facilitating the transition to Open Science. ON-MERRIT will thereby contribute to establishing the EU as leader in the domain of Open Science through ongoing engagement with RRI and Open Science initiatives (WP 2) and co-creation activities pertaining to the use-cases (WP 3, 4, 5). ON-MERRIT will achieve this, for example, by co-creating Open Science and RRI indicators and self-assessment tools for industry and academia and exploring how openness can be enabled in academia-industry-collaborations. For academia, ON-MERRIT will co-create briefings on RRI and Open Science indicators which can be used for promotion assessments. It will also study career promotion policies as well as patterns of cumulative (dis)advantage pertaining to RRI and Open Science principles (WP 3). In addition, ON-MERRIT will assess the extent to which researchers are familiar with Open Science and RRI.

Work programme impact #5: Successful proposals should foresee scientific and other types of publication

ON-MERRIT will enable ground-breaking outputs in multiple domains. In addressing leading-edge issues in inclusion in meta-research it will ensure excellence in (at least) six foreseen peer-reviewed scientific outputs across a range of disciplines. Perhaps more importantly, however, the work will bespeak the Open Science and RRI principles it seeks to investigate, and thus the project will adopt a philosophy of *continuous communication, engagement and participation*, including regular blogs and other grey-literature publications, co-creation activities which will harness user knowledge while also educating about ON-MERRIT's aims and results, and publication venues targeted to specific stakeholders (trade magazines for industry, science policy websites for policy-makers, etc.). Moreover, the project workflow will be opened to the extent possible, including publication of this research proposal, research study protocols, data, code, workflows and more (WP 2), but in addressing leading-edge issues in inclusion in meta-research it will ensure excellence in eight foreseen peer-reviewed scientific outputs across a range of disciplines. Close connections to networks for RRI initiatives, young researchers, SME clusters, and Open Science infrastructure and policy initiatives will ensure a broad reach for project findings (WP 2, see sec. 3.4 for more information on related networks).

2.1.2 Substantial impacts not mentioned in the work programme

In addition, ON-MERRIT will have impact across a range of areas not specified in the *Building the SwafS knowledge base* (SwafS-20-2018-2019) call, but of direct relevance for the aims of either the *Science with and for Society Work Programme 2018-2019* or for the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme more generally.

Enhance innovation capacity and create new market opportunities

The potential for growth through the re-use of research data by economic actors is a major driver behind policy actions to implement FAIR data. Yet understanding of how (or even if) industry players engage with Open Science resources is very low. Investigating this area will reveal the state-of-play and thus allow recommendations for further actions to stimulate this activity, enhancing Europe's innovation capacity.

New models for interdisciplinary investigation in RRI and Open Science policy

ON-MERRIT will employ an ambitious, interdisciplinary methodology mixing state-of-the-art sociological investigation, such as stakeholder surveys and qualitative enquiries, with cutting-edge computational approaches, such as scientometrics, text mining and social network analysis, to examine the Matthew effect in RRI in-depth across a range of scientific disciplines and for all “quadruple helix” stakeholders. In so doing, it will improve the means of measuring the integration of RRI in science and innovation by providing evidence of blind spots and making specific policy recommendations to mitigate such factors, including new or improved indicators.

Reflexivity in Research and Innovation

Through implementing meta-research on the impact of RRI while adhering to its principles, ON-MERRIT will contribute to a high-level understanding of the barriers and incentives for participation in research and barriers to research and innovation more generally. Such a recursive, self-critical approach bespeaks the principles of RRI.

RRI and Open Science training and policies

ON-MERRIT will improve levels of knowledge regarding policies and training practices, assessing the practical application of RRI and Open Science on researcher’s workflows and identifying which RRI and Open Science principles are reinforced by institutional policies. ON-MERRIT’s analysis and recommendations on institutional training and policies will assist in an evidence-based transformation of research-performing organization governance to be consistent with RRI and Open Science practices.

2.1.3 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for impact

To facilitate the EC’s evaluation of the impact of ON-MERRIT, a set of *key performance indicators (KPIs)* has been developed. The KPIs take careful consideration of expected results and EC expectations, and seek to set concrete goals that avoid ambiguity. The following considerations have been taken into account: going beyond economic growth; measuring the effectiveness on public policies; including short-term and long-term dimensions of impact; being based on evidence; and including policy context. The listed KPIs will be used for project internal management and monitoring, and for reporting to the EC. Periodic activity reports will report results related to these indicators to provide evidence that project activities are progressing effectively and, where necessary, to implement corrective actions.

Table 2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for impact

Impact KPI	Success measure	Success target
Research and Innovation		
Research networks	Direct communication with existing RRI and Open Science initiatives, number of initiatives engaged	30
Open deliverables	Public deliverables will be published immediately upon delivery to EC, with a CC BY on the project website and archived via Zenodo	16 of 20 deliverable made immediately publicly available
Re-usable research outputs	Number of re-usable datasets and items of code published for re-use using open licenses (via, e.g., Zenodo)	5
Engagement with researchers (especially early)	Number of researchers reached	1000 via in-depth surveys, 30 via qualitative interviews

career researchers)		
Engagement with policy-makers and RRI practitioners	Number of policy-makers and RRI practitioners reached	500 via in-depth survey, 30 via qualitative interviews, 18 via intensive stakeholder participation workshops
Industry engagement	Number of industry stakeholders reached	500 via survey, 10 via on-site qualitative interviews
RRI indicators	Minimum number of concrete recommendations for improvement of RRI indicators to avert Matthew effects	5
Management		
Research quality	Max % of deliverables for which the EC requests resubmission following project reviews	10
Resources	Max % deviation from original resource assignment	10
Deadlines	Max number of days of justified delay in submitting deliverables	40
Dissemination		
Conferences	Number of dissemination actions (abstracts, papers, presentations, workshops) in highly-regarded (international and peer-reviewed) conferences	8
OA Publications	Number of project publications in well-regarded peer-reviewed venues, and made Open Access (green or gold)	5
Co-creation activities	Number of co-creation activities conducted with stakeholders	4
Societal impact		
Benefits	Blog posts in popular community venues on issues of cumulative advantage in research, industry, policy	3
Influence	Stakeholder communities interested in ON-MERRIT	50
Knowledge transfer	Number of followers for project Twitter account	1000 by project's end

2.1.4 Overcoming barriers for impact

ON-MERRIT has identified the following potential barriers which could limit the impact of the project, and either planned precautionary actions to be implemented or identified corrective actions which will occur should the barrier be faced.

Table 3 Barriers to impact

Barrier	Precautionary or corrective action
<p>Reluctance to participate and share data/results ON-MERRIT's impact would be at risk should major stakeholder groups prove reluctant to engage with our co-design, participation and validation activities. Should this prove the case, then ON-MERRIT's evidence-base, conclusions and recommendations could be at risk of having failed to fully engage with the issues it represents, and so fail to be fully taken-up by the target communities.</p>	<p>ON-MERRIT should anticipate reluctance among the general population to participate in research and innovation (i.e., no public interest in co-creation and co-development). To counteract this, co-design and community participation is built into ON-MERRIT from the ground up. Such activities will be coordinated via a specific task in WP2, and constant evaluation (including via Deliverables and Milestones) will ensure ON-MERRIT can take an agile approach to corrective actions if necessary. Measures are described in the risk analysis section of this document.</p>
<p>Null, negative or inconclusive results It could be that across one or more of the ambitious number of ON-MERRIT research activities, no negative Matthew effects are discovered. In this case, the potential impact of the work might be thought to be under threat.</p>	<p>The goal of science is to advance through hypothesis and investigation. Understanding that Matthew effects are in fact not in operation in (specific areas of) RRI and Open Science would do much to galvanise current approaches and demonstrate the worth of current indicators. Nonetheless, the ON-MERRIT team believe that all results, whether positive, null, negative or inconclusive, should be equally reported to avoid publication bias.</p>
<p>Reflexivity of cumulative advantage ('Winners' reluctance') Resistance by stakeholders who benefit from the situation as it is now should be expected. Reluctance towards RRI and Open Science more generally among the relevant populations can also be anticipated, as well as opposition towards re-use of results (e.g. because of existing IPRs for the relevant institutions, such as SMEs and universities)</p>	<p>This understandable reaction can be combated via leveraging networks within industry, academia and policy-making to foster openness and dialogue to seek sustainable solutions. Hence, ON-MERRIT's communication strategy focuses on fostering awareness, understanding and trust in the issues and evidence, and then promoting actions based on this. The strategy of stakeholder participation and validation further seeks to include all stakeholders.</p>
<p>Language Language could be an issue in the dissemination and uptake of results.</p>	<p>The ON-MERRIT consortium already incorporates native-speaker in English, German, Spanish, Portuguese, Greek, Italian, Czech, Croatian and French. Our close links to international networks (e.g., OpenAIRE NOADs, Eurodoc) further mean we can call upon contacts for assistance with translating crucial briefing documents into other languages.</p>

2.2 Measures to maximise impact

ON-MERRIT will generate a wealth of new evidence regarding the dangers of Matthew effects in RRI and Open Science transition (including disciplinary and gender aspects), which will be used to create practical

recommendations for policy actions and best-practices (especially recommendations for revised RRI and Open Science incentives and indicators). The aim is to achieve a more equitable transition to RRI and Open Science through amendments to policies and practices at various levels, amongst various stakeholders, based on a solid foundation of evidence-based analysis.

Hence, maximal impact of project results will only be achieved to the extent that key stakeholders are aware of ON-MERRIT activities and results, understand the issues, trust the quality of the evidence and policy analyses, and act based on key recommendations.

The ON-MERRIT *Dissemination, valorisation and participation plan (D2.1)*, delivered in month 6, will set out in detail how such awareness, understanding, trust and action will be ensured. Dissemination and communication will follow the standard approach of PLAN, ACT, OBSERVE, REFLECT, which is common to all mature dissemination and marketing strategies.

- **Plan:** ON-MERRIT, through the dissemination leader, will plan a series of activities, following the “*who?, what?, why?, when?, how?*” approach: Who will be targeted? (stakeholder breakdown), What will be disseminated? (knowledge, results, training, etc.), Why does the stakeholder want to know this?, Why does the project want the stakeholder informed? When is the project going to be ready to disseminate this?, How should these results best be communicated, at this time, to this stakeholder for this purpose?
- **Act:** ON-MERRIT will undertake planned actions in line with the *Dissemination, valorisation and participation plan*, the urgency of the organisation and the positioning of the organisations and individuals concerned.
- **Observe:** ON-MERRIT will develop an extensive set of key performance indicators (a summary of indicative KPIs is shown below). KPIs will exist for breadth and depth of coverage (number of stakeholder segments reached, level of understanding gained), and the comprehensiveness of the campaign (all scientific and exploitable results disseminated).
- **Reflect:** The dissemination manager will update the plan periodically, based on the feedback received and impact achieved.

In the following we present the draft ON-MERRIT plan for dissemination and exploitation of project results, including (1) key stakeholders, (2) strategies for achieving awareness, understanding, trust and action, communication activities

2.2.1 Key stakeholders

Exposing key audiences, (academic communities, researchers, funders, industry, policy-makers, society at large) to ON-MERRIT activities and outputs will be crucial to maximising its impact. The expertise of the project consortium and the knowledge transfer within the RRI and Open Science communities ensure that ON-MERRIT has an acute understanding of the relevant stakeholders in research, industry, policy-making and societal settings. This will be further enhanced through the outreach and co-creation activities during the project building on the individual skills and community memberships of the project partners. Moreover, embedding ON-MERRIT within the landscape of past and ongoing RRI and Open Science activities will be essential for impact, both in terms of engaging and leveraging established networks of actors already familiar with and invested in these topics, but also for ensuring synergies and avoiding overlaps with former work and activities of related projects. The intended impact of the dissemination strategy will cut across several areas which are considered crucial to the successful exploitation of ON-MERRIT’s outcomes. In particular this will target training and policy recommendations, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 ON-MERRIT Target Stakeholders

Stakeholder	Areas	Description	Outreach Champion
Research performing institutions	Education, Research	Researchers or support staff in academic institutions who engage in RRI and Open Science education and training, and/or oversee research	UMINHO, UGOE

		assessment criteria for hiring and promotion	
Young scholars	Research	Early career researchers who benefit from guidance and advice on RRI and Open Science practices, and related benefits and challenges	UGOE, UMINHO
Senior researchers	Research	Senior academics of influence whose voices can be engaged to provide crucial feedback and amplify messages	KNOW
Local, national and EU policy makers and funders	Policy makers	Decision-makers of governmental and funding agencies that design interventions and funding programmes related to RRI and Open Science, at national, European and international levels	UMINHO, UGOE, TU GRAZ
Societal actors	Society	Stakeholders and civil society actors, especially those who engage in Agriculture, Climate, and Health	TU GRAZ
SMEs and start-ups	Industry	Economic actors of various sizes who can be engaged in the uptake of RRI and Open Science resources to stimulate economic activity	KNOW
Publishers	Industry, Research	Publishers who engage in activities that support RRI and Open Science and the reassessment of relevant publishing-related metrics and indicators	KNOW, UGOE
RRI and Open Science practitioners and researchers	Research	Existing networks and initiatives actively working to support or research issues related to RRI and Open Science implementation	OU, UGOE

2.2.2 Strategies for achieving awareness, understanding, trust and action

We said above that maximal impact of project results will only be achieved to the extent that key stakeholders are *aware* of ON-MERRIT activities and results, *understand* the issues, *trust* the quality of the evidence and policy analyses, and *act* based on key recommendations. We next detail the overall strategies ON-MERRIT will adopt to ensure this is achieved.

2.2.2.1 Ensuring awareness

The first step in creating awareness of ON-MERRIT and its outputs will be the creation of an engaging project identity (including logo and graphical layout guidelines) to create a strong and recognizable ON-MERRIT brand and key messages to be used on all dissemination material. Various channels will be engaged here, including project website and blog, social media accounts, various media outlets, as well as audience-specific channels (e.g., policy briefs for policy makers), in addition to more traditional dissemination via conferences, workshops and scientific journals. Stakeholders will be presented with the results of the project and continuously informed about the project and its progress through dedicated blog posts, social media, and the project website. The process of arousing attention in the project has already begun at the preparation of the application stage. A large number of existing networks and initiatives actively working to support or research issues related to RRI and Open Science implementation have already been contacted informed on the project, asked to contribute to the pilot project and to sign a Letter of Support. The overwhelming support of these communities for ON-MERRIT is reflected in the range of Letters of Support received.

2.2.2.2 Ensuring understanding

ON-MERRIT will ensure understanding of the issues by tailoring key messages for specific audiences and disseminating them via the channels most likely to reach that group. Industry players expect a different style of presentation and language than policy-makers, for example. Moreover, it is essential to provide the right level of depth to engage the audience to discover and learn more without burdening them with unneeded detail. This targeting and framing of messages will be supported by ensuring references to rich information resources via the project website, with links to sources of further information (including project deliverable reports, other project outputs, as well as third-party material). Regional uptake will of course be aided by the translation of essential briefing documents and infographics into languages other than English where possible. Finally, but perhaps most importantly, ON-MERRIT’s participatory methodologies, which include stakeholders in research design, data-collection, meaning-making and validation processes, will not only aid in the communication of key messages, but also engage these stakeholders in critically reflecting for themselves upon the issues at hand. Table 5 below shows the main proposed communication methods for each stakeholder group.

Table 5 Proposed main communication methods per target stakeholder

Target audience groups	Proposed main communication channels
RRI and Open Science practitioners and researchers	Partner networks, conferences and events, peer-reviewed journals, mailing lists
Research performing institutions	Self-reflection instruments, briefing documents, online courses, videos, mailing lists
Young scholars	Blog and online media, conferences and events, online courses, peer-reviewed journals, mailing lists
Senior researchers	Conferences and events, interviews and workshops, online media, peer-reviewed journals, mailing lists
Local, national and EU policy-makers and funders	Policy briefings, face-to-face meetings, interviews and workshops, events
Societal actors	General media (via press releases), blogs and online media, online courses, newsletter, videos, special interest groups
SMEs and start-ups	Industry events, industry media, online self-reflection tool
Publishers	Industry events, industry media, mailing lists

2.2.2.3 Ensuring trust

ON-MERRIT will ensure trust in results by embodying the RRI and Open Science principles it espouses. It will make its research aims, methods, data and outputs FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable) via innovative open science and science communication platforms and tools. The project will establish a presence on the Open Science Framework platform, which will function as a project collaboration environment as well as a platform for publishing non-traditional research outputs. This will happen right from the start, with the publication of this project proposal upon its acceptance for funding by the European Commission. Continuous project updates and stakeholder feedback will be delivered via a regularly updated project blog, which will become the primary dissemination point for preliminary results and first findings. Adherence to the EC’s Open Access and Research Data Management policies will ensure that all research publications and the fullest extent of the research data gathered, are made openly accessible to all. All software and code, including that needed to reproduce project results, will be suitably and sustainably archived and made available for re-use. Trust will also be maintained by the sustainability and visibility of the research results, including after the project’s lifetime, via the project website and the re-use of ON-MERRIT resources by continuing initiatives.

2.2.2.4 Ensuring action

By engaging stakeholders right from the start, leveraging existing networks, and targeting messages for specific audiences, the ON-MERRIT dissemination and exploitation plan will set the scene for the effective uptake of results. Through the creation of a transparent basis of evidence, ON-MERRIT will then be able to offer trusted analyses and policy recommendations – the latter strengthened by computational modelling of policy scenarios to optimise outcomes. These results will then be disseminated via tailored communication of practical guidelines, policy briefs, factsheets, white papers, academic papers, infographics, self-reflection tools, and calls-to-action for specific stakeholders. A final project workshop in project month 28 will target all stakeholder groups in an interactive discussion of project results and their implications.

2.2.3 Stakeholder engagement strategy

ON-MERRIT’s success will depend on the extent to which stakeholders engage with and participate in project activities. Target groups will be approached at various levels as listed in Table 6 below. ON-MERRIT will work at each level progressively. The table briefly outlines the dissemination aims, methods and stakeholders of each level.

Table 6 Dissemination network-building strategy

Dissemination Aims	Methods and Activities	Examples of measures
Level 1: ON-MERRIT internal communication		
Link and bring together people working on similar topics across consortium, in order to create working groups that will implement common activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review profiles and interests of partner teams across consortium - Organise team building sessions within project meetings - Organise dedicated WP team meetings within plenary or ad hoc meetings - Establish virtual communication and collaboration tools for consortium members - Set up internal mailing list for project and key activities - Prepare guidelines, templates and reference spaces for dissemination activities and materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop document with dissemination guidelines and practices - Collect CVs of all team members at shared space - Carry out team member interviews for project web site and blog posts - Organise dedicated vision building session within Kick Off and after each review meeting - Establish main use case members’ mailing lists
Create single point of reference for all dissemination material and practices across consortium		
Establish communication mechanisms and channels within consortium		
Facilitate and support direct collaboration and information sharing among partners		
Provide good guidelines and materials for dissemination activities planning, implementation and reporting		
Set up continuous communication mechanisms and channels to share ON-MERRIT progress with relevant people		
Level 2: Towards core target groups through direct networks		
Establish links with relevant networks and communities of scientists that partners are involved in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organise special training and hands on sessions or workshops at events where communities gather (i.e., Partnerday@KNOW, organized yearly by KNOW for 50+ industry partners) - Provide online access to training material 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study implementation priorities of connected networks and identify challenges, data, tools and potential pilots of high visibility/importance - Organise ON-MERRIT sessions at major stakeholder gatherings
Organise targeted actions to inform and engage scientists in the networks and communities where partners have direct access to		
Create links and synergies with relevant initiatives where partners are involved		

<p>Take advantage of open data and open research initiatives and movements where partners are involved</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consider creating ad hoc working groups related with networks of relevance - Use online channels and social-media to create awareness in existing networks - Integrate practitioners and CSOs skills in training activities - utilising considerable skills and experiences of consortium in outreach, public engagement and stakeholder consultation 	<p>(i.e., Partnerday@KNOW)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organise training/ awareness webinars - Organise ON-MERRIT workshops or sessions at RRI and Open Science events - Utilise engagement in other activities e.g. FIT4RRI, OpenAIRE, OpenMinTeD, FOSTER
Level 3: Towards other stakeholders and decision-makers		
<p>Establish links with new RRI and Open Science research projects and initiatives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Join or organise clustering events with coordinators of research projects - Visit key institutions - Meet with project coordinators - Reach out through targeted messages and channels - Organise online challenges and social media campaigns - Prepare information material for decision makers - Organise press campaigns for public media - Actively invite policy-makers, -advisors and intermediary actors to contribute to ON-MERRIT events - Loop-back findings of ongoing research to integrate stakeholder experiences and skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborate with other SwafS projects - Organise training and awareness visits to targeted key institutions in partners' countries - Organise training and awareness missions to regions and institutions of strategic importance - Organise workshops and events together with other related projects - Organise ON-MERRIT representation and booths in major conferences and exhibitions - Prepare press releases for distribution in all partner countries
<p>Organise targeted actions to inform and engage scientists, publishers, SMEs, policy-makers, societal actors and others providers outside the partner networks</p>		
<p>Carry out actions targeting institutions and networks of strategic importance</p>		
<p>Promote project outcomes and opportunities to related start-ups to engage further</p>		
<p>Promote project outcomes of relevance to RRI and Open Science stakeholders</p>		
<p>Inform funding agencies, donors, decision makers</p>		
<p>Inform general public</p>		

2.2.4 Communication activities

Throughout the project, continuous and inclusive communication activities will increase awareness of ON-MERRIT's goals and progress, as well as help to promote the discussion about the ongoing RRI and Open Science transition. For this aim, WP 2 will specify the communication strategy in the first six months of the project, detailing measures to be implemented and by whom. For achieving awareness, understanding, trust and action, the following main objectives will be critical for ON-MERRIT's communication efforts:

- Establish a clear set of agreed external communication messages,
- Convene a welcoming, barrier-free and constructive public discussion,
- Promote inclusiveness and diversity in academia, industry and society.

To ensure civil conversation within and outside the project consortium, the communication strategy will be backed by a Code of Conduct which outlines expectations as well as consequences for violating it from the start of the project. The effectiveness of ON-MERRIT’s communication strategy will be evaluated twice a year within WP2. The Project Management Board (i.e., Work Package leaders, see sec. 3.3.1) will also regularly address communication issues in its monthly meetings. Both measures will assist ON-MERRIT in:

- Identifying key persons and initiatives, how they engage with RRI and Open Science, and what communication channels and venues they use,
- Informing ON-MERRIT’s participatory processes and co-creation activities,
- Refining key messages.

ON-MERRIT will use a multi-channel approach where different communication mediums will be used to achieve impact. Table 7 summarises the communication means, grouped by types of activities.

Table 7 ON-MERRIT Communication and dissemination plan

What	How	Why
Internal communication <i>Aim: Effective communication across the consortium to coordinate actions/activities and mitigate risks</i>		
Private communication channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create and moderate Slack channels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Support structured yet informal communication to align and support joint tasks
Internal news briefing via email	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Led by Dissemination and participation WP lead, a summary of events, outreach, public discussions will be sent out once or twice a semester 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Transparency among consortium about all outreach and communication activities
Promotion and participation <i>Aim: Ensure broad awareness of project aim and activities within stakeholder communities, and motivate stakeholders to take part in processes of co-design and validation</i>		
Project website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Webpage and highlights from news 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Awareness of project activities ● Create strong project identity for stakeholders
Social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create a comprehensive social media strategy via a range of channels ● Timely promotion and discussion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Daily interaction with key stakeholders, particularly in academia ● Highlighting ON-MERRIT’s progress
Leaflets, postcards, stickers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital and physical presentation of value-based branding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Visual, short messaging to raise awareness
Factsheets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Summarise key objectives and findings ● Create and include infographics that visually support key messages and facts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Effective advocacy

Cross-promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Invite RRI and Open Science initiatives to work together in promoting the project's progress (digital and joint event attendance) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increasing visibility ● Liaising with related initiatives e.g. OpenAIRE, FIT4RRI, RDA to support and promote the aligned objectives
Blog	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Write and share regular blog posts about project's progress and related developments including opportunities to comment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Activating the community ● Gathering feedback for co-creation activities
Discussion sessions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organise and convene Twitter live chats ● Organise and convene webinars ● Organise and convene sessions in RRI and Open Science events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engaging with targeted communities ● Gathering feedback for co-creation activities
Social Coding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create and maintain ON-MERRIT GitHub account ● Share source code and data of ON-MERRIT's quantitative analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engaging with targeted communities ● Providing a feedback mechanism for data analytics (issue tracker) ● Incentivizing source code and data contributions (pull requests)
Dissemination <i>Aim: Effective knowledge-transfer to educate and inform stakeholders regarding project results and their implications, and enable the re-use of project outputs</i>		
Peer-reviewed publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Submit articles to relevant peer-reviewed journals or conference proceedings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Publicize ON-MERRIT research results and disseminate ON-MERRIT findings to a wide academic audience ● Enable discussion, feedback and criticism
FAIR data-sets and code	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Make datasets and code created as a result of ON-MERRIT research (from surveys, web-mining, etc.) openly accessible via open repositories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enable trust in research integrity ● Enable reproducibility of results ● Enable data re-use (via open licensing)
Conference and poster presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Present and publicize research results at topic-related conferences ● Engage and discuss results with peers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Disseminate early results to receive feedback from peers and provoke discussion of and interest in ON-MERRIT amongst different research and practitioner communities
Briefing papers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Collaboratively write briefing papers (1 per year) ● Publish them on the ON-MERRIT website and circulate among the stakeholder network (e.g. ministries, NGOs, funding agencies etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Make ON-MERRIT results on Matthew effects in Open Science and RRI accessible to policy-makers, national and regional officials, funding agencies and other non-academic stakeholders
Media engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Issue press releases to accompany major project milestones/research findings ● Publish them on the ON-MERRIT website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Make ON-MERRIT results accessible to the wider public ● Ensure pertinent messages are

	and circulate among press outlets	targeted to specific stakeholder communities and specialist presses
Science shops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up mediators between ON-MERRIT and civil society stakeholders, e.g. at the academic partner institutions to facilitate interaction between ON-MERRIT and civil society organisations/stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Respond to civil society's needs for expertise and knowledge Provide participatory research support in response to civil society's concerns Promote public access to ON-MERRIT's research activities Enhance the skills of students, civil society representatives and researchers We acknowledge that the effectiveness of this communication strategy depends on the performance of third parties that are not officially aligned to the project. To compensate, we will immediately begin to engage Science Shops to ensure sufficient time to organise this.
Self-reflection tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Draft and commission self-reflection tools (e.g. in the form of short self-assessment questionnaires) and distribute them among ON-MERRIT's stakeholder network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To stimulate uptake of ON-MERRIT's research among e.g. academia and industry To stimulate engagement with RRI and Open Science objectives

For the first year the following areas will be priorities within ON-MERRIT's agile communications roadmap (to be further developed in D2.1 Dissemination, valorisation and participation plan, due M6):

- Establish a communications plan, aligned closely to project objectives and milestones. This plan will agree on a number of small 'campaigns' to communicate activities of the project.
- Agree on a set of communication objectives e.g. "ON-MERRIT supports science done right" "Ethical workflows within the academic workflow"
- Set up a dedicated focus group within the project to discuss communication issues on a bi-monthly basis. Identify champions within the target group (Academia, Industry, Policy and Society) to join this group to review, adjust and refine communication activities. The focus group will also provide valuable feedback on the communication strategy. The project advisory board will also be invited to join.
- Dissemination strategy: ensure that all deliverables and project outputs are appropriately promoted.
- Exploitation strategy: ensure that (1) all project deliverables, publications, presentations, and posters are internally shared via, for example, a sharing platform such as Owncloud or the Open Science Framework and (2) there is an established workflow for publishing via e.g. Zenodo, the FOSTER portal and Slideshare. Usage statistics will be monitored and used for measuring the performance of the dissemination and communication activities.

Experiences made will provide a meaningful basis for adjusting and optimising communication efforts in the second and third years of the project.

2.2.5 Key performance indicators (KPI) for dissemination and communication activities

In order to measure the impact of our activities and success of our dissemination communication efforts, quantified measures for monitoring progress and results will be established from the start. This will assist in prioritising and sharing the work effectively.

Some of the below KPIs are baseline activities such as factsheets and will feed directly into the targets the project needs to achieve. Other KPIs are intentionally meant to achieve impact within the communication strategy as a whole and will be refined in line with the communication roadmap, e.g. promotion campaigns. The progress of KPI targets will be shared within the consortium on a quarterly basis. Table 8 lists ON-MERRIT's KPIs for impact.

Table 8 ON-MERRIT Impact Key Performance Indicators

KPI description	KPI target
Internal communication	
Workspace engagement	Weekly usage of internal collaboration and communication channels by all project members
Number of internal news briefings via email	Six internal news briefings
Promotion and participation	
Reference of the ON-MERRIT values on another website	At least two RRI and Open Science initiatives positively refer to ON-MERRIT's communication values
Factsheets dissemination	At least four factsheets created and shared on the website as well as directly sent to at least 10 European and national policy bodies
Participation in policy consultations	At least four invitations to contribute to RRI and Open Science policy development
Social media engagement	Daily engagement with ON-MERRIT via Twitter; 1.000 Followers at the end of the project; 10 Twitter campaigns (e.g., conference live tweeting, Twitter discussions with novices and experts)
Joint RRI and Open Science campaigns	At least three joint promotional campaigns with related initiatives (e.g., SPARC Europe, OpenAIRE, FIT4RRI, FOSTER)
Blog activity	Monthly blog posts including cross-posts and news items
Dissemination	
Sharing of dissemination outputs	100 % immediate open access to all dissemination outputs, publications and datasets
Reference in RRI and Open Science policy documents	At least two policy documents refer to ON-MERRIT outputs
Peer-reviewed publications accepted	At least five peer-reviewed journal or conference proceedings articles presenting project results (e.g., Science and Public Policy, Research Evaluation, PLOS One, PeerJ, Science Technology and Human Values,

	Journal of Responsible Innovation, Sustainability (Switzerland), Publications, F1000Research, Ethics and Information Technology) and made Open Access (green or gold)
Conference speaking engagement	At least eight public presentations/posters at topic-related conferences or workshops (e.g., Elpub, LIBER, Science and Technology Indicators (STI), EuroScience Open Forum (ESOF), ASIS&T, EASST, ESA)
Special sessions and hands-on trainings at international conferences	At least two sessions run in conjunction with major events
Access to online educational materials	At least three webinars on ON-MERRIT themes via the website and re-used by others (e.g., FOSTER); at least two pro-active contributions to existing educational materials / platforms (e.g., Open Science MOOC, FOSTER)
Outreach to policy and decision makers informing about project activities, outcomes, successes, societal impact	1 outreach item (briefing memo/blog post/news item in relevant venue) per year informing scientific communities and networks; 1 outreach item per year informing funding agencies and donors (e.g. project officers, unit directors); 1 outreach item per year informing national and regional government officials (e.g. scientific advisors, officials in Ministries of Science and Technology, etc.)
Networking with RRI and Open Science initiatives	Consultations with / visits to at least 15 related initiatives
ON-MERRIT FAIR datasets and code archived and made available via open repositories	At least 5 datasets or code objects made available with open licenses to enable re-use and reproducibility

2.2.6 *Exploitation pathways*

ON-MERRIT's dissemination plan will be inherently linked to and shaped around the valorisation/exploitation goals of the project. ON-MERRIT will undertake all dissemination actions with reference to the needs of the identified target audiences, relevant project results and the impact of past dissemination efforts. ON-MERRIT dissemination activities and tools (website, posters, blog posts, publications, etc.) will be subject to continuous updates and shaped to facilitate the exploitation of project results during and after the lifetime of ON-MERRIT.

The ON-MERRIT Dissemination, valorisation and participation plan (D2.1), delivered in month 6, will set out in detail how such understanding, trust and action will be ensured. It will define ON-MERRIT deployment scenarios and use-cases for the main exploitable results of the project, which will include:

- RRI and Open Science incentives and indicators, in particular in the context of career promotion
- Insights into disciplinary and gender aspects through case studies
- Uptake of Open Science in information seeking practices in policy-making
- Scenario modelling of interventions to overcome Matthew effects in RRI and Open Science
- Practical guidelines and policy recommendations

Exploitation opportunities will be identified for the areas of academia and research, industry, policy-makers and societal actors. Thereby we will target different audiences including RRI and Open Science experts, scientific communities, industrial Research and Development groups, policy-makers in parliaments and ministries, and the general public. It will include analysis of user and community needs to achieve the best positioning of results within identified target groups, communities and markets. The plan will hence set out a

collaboration and outreach strategy tailored target stakeholders, and specify the detailed steps needed to achieve optimal uptake and exploitation of ON-MERRIT's outcomes. In summary, the first iteration of the ON-MERRIT exploitation plan will cover:

- Precise definition of exploitable ON-MERRIT end-results or outcomes
- Preliminary view on the uptake of RRI and Open Science resources outside academia (especially industry) and project positioning
- SWOT analysis
- Results identification
- User and community needs
- Positioning of results within identified target groups, communities and markets

2.2.7 Knowledge management and IPR

The consortium will sign a Consortium Agreement based on the DESCAs model⁸⁷ that will cover necessary issues of management, risk and liability and intellectual property rights.

The consortium partners are familiar with open innovation approaches (open source, open publishing, open access, etc.) and are supportive of them. There is considerable experience with licensing software as open source and using third party open source materials. The consortium is aware of the benefits and drawbacks. The consortium has adopted the position of *open by default*. Nonetheless exceptions may occur where for commercial, security, data-protection or legal issues certain information or results must remain confidential. The project will work under the principle of the generator(s) of results having ownership of them. Joint ownership will be clarified to the maximum extent possible through a clear and agreed breakdown of work. Where individual ownership is indiscernible, all joint owners will have the right to royalty-free exploitation of the whole results. This is aligned to the strategy of focussing on individual exploitation.

Through the consortium agreement measures will be put in place to manage associated risks, such as a vetting process for publications to prevent accidental exposure of other's foreground and an IPR register to record all the background introduced into the project and the foreground produced.

The scientific publications produced within ON-MERRIT will be made available in Open Access. Both 'gold' and 'green' Open Access models will be considered. Criteria of cost and value will be used on a case by case basis. In all cases, publications will be deposited in OpenAIRE-compliant repositories. ON-MERRIT will use OpenDOAR⁸⁸ or re3ata⁸⁹ to select suitable Open Access repositories for publications and data respectively, and ensure all research outputs are linked in OpenAIRE to project funding information (to enable the ingest of this information in CORDIS). Budget for the cost of Open Access is included in partners' direct costs. Costs will be split between authors on a case-by-case basis.

2.2.8 Data management strategy

ON-MERRIT will participate in the Pilot on Open Research Data in Horizon 2020, in line with the principles of the project and the EC's Open Access to research data policy for facilitating access, reuse and preservation of its research data. For this purpose, ON-MERRIT includes a sub-task within Work Package 1 (Management and Coordination) dedicated to the development of a Data Management Plan (DMP) that will outline how research data will be handled during and after the project, describing what data will be collected, processed or generated and following what methodology and standards, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved. The ON-MERRIT DMP (project deliverable D1.2, due in Month 6) will describe:

- How data will be created or captured, stored and processed in accordance with local and European regulations regarding data protection and processing.

⁸⁷ <http://www.desca-2020.eu/>

⁸⁸ <http://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opendoar/>

⁸⁹ <https://www.re3data.org/>

- How the project will deposit project publications, datasets and other outputs in the institutional data repositories of our partners as well as in a repository service provided by national aggregators.
- How the project coordinator will monitor, track and disseminate information about its produced research publications and data sets to the relevant channels so that they are included in the European research e-infrastructure of OpenAIRE.
- How the project will take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) the following:
 - the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications as soon as possible
 - other data, including associated metadata
- Information on the tools and instruments needed to validate the results produced by using the specific data sets.
- Guidelines, support material, proposed workflows and tools for both the coordinator and each project partner, translating the generic requirements of the Open Access and Open Research Data Pilot into specific practical guidelines that they can apply during the lifetime of the project.

Through its participation in the national thematic aggregators, the project will also register the institutional publication and data repositories of each partner, in order to provide information about the current systems that the project partners maintain. For partners that do not have a data repository to deposit their research data, OpenAIRE's Zenodo⁹⁰ repository service will be used (where a "community" will be created for project outputs).

The DMP will be constructed with online tools (e.g., DCC's DMPOnline⁹¹) and will specify a set of recommended licensing schemes for the produced research data, preferably using the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0) or the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license as suggested by H2020. In the cases where the datasets cannot be publicly shared, the reasons will be mentioned in their metadata descriptions (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related). Our project's research data will be deposited in the partners' institutional repositories or Zenodo. Having these data sets or data streams registered will make their metadata publicly discoverable for other interested researchers to discover, access, reuse and verify.

⁹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/>

⁹¹ <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>

3 Implementation

3.1 Work plan – Work Packages and deliverables

ON-MERRIT is composed of a closely interrelated set of activities to create primary evidence on the extent of Matthew effects in RRI and Open Science transition, and to use this evidence to reflect critically upon current RRI and Open Science indicators and incentives. The work plan consists of 6 Work Packages (WPs), classified into common "horizontal" activities involving all partners (WPs 1, 2, 6), and "vertical" activities that regroup expert partners in the different sub-domains (WPs 3, 4, 5).

Figure 4 ON-MERRIT Work Package structure

Each Work Package is structured as a series of well-defined and coherent set of tasks. To ensure structure and timely delivery of results, ON-MERRIT will take place in three main phases, shown in Figure 5 below. Each phase will follow logically from the last such that there will be strict interlinking dependencies across Work Packages, tasks, deliverables and partners through time.

Figure 5 ON-MERRIT project phases

The Work Packages are structured such that project management functions and cross-WP dependencies are clear and verifiable:

- **WP1 Management and coordination** is dedicated to the management, coordination and monitoring of the project to enable the efficient progress of its work meeting the contractual obligations and the quality expectancies of the consortium. It also addresses the project's data management plan and implementation.
- **WP2 Dissemination and participation** covers a diverse set of activities that relate to raising awareness about the project in domains of interest and engaging stakeholder to co-create research instruments for the uptake of the results (framework, co-design, recommendations).
- **WP3 Research cultures, support and incentives** investigates the extent of Matthew effects in science and how they are influenced by the application of RRI and open science principles. Through analysis of multiple scholarly datasets, it addresses how Matthew effects in scholarship are related to access to scientific literature, creation of academic collaborations, getting recognised and getting promoted.
- **WP4 Innovation and industry** investigates uptake of Open Science outputs in industry and the readiness of economic actors to exploit FAIR data resources, especially in light of which attributes might affect cumulative advantage.
- **WP5 Policy-making and societal actors** aims at revealing the role of open access and open science resources, as well as public engagement, in policy-making. It will study how Open Science outputs are used in policy-making and identify which societal actors have influence in public participation in policy-making.
- **WP6 Synthesis, validation and policy recommendations** is responsible for turning all ON-MERRIT results into practical guidelines and policy recommendations for EU/national/institutional policy makers.

It is important to note, however, that in spite of this pragmatic separation of foci, in line with our recognition of the essential interconnectedness of the quadruple helix, which emphasises interaction dynamics and knowledge flows between all these stakeholder areas, intimate links between each of these strands of work will ensure that they are treated holistically.

3.2 Management structure, milestones and procedures

With the specific objectives of ON-MERRIT, a strong expertise and organisational structure is required in order to ensure the quality and achievability of the results. As the project will base on existing state-of-the-art technologies in conjunction with a diversity of expertise and methodologies, strong collaboration between the participants is an explicit requirement in order to form a project-wide knowledge base.

ON-MERRIT requires a strong and well-defined project management. Therefore, the distribution of responsibilities, the flow of information for management, controlling, and reporting are of particular importance. Clear conflict management processes are required to ensure quick and fair conflict resolution in order to reduce the risks of conflict escalation. A thorough assessment and analysis of potential risks is also important in order to handle them properly in advance. The partners and the organisational structure, which will be introduced in the following sections, are designed to meet the project goals and procedures. Adequate structures have been put in place to ensure and enforce the collaborative, integrative and business aspects of the project.

3.2.1 Management structure

The project management structure presents the different roles of the beneficiaries and partners according to the work plan and needed levels of decision and advice. Figure 6 provides a high-level view of the management structure.

Figure 6 ON-MERRIT Project Management Structure

The following specific functions are implemented in this structure:

Project coordinator (PC) Tony Ross-Hellauer: The PC will be responsible for the overall project and its objectives, quality, schedule and budget. He is the contact point for the European Commission and chairs the Project Steering Committee and oversees the Project Management Board. Supported by the coordination team at KNOW, the coordinator's main responsibilities are to: (1) assure efficient project management; (2) manage the project's decision-making process; (3) chair the Project Management Board (PMB), leading the set of activities to be carried out by this committee; (4) coordinate technical/support activities amongst work-packages; (5) assure the quality and timely delivery of ON-MERRIT deliverables; (6) serve as the only interlocutor of the Consortium with the European Commission; and (6) act as the Financial Officer within the Consortium, including managing the preparation of financial statements for the Commission.

Project Steering Committee (PSC): The PSC will be composed of one senior representative from each beneficiary. It deals with all decisions related to the consortium agreement and to the respective beneficiaries, oversees contractual issues with the European Commission, and is the highest body for solving disputes. The PSC will be mainly responsible for: (1) the definition of overall project strategy; (2) fulfilling the Commission requirements pertaining to preparation of progress and financial reports; (3) deciding on long-term exploitation plans; (4) conflict resolution within the consortium, under chairing of the project coordinator; (5) technical coordination and decision-making (assessment of the technical work, interchange of technical information amongst partners, submission of deliverables, etc.); and (6) risk management. The PSC will meet at least quarterly (either face-to-face or virtually) and meetings will be timed to take place in advance of major project milestones to enable major Go/No-Go decisions to be made. The PSC will consist of the PC, in addition to the following roles:

- **Scientific Coordinator Petr Knoth:** ON-MERRIT has significant research elements which will benefit from dedicated supervision of research related activities of the project. Scientific Management will be coordinated by Petr Knoth, OU, who has overseen scientific coordination of various research projects in the areas of RRI and Open Science. The main task consists in ensuring that the research aspects are appropriately represented in the overall work and activities and are aligned with each other across Work Packages and tasks.
- **Community Coordinator Birgit Schmidt:** Supporting innovation in participation processes and dissemination of research results is a key aim of ON-MERRIT. Because of the importance of communities in the project activities, ON-MERRIT will appoint a dedicated Community Manager. Her main responsibilities will be to ensure that each individual partner, but also the project as whole, realises the participative potential that lies in the planned project activities. The Community Manager will make sure that the co-creation activities meet real requirements coming from scientific communities and support the Policy Synthesis Manager in turning the project results into successful policy recommendations. The Community Manager of ON-MERRIT will be Birgit Schmidt, UGOE.
- **Policy Synthesis Coordinator Eloy Rodrigues:** In addition to the generation of evidence to build the SWAFS knowledge base, a major pillar of ON-MERRIT's mission is to turn these findings into actionable recommendation for policy interventions for a range of stakeholders. ON-MERRIT will therefore appoint a Policy Synthesis Manager whose role is to ensure that all project findings across multiple strands of work feed into a joined-up framework of policy recommendations.
- **Research Integrity Coordinator Bernhard Wieser:** ON-MERRIT's commitment to research integrity is demonstrated by the assignment of Bernhard Wieser from TU GRAZ to oversee adherence in matters of ethics and research integrity. The Research Integrity Coordinator will ensure adherence to the highest levels of fidelity in matters of stakeholder and participant engagement, data storage and processing, and reporting.

Project Management Board (PMB): The Project Management Board will report to the PSC, and will be responsible for the day-to-day operations of the project. The PMB will monitor the activities of the project and provide for exchange and coordination between the Work Packages. It will be composed of the Work Package leaders (the member of each institution leading operational activities) and will provide for overall risk management and day-to-day decision-making in matters that cut across Work Packages. The PMB will meet at least once a month to discuss progress and make cross-WP operational decisions.

Work Package Leaders (WPLs): Work Package Leaders are responsible for implementing the main activities of the project. WPLs ensure and facilitate timely communication between the task leaders and oversee risk management for all tasks within the Work Package. Hence, the responsibilities of WP leaders include: (1) technical management of their WPs, including timely submission of deliverables and milestones, liaison with task leaders; each WP leader will be also responsible of the quality assurance of documents and deliverables produced; (2) technical reporting to the PMB; and (3) communication exchange amongst the partners involved in their WP(s).

Advisory Board (AB): The Advisory Board will be composed of high-level external stakeholders with a demonstrated record/interest in RRI and Open Science, including independent experts as well as

representatives of key organisations. Members will be invited based on suggestions of the beneficiaries. The board will advise the project in strategic matters and will provide advice for the high-level dissemination and outreach strategy of the project. The Advisory Board will also be essential for the verification and finalisation of the project's core results and recommendations. Organisations and individuals under consideration for the Advisory Board include the Global Young Academy and Eurodoc (academia, early career researchers), LIBER (academia, libraries), GENDERACTION (gender expertise), PPMI (policy expertise), OCSDnet (Global South perspective) as well as other independent experts.

Gender balance: ON-MERRIT, in line with the aims and goals of RRI and as a matter of course in modern research, builds upon a gender-balanced consortium and a strict policy of gender equality. It goes without saying that the development of new ideas and generation of new knowledge without any gender prejudice will be continued in the active phase of ON-MERRIT, as our leading experts and associated advisors are tasked with addressing gender-related issues continuously throughout the project.

3.2.2 Management procedures

Project meetings: The PSC meets at three-month intervals either virtually or face-to-face (average 2 f2f meetings per year) to assess the overall progress and to align individual work across participants. Meetings will either be scheduled to major milestones (e.g., the 3 “Gateway Milestones”. M1.2, 1.3, 6.2, at the end of each major project phase) or (to economise on travel costs for f2f meetings) to coincide with a major conference or project event. In addition, a monthly jour-fixe will be organised as a web meeting involving the PC, PMB and other specific team members with timely inputs from across the whole consortium. Project monitoring will be performed at each milestone of the project within a meeting of the PSC. The Work Package leaders report about progress against objectives, milestones, activities, schedule, resource consumption, deviations, encountered problems and risks. In addition, they give an outlook to the upcoming project period. Individual Work Package meetings will be established as needed, organised by the respective WP leader and in accordance with the Project Coordinator.

Project communication: Communication within the project is established through specific procedures, in addition to dedicated channels and means to exchange information. Communication does not only involve cross partner exchange of results and work alignment, but also progress and risk reporting. Therefore, the Project Coordinator will set up a set of communication and data exchange tools at the beginning of the project in order to support collaboration. In particular, standardised tools for communication like dedicated mailing lists, file servers with versioning control, shared desktop tools, chatting and tracking applications as well as telephone or web conferencing tools for remote meetings will be introduced.

Quality control is performed by the respective decision level (Task > Work Package > project) against quality standards measured by indicators laid down in the project management handbook. For the internal quality assurance, a beneficiary not involved in the conception or delivery of each deliverable will be assigned at the beginning of the project. Deliverables will hence be ready for consortium review one month in advance of their EC delivery date, allowing two weeks for review, one week for further revisions, a final week in which the whole consortium can then comment and resolve any final issues, followed by timely delivery to the EC. In addition, the project coordinator can organise external quality control with the help of experts from the ON-MERRIT community.

Conflict resolution: In general, it is expected that the instructions of the coordinating tasks will be followed by the concerned WPs, or that conflicting views will be solved bilaterally. The decision mechanism and dispute resolution process follow the principle that the decision is made by the lowest possible level of responsibility. Decisions should be made in consensus. In the exceptional case that conflicts cannot be solved on a WP level, conflicts shall be escalated to the project executive. Where needed, the PSC can install a specific committee for appropriate dispute resolution (e.g. mediation involving professional mediators).

Legal, administrative and financial management is performed by the Project Coordinator with the help of his assistant and of the Work Package leaders.

Innovation management is to be seen against the background of a research project dealing with opening of the process, the tools and the results and involving contributors from outside the consortium. The responsible person is the Scientific Coordinator, Petr Knoth (OU). Questions of exploitation, copyrights and IPR will be an agenda point at each management meeting. Opportunities and risks in this regard will be observed continuously.

Consortium agreement: The Consortium Agreement is complementary to the commission contracts and will take into account the individual aspects of the consortium and the specific aspects of the project. Major issues are the definition of the steering and advisory committees (such as representation, delegation, and quorum), IPR regulations (pre-existing knowledge), financial payment mechanisms (result depending payment release) as well as escalation strategies. All partners will sign the document before the project starts and the EC contract is signed.

Management processes and management handbook: The overall project management will be covered by a number of management processes that shall provide reference rules for all relevant management tasks. These processes are building on current coordinator internal processes that are all ISO 9002 certified and fully documented in the Project Management Handbook (D1.1., due in M2). The Handbook will be aligned to rules and procedures requested by the European Commission. It will define structures, plans, procedures, and quality indicators for each activity. Establishing project quality procedures will allow the continuous and successful monitoring of all project's activities, ensure that objectives are met and assure the quality of the final product (considering quality the fulfilment of initial requirements). The following processes will be explained in detail in the Project Management Handbook: (i) Future directions and maintenance of the constituency; (ii) Set-up, integration and Kick-Off of activities; (iii) Management of the project and/or its Work Packages; (iv) Reporting and work progress; (v) Quality assurance and audits; (vi) Dissemination and exploitation of results; (vii) Closure of the project and/or its activities; (viii) Operational accounting of the project and/or its activities. A first version of the Management Handbook will be provided at the beginning of the project (M2). To better implement the above and facilitate partners' work, templates and tools will be prepared by the Project Coordinator, and presented to the partners at the Kick-off meeting.

3.2.3 Critical risk assessment and mitigation

Risk management has to be performed by the task leaders, Work Package leaders and by the project coordinator. Each person has to observe the risks and report the risk status at the next project meeting (including the monthly web meeting). In case of urgency, the Project Coordinator has to be informed without any delay. The Project Coordinator organises the risk mitigation measures.

In large, complex and relatively long projects, where many partners are involved, it is unavoidable that problems turn up from time to time. It is of paramount importance that potential risks are clearly identified and assessed, and that the project prepares for resolving actions if required. ON-MERRIT will execute a continuous risk analysis methodology throughout the consortium, the so-called Risk Log. Within this living document, the initially defined project technology and execution risks are listed, maintained and complemented. Those regular updates reflect the current development state appropriately and enable efficient planning before risks become critical. Consequently, the hierarchical structure follows the project management hierarchy:

- The Work Package members identify threats and risks on the low, concrete technical level and communicate them up to the Work Package leaders. They are responsible for weighting the threats and suggesting methods to counter them on the technical level, e.g. through alternative approaches.

- WP Leaders are responsible for the identification of risks that threaten the achievement of the respective WP's objectives, involving alignment of the participants' tasks and ensuring communication inside the WP.
- The Project Coordinator is responsible for the alignment of all actions across the whole consortium - this involves technical and management aspects. All risks, threats and potential means to address them are communicated to the board, which will analyse risk, impact and corrective actions based on the likelihood of the respective risk. It will initiate the actions necessary to handle the corresponding risk, following the order of priority given impact and likelihood of occurrence. The Project Coordinator may involve the Advisory Board in accordance with the conflict resolution strategy described above.
- For risks with medium to high probability that cause severe impact, countermeasures and contingency plans are discussed regularly. In addition, they will be flagged throughout the entire execution of the project as risk items within the Risk Log. This process ensures that all levels of the project take special care of these particular items.
- For risks with low probability or low impact, and for those that cannot be foreseen at this stage, the Project Coordinator will ensure that such are identified in an early phase, and that necessary countermeasures are taken. The introduced Risk Log therefore relies on constant updated in order to capture both the risks, but also the mitigation measures.

3.3 Consortium as a whole

The ON-MERRIT consortium brings together an international group of partners collectively representing the interdisciplinary expertise of a wide range of social and cultural science, humanities, as well as natural and engineering science disciplines. The partners have been carefully selected for their expertise and experience to intensify collaboration across the targeted activities. The consortium will benefit greatly from a foundation of pre-existing, proven approaches, technologies, and working relationships developed during successful participation in a variety of RRI projects. Previous research was especially strong in relation to Open Science and stakeholder engagement, as demonstrated in a large number of directly relevant FP6, FP7 and Horizon 2020 projects including RDA Europe 4.0 (H2020), FIT4RRI (H2020), OpenUP (H2020), OpenAIRE-Advance, OpenAIRE-Connect and OpenAIRE2020 (H2020), MOVING (H2020), FOSTER and FOSTERplus (H2020), FoTRRIS (H2020), PASTEUR4OA (H2020), EOSCpilot (H2020), OpenMinTeD (H2020), CHIC (Horizon 2020), STELLAR (FP7), OpenAIREplus and OpenAIRE (FP7), DRIVER II (FP7), FAAN (FP7), G-TwYST (FP7), DRIVER (FP6), and APOSDLE (FP6) (for a comprehensive explanation of expertise gained in these projects see section 1.3.6.1 *Linked Research* of this proposal).

Furthermore, the consortium brings together key actors from European Open Science and Big Data initiatives such as OpenAIRE, a pan-European network of National Open Access Desks (coordination), COAR (Confederation of Open Access Repositories; host), Leibniz Association (full member), Big Data Value Association (full member), DINI (German Initiative for Networked Information; secretariat), ESFRI activities (management), and projects DARIAH (technical coordination). Active engagement in these networks will aid uptake of the project results by relevant stakeholder groups.

The ON-MERRIT consortium has been formed with an eye towards bringing together state-of-the-art expertise and capacity for evaluating and promoting new approaches in support of RRI with special emphasis on Open Science practices. ON-MERRIT deploys an integrated approach and features partners with profound experience in collaboration and engagement with stakeholders from academia, industry, civil society and policy-making. The consortium is evenly balanced between well-established and promising young researchers and takes gender and regional diversity into consideration. The consortium includes partner institutions from four European countries. Each partner features an international team whose members represent all European member states. Research activities will comprise the EU-28 to ensure a wide uptake of European perspectives. Further synergies will come from outreach to countries beyond those represented by partner institutions. Efficacy will be leveraged through two partners of the consortium (UGOE and UMINHO) and their engagement in a vast network of national contacts to Open Science initiatives (OpenAIRE), covering 33 European countries in total. ON-MERRIT's partners all combine

tangible experience in establishing and operating e-Infrastructures for RRI and Open Science with research excellence in investigating and ensuring the socio-technological conditions for effective transition towards a more open, participatory and equitable science and society relationship. In ON-MERRIT, first-class research skills and innovative approaches will be seamlessly combined with policy research, stakeholder engagement as well as excellence in design and implementation of digital research infrastructures and outreach activities. This diversity of experience and approaches will guarantee that the objectives in hand will be dealt with in the most comprehensive and all-encompassing way. Partners' experience and expertise relates to:

- eInfrastructures and human networks supporting open scholarship and policies (UGOE, UMINHO and OU in the context of OpenAIRE/DRIVER, 2005- ongoing; FOSTER/FOSTERplus, RDA Europe 4.0; OpenMinTeD and other initiatives)
- Exploring, assessing and implementing novel approaches for Responsible Research and Innovation (KNOW, UGOE, UMINHO and TU GRAZ in the context of OpenUP, FIT4RRI, G-TwYST and FoTRRIS),
- Quantitative and qualitative research into science and society engagement (TU GRAZ, UMINHO)
- Computational research into open access publication and bibliometric analysis (OU, KNOW)
- Evaluation of policy interventions (KNOW, UGOE in the context of OpenUP and ERC Open Science study)
- Translation of research into policy recommendations and stakeholder engagement (KNOW, UGOE, TU GRAZ)

Consortium expertise

The consortium is especially strong in collaborative research with social actors in academia, industry, civil society and policy-making. Research on each of these areas will be led by the partner with the highest reputation in the respective field of expertise.

KNOW, as is a competence centre for data-driven business and big data analytics, has especially strong industry links in addition to strong expertise in application-oriented research, collaborations with 37 major industry partners, and having spun off three companies. In its role as an innovation hub connecting science and industry, KNOW cooperates with academic institutions and companies to conduct application-oriented research. Since its inception in 2001, KNOW has successfully completed more than 450 application-oriented research projects. KNOW therefore occupies an excellent position to study the uptake of Open Science outputs in knowledge intensive industries. Furthermore, KNOW has an impressive track-record in participating in and leading FP6, FP7 and H2020 projects: OpenUP (H2020), MOVING (H2020), Learning Layers (FP7), STELLAR (FP7), and APOSDLE (FP6).

OU has a long-standing expertise in Open Access and Open Science (a core pillar of RRI) as demonstrated in EOSCpilot (H2020), OpenMinTeD (H2020) and FIT4RRI (H2020), and is a prime facilitator of what is currently the world's largest full text open access papers dataset with over 25 million unique visitors per annum. OU's Knowledge Media Institute (KMI) is especially strong in scientometrics and social network analysis. Additionally, it conducts research into the training needs of young academic researchers and has gained valuable insights into incentive structures relevant for the successful implementation of Open Science Strategies.

TU GRAZ has a long record of accomplishments in participatory deliberation of science and technology – essential elements of RRI's aims of facilitating inclusive governance and the engagement of civil society stakeholders in research. TU GRAZ's research staff has gained distinguished expertise in stakeholder engagement and was engaged with respective tasks in a series of FP7 and H2020 projects, including G-TwYST (FP7) and CHIC (Horizon 2020). The researchers at TU GRAZ have previously coordinated collaborative research designed to engage civil society organisations in co-operative research activities. Through its experience in trans-disciplinary engagement of civil society actors, TU GRAZ experts are particularly qualified to advance science governance as shown in previous research such as FAAN (FP7), FoTRRIS (H2020). TU GRAZ contributes experience in deliberative policy-making in biomedicine, agricultural biotechnology, and alternative types of agricultural innovation in Europe.

UMINHO has participated in several FP7 and H2020 projects (e.g. FOSTER, H2020 and OpenUP, H2020) and is therefore excellently equipped to lead policy synthesis activities and undertake research on the uptake of RRI and Open Science principles in relation to policy and training. UMINHO is well-equipped to contribute empirical research on information-seeking behaviours of policy-makers due to its profound experience with community-led Open Science and RRI initiatives.

UGOE is a distinguished promoter of Open Science practices. Its involvement in key research infrastructures (such as OpenAIRE, RDA Europe, COAR, FOSTER and ESFRI) and stakeholder associations (e.g. LIBER, RDA) will be an invaluable asset for ON-MERRIT, as the research in ON-MERRIT will be carried out in collaboration with infrastructure and support network providers. As a facilitator of core research infrastructures and prime open access research repositories, UGOE is in an excellent position to investigate the ways in which Open Science principles are implemented in policy and training and how research data, software and protocols are being reused amongst economic/business actors in Europe.

Collaboration with associated initiatives: ON-MERRIT will establish a broad knowledge coalition consisting of the beneficiaries of RRI and Open Science resources in academia, industry, civil society and policy-making. ON-MERRIT partners represent different kinds of expertise related to Open Science and RRI, and are well integrated into stakeholder networks comprising NGOs, think-tanks, publishers, research institutions, universities and individuals (including citizen scientists). As demonstrated by the range of Letters of Support received, the consortium is already closely embedded within or associated with various networks of direct relevance for ON-MERRIT. Key initiatives and institutions in this regard include a wide range of actors central to investigating and implementing both Responsible Research and Innovation (**SUPER_MoRRI, GENDERACTION, RRI-Practice, OpenUP, New HoRRizon**) and Open Science (**FOSTER, Open Science MOOC, Public Knowledge Project, OpenAIRE, COAR, Jisc**). In addition, we have the confirmed support of organisations representing early career researchers (**Young Academies, Eurodoc, YEAR network**), library associations (**LIBER**), policy and advocacy groups (**SPARC Europe**), industry (**Data Market Austria, human.technology SME cluster, Open Innovation in Science Center**), as well as organisations working to advance equity in Open Science in Eastern Europe and the Global South (**EIFL, OCSdnet**). These links will foster stakeholder engagement with specific tasks across the entire ON-MERRIT project. As indicated in the Letters of Support, ON-MERRIT has already laid the ground to work with all these initiatives in a range of activities including contributions to the co-creation of research activities and the validation and dissemination of results. This initial community will be organically grown through a structured outreach plan which targets key communities. Together, this ON-MERRIT map of stakeholder communities will form a strong network for change that will advance a more balanced and inclusive implementation of the SwafS knowledge-base.

3.4 Resources to be committed

The resources of the project have been optimised for maximum utilisation and coherence amongst partners, the integration of resources and the avoidance of unnecessary cost and overhead. Consequently, the ON-MERRIT consortium has carefully aligned the necessary and relevant resources needed for the 30-month project duration. The project makes use of the complementary nature of the competencies of the partners, which reflects the close relationships between research and application, in particular for the industrial stakeholders.

3.4.1 Adequacy of the overall financial plan

The critical mass for a successful ON-MERRIT consists of 127 Person Months distributed over 30 months and between 5 partners. To run effectively the project and support the management hierarchy as well as activities, it has been ensured that those partners being in a lead position (Project, WP, Tasks) have enough effort to pursue this activity effectively. The resources (personnel, travel, equipment and other costs) have been developed bottom-up from a task level view point. Consequently, in monetary terms, the budget including all incurred project costs is €1,000,000.00.

3.4.2 Other major cost items

Besides the personnel cost, other major cost items that have been considered include the following:

Scheduled Travels: Travel costs have been estimated per partner considering a cost of 800 € per FTE and travel, taking into account flight, accommodation and allowance. All partners have been assigned seven travels to General Assembly Meetings (including the Kick-Off and then, approximately every 6 months) per FTE. In addition, three travels per FTE have been assigned to cover costs for the review meetings and another three travels for each FTE have been assigned for other meetings and / or conference participation.

Other direct costs: Costs for Workshop will cover meeting room, catering, speakers.

With respect to the assigned costs, the following partners exceed the 15% ratio of personnel costs. Consequently, a justification for 3 partners is given below.

Table 15 TU GRAZ 'Other direct cost' items

Partner 3. TU GRAZ	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	15,500	Participation in project and 3rd party events (Kick-off (2 attending); EC mid-term evaluation (2 attending); Final evaluation (2 attending); 3 x conference; 3 x partner meetings); travel to conduct expert workshops (WP5)
Equipment	-	
Other goods and services	15,000	3 x Expert Workshops (venue, catering, travel/accommodation costs for experts)
Total	30,500	

Table 16 UMINHO 'Other direct cost' items

Partner 4. UMINHO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	15,500	Participation in project and 3rd party events (Kick-off (2 attending); EC mid-term evaluation (2 attending); Final evaluation (2 attending); 3 x conference; 3 x partner meetings); travel to conduct on-site interviews (WP4)
Equipment	-	
Other goods and services	-	
Total	15,500	

Table 17 UGOE 'Other direct cost' items

Partner 5. UGOE	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	14,000	Participation in project and 3rd party events (Kick-off (2 attending); EC mid-term evaluation (2 attending); Final evaluation (2 attending); 3 x conference; 3 x partner meetings)
Equipment	7,000	Project promotional and dissemination materials, campaign design (logo, infographic, flyers, posters, etc.)
Other goods and services	13,000	1 final project event (venue, catering, speakers travel/accommodation)
Total	34,000	

4 Members of the consortium

4.1 Participants

4.1.1 Know-Center GmbH

Short Name	KNOW	
Type	Research Institute/Centre	
Country	Austria	
Website	www.know-center.at	

Short Profile:

The Know-Center (www.know-center.at) is Austria's competence centre for data-driven business and big data analytics, founded in 2001. As a connecting link between science and industry, the Know-Center conducts application-oriented research in cooperation with other academic institutions and with companies. Today, the Center has over 100 researchers, 37 industry partners, over 700k€ annual industry assignments, a dedicated business development cooperating with major players and offers data-driven services to hundreds of users and has spun off three companies. In its role as an innovation hub connecting science and industry, the Know-Center conducts application-oriented research in cooperation with academic institutions and companies, successfully completing over 450 application-oriented research projects since its founding in 2001. Science 2.0 and Open Science are pivotal topics for Know-Center. The Know-Center has been involved in several EU-funded projects related to these topics, including a ~500k consultancy project for the ERC, the H2020 project OpenUP, the FP7 projects CODE and EEXCESS, and the FP7 Network of Excellence STELLAR. Furthermore, Know-Center is part of the Leibniz Research Alliance Science 2.0, the Open Access Network Austria, Research Data Alliance Austria and associate partner in the project e-Infrastructures Austria plus. Know-Center annually organises Europe's largest conference on big data analytics and data-driven business, the i-KNOW conference (<http://www.i-know.at>), which has a special track devoted to Science 2.0 & Open Science.

Two Know-Center groups will participate in ON-MERRIT. The **Open Science group** (linked to the Social Computing research group), led by Dr. Tony Ross-Hellauer, leads the consortium. It uses evidence-based approaches to making research cultures more transparent and participatory through new practices and technologies. Using data-driven philosophical and sociological approaches to technology assessment and cultural change, we investigate and foster the uptake and evaluation of RRI; Open Access; FAIR data and research data management services; collaborative and open research methods; reproducible research; and responsible research evaluation (especially open peer review). The Social Computing group represents the data network perspective. The purpose of this area is to analyse and model digital traces in complex online systems to shape and improve social behaviour e.g. through recommender systems. Specifically, it aims to develop novel methods and algorithms to better understand, predict, support and control social behaviour in complex networks and systems.

The **Data-Driven Business research group**, led by Ass. Prof. Dr. Viktoria Pammer-Schindler, deals with the understanding and design for data-driven business from the perspectives of business models, technology-enhanced (organizational) learning and knowledge management. The goal of the area is to embed data-driven technologies into organisations in support of decision making, compliance, knowledge management and learning, thereby ultimately impacting how organisations do business at the level of work practice, business process and business model. The area provides competences in Knowledge Management, Technology Enhanced Learning, and Data-driven Business Models. With regard to ON-MERRIT, the area will lead on activities related to analysis of uptake of RRI resources in industry by applying methods like questionnaires and contextual inquiries to check the readiness of companies (SMEs and large industry distributed all over Europe) for exploiting the potential of open access data.

Key Personnel:

Dr. Tony Ross-Hellauer (male), PhD in Information Studies (University of Glasgow), MSc in Information and Library Studies (University of Strathclyde), MA(Hons) in Philosophy (University of Dundee). Tony is Senior Researcher at Know-Center working on a range of issues related to RRI and open science evaluation, skills, policy, governance, monitoring and infrastructure. In 2018, Tony became Editor-in-Chief of “Publications”, an open access journal on scholarly communication, published quarterly online by MDPI since 2012. From 2015-2017 Tony was Scientific Manager for OpenAIRE, the globally-leading EC-funded infrastructure for Open Science. With OpenAIRE, Tony managed outreach, strategy and research & development. He has over 8 years of established experience in leading and contributing to multi-stakeholder projects that deal with Open Science, research evaluation, science policy and information studies - for example as Work Package leader for the OpenAIRE2020 and OpenUP projects. He is a core member of Research Data Alliance Austria (for which he serves as Auditor) and Open Access Network Austria (for which he is co-coordinator of the open science strategy working group), as well as a member of the EC COST Action networks ENRESSH and PEERE. He is a co-author of the Open Science Training Handbook, and his work on open peer review has received international recognition. Tony co-leads TRANSPOSE (transpose-publishing.github.io), a grassroots initiative to build a crowdsourced database of journal policies for preprints and peer review.

Prof. Dr. Stefanie Lindstaedt (female); Know-Center, CEO; Habilitation in computer science from Graz University of Technology (Austria), Ph.D. and MSc. in Computer Science from the University of Colorado at Boulder (USA). Stefanie Lindstaedt is head of the Institute for Interactive Systems and Data Science (ISDS) of Graz University of Technology and Managing Director (CEO) of Know-Center (www.know-center.at), Austria's leading research center for data-driven business and big-data analysis. Since 2001, Know-Center has been bridging the gap between science and industry in more than 50 applied scientific projects. Stefanie has an excellent track record in acquiring national and international research projects and leads large interdisciplinary research projects and groups. She has published more than 150 scientific papers in conferences and journals and has supervised more than 15 doctoral students. Since 2010 she is chair of the I-Know conference series (www.i-know.at), she was program officer of the conferences EDF 2015 and EC-TEL 2012. Prior to joining Know-Center, she led several projects at Daimler (Chrysler) Research, Ulm, Germany, and was a product manager for web globalization services at GlobalSight, Boulder, USA. Stefanie has also extensive experience in process and technical consulting, solution sales, marketing and organizational development for international companies. Other functions: Board of Directors: Big Data Value Association (BDVA), Digital networked Data Association (DnD), Smart Production Graz TU Graz Strategic Project; Coordinator: CoE Network, BioTechMed Data Integration Taskforce; High Level Expert Group on Open Science Cloud (EOSC); Advisory Board for Policy Making: EU Connect Advisory Forum (CAF), EU High Level Interest Group Open Science Cloud (HLEG OSC), Friends of Europe (FOE).

Ass.-Prof. Dr. Viktoria Pammer-Schindler (female) is research area manager at the Know-Center and assistant professor at the Institute for Interactive Systems and Data Science, Graz University of Technology. She is responsible for teaching, research and innovation in the fields of e-Learning, knowledge management, and data-driven business model innovation. Viktoria's field of research is user-centered design of innovative technologies for learning, knowledge management, and knowledge creation such as the elaboration of novel business models. Two major research streams are using data as basis for learning in organisations; and combining face-2-face with computer-mediated trainings in organisations (blended learning). She has published over 70 peer reviewed papers and regularly serves as PC member in international conferences. She is currently General Chair of the European Conference on Technology-Enhanced Learning (ECTEL 2019), member of the managing committee of the European Association of Technology Enhanced Learning (EATEL), and board member of the International Alliance to Advance Learning in the Digital Era (IAALDE).

Dr. Angela Fessl (female) is working as a senior researcher in the area of technology enhanced learning at the Know-Center. Angela received her Master for Computer Science (MSc) in the field of Telematik and her PhD (with distinction) in Informatics at Graz, University of Technology, Angela has

a long experience and a proven track of research and development projects in the areas of Document Management, Content Management and eLearning systems for various international companies and worked for various research institutions. Currently her primary research interests are in the area of Technology Enhanced Learning, with focus on reflective learning at the workplace. Angela has more than 8 years of established experience in leading and contributing to multi-stakeholder projects that deal with Technology Enhanced Learning and Learning Analytics like for example as Task leader in the MOVING project or Work Package leader for the AFEL project.

Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi (female) is a researcher and software developer in the Social Computing/Open Science area at the Know-Center. She is currently finishing her PhD at the Graz University of Technology on the topic of consensus building in online collaboration networks. Her research interests include social network analysis, dynamics in online social and collaboration networks, opinion diffusion and dynamics of social influence in complex networks. She has over 8 years of experience working on national and international, research and industry projects.

Stefan Reichmann (male), Diploma Studies in Philosophy at the University of Graz (with honours), MA in Sociology from the University of Graz (with honours). Stefan is a Junior Researcher in the area of Social Computing/Open Science at the Know-Center in Graz. He is working on a range of questions related to Open Science/RRI and Open Peer Review. He has several years of research experience in FWF as well as Horizon2020 projects. His previous work has focused on Sonification and Auditory Interaction Research (at the Institute for Electronic Music and Acoustics, Graz), Science and Technology Studies (University of Graz) and Trust/Trustworthiness of ICT (Social and Ethical Aspects of Digitization).

List of relevant publications, and/or products, services

1. Bezjak S., Clyburne-Sherin A., Conzett, P., Fernandes, P., Görögh, E., Helbig, K., Kramer, B., Labastida, I., Niemeyer, K., Psomopoulos, F., Ross-Hellauer, T., Schneider, R., Tennant, J., & Verbakel, E. (2018) *Open Science Training Handbook*. Gitbook. <https://open-science-training-handbook.gitbook.io/book/>
2. Fessl, A., Feyertag, S., & Pammer, V. (2015) Designing Innovative Digital Technologies for Knowledge Management and Data-driven Business: A Case Study. 15th Int. Conf. on Knowledge Technologies and Data-Driven Business (i-Know 2015). DOI: 10.1145/2809563.2809570
3. Hasani-Mavriqi, I., Geigl, F., Pujari, S.C. et al. (2016) The influence of social status and network structure on consensus building in collaboration networks. *Social Network Analysis and Mining*. 6: 80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13278-016-0389-y>
4. Lindstaedt S.N., Scheir P., Lokaiczkyk R., Kump B., Beham G., Pammer V. (2008) Knowledge Services for Work-Integrated Learning. In: Dillenbourg P., Specht M. (eds) *Times of Convergence. Technologies Across Learning Contexts. EC-TEL 2008. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 5192. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-87605-2_26
5. Ross-Hellauer, T., Deppe, A., & Schmidt, B. (2017). Survey on open peer review: Attitudes and experience amongst editors, authors and reviewers. *PLOS ONE*, 12(12), e0189311. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189311>

List of relevant previous projects or activities

OpenUP – Opening UP new methods, indicators and tools for peer review, impact measurement and dissemination of research results (Horizon 2020 grant no. 7110722, budget 2.2 million euros, 9 participants, 2016-2018): The RRI project addresses key aspects and challenges of the currently transforming science landscape and aspires to come up with a cohesive framework for the review-disseminate-assess phases of the research life cycle that is fit to support and promote Open Science. OpenUP has a strong focus on novel practices in OPR, innovative dissemination and research impact measurement/altmetrics. In addition to some extensive research activities, OpenUP has supported or is in the process of organising a range of dissemination activities/campaigns, including two large-scale

international conferences, multiple workshops and a high-level policy workshop on ongoing developments in Horizon Europe which are related to the key pillars of the programme.

Study on open access to publications and research data management and sharing within ERC projects (client: the ERC, budget 484,000 euros, 6 participants, 2017-2019): The goal of this study is to better understand the current practices and attitudes among ERC funded researchers in relation to the provision of open access to publications as well as research data management, sharing and reuse. The assignment is the largest and most comprehensive study of OA, OS and RDM issues in EU FPs launched to date. Although the contract is still ongoing, the study has already produced some important results, incl. quantification of OA publishing costs per ERC publication and project. These results, and many other findings, will contribute to improving the ERC's specific approach to the provision of OA to publications and RDM practices.

MOVING - Training towards a society of data-savvy information professionals to enable open leadership innovation (Horizon 2020, 9 participants, 2016-2019), Public administrators, compliance officers, auditors and researchers dealing with an ever growing flood of information need sophisticated tools that allow fast and accurate evaluation and visualisation of the analysis results. Specifically, this means that on the one hand the tools need to enable state-of-the-art searching and semantic analysis of large digital contents, where the users will be able to: i) get access to an extensive source inventory, ii) use search and visualisation methods which are as yet nowhere available for widespread use, and iii) generate knowledge that cannot be derived from existing solutions in a comparable speed and comprehensiveness. And, on the other hand, the tools also need to make their own functioning understandable to their users and support them through: i) a detailed and scientifically-proven help system (glossary, tutorials, guidance), ii) individually-configurable training programs (learning modules, videos, exercises), and iii) a vivid community of people from various sectors of society (science, administration, business) that have similar interests or problems to be solved. To face these challenges, MOVING is building an innovative training platform that will enable users from all societal sectors (companies, universities, public administration) to fundamentally improve their information literacy by training how to choose, use and evaluate data mining methods in connection with their daily research tasks, and to become data-savvy information professionals.

Learning Layers (FP7 EU Project, 20 participants, 2013 - 2015): Focused on developing technologies that support informal learning in the workplace. The particular focus is on Small and Medium sized Enterprises (SMEs) within Regional Innovation Clusters. In Layers, mobile and social technologies have been developed that unlock and enable peer production within and across those SMEs. The technologies also act as "scaffolds" for the individuals so that they can learn in the right context and at the right time.

STELLAR (FP7, Partner): A Network of Excellence of leading institutions and projects in European Technology-Enhanced Learning (TEL) to unify the diverse TEL community. A number of Science 2.0 tools to connect researchers and to analyse online communication have been developed in this project, alongside studies on Science 2.0 practices in interdisciplinary communities. Furthermore, insights into the future of TEL have been generated in a large Delphi study, the results of which were further corroborated with the outcomes of high-level meetings with policy makers.

APOSDLE (FP6, Coordinator): Researched how to connect learning, collaboration, and work process. The solutions developed in APOSDLE assumed workplaces with desktop computer access and were rather focused on the individual learner in an organisational context, without sharing across learners or networks).

Significant infrastructure/Technical Equipment/Products/Tools

The Know-Center has an Interaction Lab and a Big Data Lab available, which enables us to carry out research on innovative interaction technologies, and to analyse big data on contemporary hardware (GPU cluster, Hadoop cluster).

The Know-Center uniquely combines research excellence, a long track record of collaboration with industry in terms of analyzing industrial data and working together with different stakeholders in an organization, innovative (e.g., data analytics) technology development and methodological know-how on embedding technology into practice.

4.1.2 The Open University

Short Name	OU	
Type	Research Institute within a University	
Country	United Kingdom	
Website	http://kmi.open.ac.uk/	

Short Profile:

The Open University's Knowledge Media Institute (OU) was set up in 1995 in recognition of the need for the university to be at the forefront of research and development in the converging areas of Data & Information Sciences & technology enhanced learning. KMI has extensive experience in creating, managing and participating in national and European research projects related to open access & open science, technology enhanced learning, big data, text-mining, artificial intelligence and machine learning, digital libraries and scholarly communication.

The OU's ON-MERRIT project team will be represented by the KMi's Big Scientific Data and Text Analytics group, which consists of a mix of researchers & developers with a unique expertise in the fields of web-scale scholarly text and data mining & machine learning to support research and open science. The group's research also focuses on the use of natural language processing for the development of novel reward mechanisms in science that go beyond bibliometrics. The team is responsible for running the Connecting Repositories (CORE - core.ac.uk) service which contains the currently world's largest dataset of full text open access papers and has over 25 million unique visitors per annum. The team has previously participated in a number of EU funded projects in the areas of text and data mining and open science. These include OpenMinTeD, which developed a shared platform for open text and data mining of scientific literature, FOSTER and FOSTER Plus, where the team developed a well-known online platform (The FOSTER Portal - fosteropenscience.eu) for delivering online courses on Open Science. The project team has also been organising for the last 8 years the International Workshop on Mining Scientific Publications, which brings together researchers and practitioners analysing and mining databases of scientific publications and has a deep expertise & interest in the interdisciplinary issues surrounding the use of artificial intelligence to aid research. OU will lead WP3, addressing primarily Matthew Effects in Academia and RRI and OS training as well as Task 6.1 looking at RRI and OS incentives and indicators.

Key Personnel:

Dr. Petr Knoth (male) leads the KMi's Big Scientific Data and Text Analytics group. He is the founder, product and team leader for CORE, which is a service that aggregates millions of open access articles from around the world and makes them available for people to search and machines to text-mine. Previously, he worked as a Senior Data Scientist at Mendeley on information extraction and content recommendation for research. He has a deep interest in the use of AI to improve research workflows. He has co-founded Semantometrics.org which aim to go beyond bibliometrics and altmetrics to produce new research evaluation methods that make use of the publication full-texts in research assessment. Petr has been involved as a researcher and as a PI in a number of European Commission, national and international funded research projects in the areas of text-mining, open science and technology enhanced learning and has over 50 peer-reviewed publications based on this work.

Dr. Nancy Pontika (female) has a PhD in Scholarly Communications with a focus on Open Access from the School of Library and Information Science, at Simmons College, Massachusetts, United States. She has been involved in international open access projects, such as the Open Access Tracking Project (OATP) and the Open Access Directory (OAD), in which she also serves as an Editor. Her interests are scholarly communications, licenses and rights, open science, open access, and open access

fundings' policies and their compliance. In the past she worked at the Berkman Center for the Internet and the Society, Harvard University, as a research assistant on open access, at the Repositories Support Project as the Project Coordinator and she was also a repository manager at Royal Holloway, University of London. Currently she is working for CORE, an aggregation service of open access content, funded jointly by The Open University and Jisc. She is also the External Liaison Officer at the United Kingdom Council for Research Repositories (UKCoRR). Nancy has been involved in three European-funded projects, FOSTER, OpenMinTeD and FIT4RRI and has published both at international conferences and journals based on this work.

Dr. Drahomira Herrmannova (female) is a Research Associate in the Big Scholarly Data and Text Analytics Group at the Open University, UK. The focus of her research is on accelerating scientific discovery and helping scientists work more effectively by enabling intelligent access to the content of research publications. Her doctoral research directly resulted in the development of a new area called *semantometrics*, which uses full-text for research evaluation. Within this area, she has developed several methods which demonstrate the benefits and suitability of using full-text in automated impact assessment. Prior to her current appointment, she conducted a two-year internship in the Computational Data Analytics Group at Oak Ridge National Laboratory, TN, USA, where she worked on a number of projects in the areas of information extraction, text mining, and research evaluation. She has been a finalist in two international research competitions in the areas of scholarly data mining and text mining. She is well connected in the academic community and has been organizing research workshops since 2014 to bring together different communities working on related problems in text mining of research publications.

David Pride (male) graduated in 2016 from the University of Hertfordshire with an MSc. in Computer Science (with distinction). His master's dissertation centred on using Natural Language Processing techniques to analyse the sentiment of large volumes of textual data. He joined KMi as a PhD. student in 2017 under the supervision of Dr. Petr Knoth. David has a fully funded PhD. studentship, sponsored by Jisc. His research is focused on web-scale analytics for identifying research excellence. This has thus far resulted in two published papers in the areas of citation context analysis and citation typing and a third which conducted the largest ever comparative study of peer review and bibliometrics.

List of relevant publications

1. Pride, D. and Knoth, P. (2018) Peer review and citation data in predicting university rankings, a large-scale analysis, 22nd International conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL2018), Porto, Portugal Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Springer - (Best Paper Award). DOI:10.1007/978-3-030-00066-0_17
2. Herrmannova, D., Knoth, P. and Patton, R. (2018) Analyzing Citation-Distance Networks for Evaluating Publication Impact, Proceedings of the Eleventh International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2018), Miyazaki, Japan
3. Labropoulou, P., Galanis, D., Lempeis, A., Greenwood, M., Knoth, P., Castilho, R., Sachtouris, S., Georgantopoulos, B., Martziou, S., Anastasiou, L., Gkirtzou, K., Manola, N. and Piperidis, S. (2018) OpenMinTeD: A Platform Facilitating Text Mining of Scholarly Content, Proceedings of the Eleventh International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2018), Miyazaki, Japan, European Language Resources Association (ELRA)
4. Knoth, P., Gooch, P. and Jack, K. (2017) What Others Say About This Work? Scalable Extraction of Citation Contexts from Research Papers, 21st International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL), Thessaloniki, Greece. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-67008-9_23
5. Knoth, P. and Khadka, A. (2017) Can we do better than co-citations? Bringing Citation Proximity Analysis from idea to practice in research articles recommendation, Workshop: 2nd Joint Workshop on Bibliometric-enhanced Information Retrieval and Natural Language Processing for Digital Libraries (BIRNDL 2017) at The 40th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval (SIGIR 2017)

List of relevant previous projects or activities

FOSTER; Facilitate Open Science Training for European Research; (Horizon2020 grant no. 741839, budget 925000 euros, 12 participants, 2017 - 2019); Facilitate Open Science Training for European Research (2014-2016, May 2017 - Apr 2019). FOSTERplus builds on the achievements of FOSTER and will focus on promoting the practical implementation of Open Science, with activities targeting academic staff, young scientists and policy makers in particular. It will develop more advanced level and discipline-specific material that build capacity for the practical adoption of Open Science and promote a change in culture.

EOSC Pilot: Frictionless Data Exchange Scientific Demonstrator; (Horizon2020 grant no. 739563, budget 9,9 million euros, 32 participants, 2017 - 2018); The EOSCpilot project will support the first phase in the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as described in the EC Communication on European Cloud Initiatives [2016]. It aims to establish the governance framework for the EOSC and contribute to the development of European open science policy and best practice; develop a number of pilots that integrate services and infrastructures to demonstrate interoperability in a number of scientific domains; and engage with a broad range of stakeholders, crossing borders and communities, to build the trust and skills required for adoption of an open approach to scientific research. These actions build on and leverage already available resources and capabilities from research infrastructure and e-infrastructure organisations to maximise their use across the research community.

CORE; COncecting REpositories; Jisc; Infrastructure for Resource Discovery - CORE is a global harvester of open access research publications. CORE collects its content from repositories, disciplinary and institutional, and journals, both open access and hybrid. CORE's mission is to aggregate all open access research outputs from repositories and journals worldwide and make them available to the public. In this way CORE facilitates free unrestricted access to research for all. Currently CORE is the world's largest harvester of open access research publications, and has 25 million unique visitors per year.

eCloud; Europeana Cloud: Unlocking Europe's Research via The Cloud; (Horizon2020 grant no. 325091, budget 4.7 million euros, 35 participants, 2013 - 2016) Europeana Cloud is a Best Practice Network, submitted under Objective 2.1.a and coordinated by the Europeana Foundation, designed to establish a cloud-based system for Europeana and its aggregators. Europeana Cloud will provide new content, new metadata, a new linked storage system, new tools and services for researchers and a new platform - Europeana Research. Content providers and aggregators, across the European information landscape, urgently need a cheaper, more sustainable infrastructure that is capable of storing both metadata and content. Researchers require a digital space where they can undertake innovative exploration and analysis of Europe's digitised content. Europeana needs to get closer to the target of 30 million items by 2015. Europeana Cloud meets these needs. The key objectives of Europeana Cloud are: 1. To provide access, at Europeana, to 1.1m new metadata records and 5m research focussed items from across European Universities, libraries, data centres and publishers; 2. To create a cloud based infrastructure capable of delivering cost-efficient content and metadata storage for stakeholders across Europe; 3. To understand and incorporate the legal, strategic and economic issues of a cloud-based system for content for cultural heritage institutions and domain aggregators; 4. To achieve a broad consensus among European content aggregators and research networks on the advantages of a cloud based solution; 5. To develop a digital platform, named Europeana Research, to discover and use Europeana research content; 6. Via this cloud to provide tools and services for researchers that permit innovative research that exploits digitised content in Europeana. This is a vital project for the Europeana network of content providers and aggregators, moving to an infrastructure that can deal not just with descriptive metadata but actual digitised content as well.

OpenMinTeD - Open Mining Infrastructure for Text and Data; (Horizon2020 grant no. 654021, budget 6.6 million euros, 17 participants, 2015 - 2018) Recent years witness an upsurge in the quantities of digital research data, offering new insights and opportunities for improved understanding. Text and data mining is emerging as a powerful tool for harnessing the power of structured and unstructured content and data, by analysing them at multiple levels and in several dimensions to

discover hidden and new knowledge. However, text mining solutions are not easy to discover and use, nor are they easily combinable by end users. OpenMinTeD aspires to enable the creation of an infrastructure that fosters and facilitates the use of text mining technologies in the scientific publications world, builds on existing text mining tools and platforms, and renders them discoverable and interoperable through appropriate registries and a standards-based interoperability layer, respectively. It supports training of text mining users and developers alike and demonstrates the merits of the approach through several use cases identified by scholars and experts from different scientific areas, ranging from generic scholarly communication to literature related to life sciences, food and agriculture, and social sciences and humanities. Through its infrastructural activities, OpenMinTeD's vision is to make operational a virtuous cycle in which a) primary content is accessed through standardised interfaces and access rules b) by well-documented and easily discoverable text mining services that process, analyse, and annotate text c) to identify patterns and extract new meaningful actionable knowledge, which will be used d) for structuring, indexing, and searching content and, in tandem, e) acting as new knowledge useful to draw new relations between content items and firing a new mining cycle. To achieve its goals, OpenMinTeD brings together different stakeholders, content providers and scientific communities, text mining and infrastructure builders, legal experts, data and computing centres, industrial players, and SMEs.

FIT4RRI - Fostering Improved Tools for Responsible Research and Innovation; (Horizon2020 grant no. 741477, budget 3.2 million euros, 12 participants, 2017 - 2020) FIT4RRI moves from the assumption that there is a serious gap between the potential role Responsible Research and innovation (RRI) and Open Science (OS) could play in helping Research Funding and Performing Organisations (RFPOs) to manage the rapid transformation processes affecting science (especially the science-in-society aspects) and the actual impact RRI and OS are currently having on RFPOs, research sectors and national research systems. FIT4RRI is precisely intended to contribute in bridging this gap, promoting viable strategies to activate institutional changes in RFPOs. The project, in particular, will act on two key factors i.e. i) Enhancing competences and skills related to RRI and OS through an improvement of the RRI and OS training offer (in terms of training tools, actions and strategies) presently available; ii) Institutionally embedding RRI/OS practices and approaches by promoting the diffusion of more advanced governance settings able to create an enabling environment for RRI and OS. With this double aim in view, FIT4RRI is organised following an overall methodology based on three main steps: an analytical strand devoted to understand what is happening in the RRI and OS practice, taking into account general trends, barriers and drivers to RRI and OS, interests and values, advanced experiences; a testing strand (observing RRI/OS in action through 4 co-creation experiments) aimed at figuring out possible solutions in terms of training approaches and governance settings; and a proactive strand, promoting changes (i.e. developing training tools and actions and easy-accessible evidence-based guidelines on governance settings functioning as enablers for RRI and OS). The project will last 36 months and includes 7 WPs: Mapping and benchmarking; Sectoral diagnosis, Co-creation experiments, Training tools and actions, Governance Setting, Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results, Management. This project involves 13 partners from 9 EC.

Significant infrastructure/Technical Equipment/Products/Tools

KMi's Big Data Cluster for processing large amounts of data (about 16 server nodes) will be available to the project.

CORE (core.ac.uk) offers seamless access to millions of open access research papers, enriches the collected data for text-mining and provides unique services to the research community. As of October 2018, it is the 9,099th most popular domain globally based on Alexa Traffic Rank with over 25 million unique visitors per annum.

FOSTER (<https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/>) is a popular platform technically developed by this team in the context of the FOSTER and FOSTER Plus projects, offering free online courses on open science, responsible research and innovation and text and data mining.

Semantometrics builds on the premise that the full-text of a publication is needed to assess the

publication's value. It is a class of evaluation metrics that measures research value by using text analytics to assess how far each discovery takes us.

4.1.3 Technische Universität Graz

Short Name	TU GRAZ	
Type	University	
Country	Austria	
Website	https://www.tugraz.at/arbeitsgruppen/sts/home/	

Short Profile:

The Science, Technology and Society Unit (STS Unit) at Graz University of Technology (TU-Graz), is a newly established group of inter- and transdisciplinary researchers formerly affiliated with the Institute of Science, Technology and Society Studies Unit of Universitaet Klagenfurt. The members of the research group have long-standing experience in investigating the linkages between science, technology and society. Addressing technology as a social process, the STS-Unit at TU-Graz aims at integrating wider societal issues into engineering studies. A particular research focus lies on public policy and broader governance issues related to plant biotechnology, biomedicine and sustainable food systems using sociological methods in inter- and transdisciplinary project design. Conducting and scrutinising public engagement processes and stakeholder consultations are frequent characteristics of project work and have been successfully applied in the field of plant biotechnology, genetic testing and food systems for many years (<https://www.tugraz.at/arbeitsgruppen/sts/home/>).

Key Personnel:

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Bernhard Wieser (male) is Associate Professor for Science, Technology and Society Studies at TU Graz. He has a social science background and acquired *venia docendi* at Klagenfurt Universitaet. He carries out interdisciplinary research in the field of science and technology studies with a particular focus on the life sciences. In his previous work, he has investigated ethical, legal and social aspects of biomedicine and diffusion factors of genetic testing in medical practice. Bernhard Wieser has experiences both in qualitative and quantitative methods of sociological research.

Dr. Armin Spök (male) is Senior Scientist at the TU-Graz STS-Unit. He has an academic background in molecular genetics from the University of Graz and science and technology policy from that University of Sussex, Brighton and more than 20 years of experience in interdisciplinary and social science research related to plant biotechnology. A particular focus of his research lies on identifying and managing health and socio-economic impacts of plant biotechnology and on broadening biotechnology governance by public engagement. He participated as principal investigator or researcher in more than 30 national and EU projects and (co-) authored more than 60 publications. He is a member in various expert groups on GMO risk assessment or risk communication at EU- and international level.

Sandra Karner (female) is a senior contract researcher. She has an academic background in biology and she has been working for 15 years on participatory approaches to science governance in the field of agriculture, food systems and plant biotechnology. Most recently, she is also working on Responsible Research and Innovation concepts.

Dr. Christian Dayé (male) is a post-doctoral researcher and recently joined the STS-Unit at TU Graz. He graduated from the University of Graz with a PhD in Sociology and was a post-doc researcher at Alpen-Adria Universität Klagenfurt. His research focus is on historical and sociological analysis of scientific policy advice. At the STS-Unit, Christian is currently involved in a project concerned with Responsible Research and Innovation in agricultural biotechnology and manages the stakeholder engagement processes. He is experienced with various methods of user involvement and expert deliberation.

List of relevant publications, and/or products, services

1. Haddaway NR, Kohl C, Rebelo da Silva N, Schiemann J, Spök A, Stewart R, Sweet JB, Wilhelm R. (2017) A Framework for Stakeholder Engagement during Systematic Reviews and Maps in Environmental Management. *Environmental Evidence* 6:11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-017-0089-8>
2. Dayé, C. (2018) 'How to train your oracle: The Delphi method and its turbulent youth in operations research and the policy sciences', *Social Studies of Science*. Online first: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306312718798497>
3. Wieser, B. (2017): *How Genes Matter: Genetic Medicine as Subjectivisation Practices*. Transcript: Bielefeld April 2017, ISBN 978-3-8376-3766-3
4. Wieser, B. (2011). The microphysics of accountability. In: *Accountability in Research*, special issue on "Impact of Genomics on Ethical Issues" edited by Ruth Chadwick & Jeantine Lunshof, vol. 18, issue 3, S. 163-180, 2011, doi: 10.1080/08989621.2011.575034
5. Wieser, B. & Karner S. (2010). Deliberating Genome Research: discursive strategies and performative roles. In: *Science as Culture*, vol. 19, issue 3, 2010, S. 327-349; doi: 10.1080/09505430903281293

List of relevant previous projects or activities

FoTRRIS (Horizon 2020, 2015-2018, partner). Fostering a Transition towards Responsible Research and Innovation Systems (FoTRRIS) was coordinated by the Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO) of Belgium. The main objective of FoTRRIS is to develop and introduce new governance practices to foster Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in research and innovation systems. FoTRRIS focusses, more specifically, on new governance practices to co-design transdisciplinary RRI-projects that are attuned to societal needs, values and opportunities and that connect and mobilise relevant stakeholders. FoTRRIS performs a transition experiment to support the transformation of present-day research and innovation strategies into co-RRI-strategies. It will design, test and validate the organisation, operation and funding of a co-RRI-knowledge-arena. This knowledge arena is conceived as a small organisational unit that will function as a local one-stop innovation platform that encourages various knowledge actors from science, policy, industry and civil society to co-design, -perform, and -monitor co-RRI-projects that are attuned to local manifestations of global sustainability challenges. The STS-Unit of TU-Graz is engaged with the co-design of co-RRI-projects, facilitated by the proposed knowledge arenas, in Austria and the provision of policy recommendations on the implementation of co-RRI. (<http://fotrris-h2020.eu/>)

CHIC (Horizon 2020, 2018-2022, partner). Chicory Innovation Consortium (CHIC) is coordinated by Stichting Wageningen Research (NL). Chicory is a multipurpose crop for dietary fibre and medicinal terpenes. The STS-Unit of TU Graz is work-package leader for developing and implementing the RRI-type project design, in particular for the stakeholder engagement. Moreover TU Graz will conduct analyses of policies relevant to and of possible social impacts of the cultivation of GE chicory. In general, the Chicory Innovation Consortium's (CHIC) pursues two objective (i) to explore new plant breeding techniques (NPBTs) in chicory for the production of immunomodulatory inulin and medicinal terpenes - products with clear benefits for consumers - and ii) to co-develop with stakeholders sustainable innovation pathways for NPBTs. For pursuing this goal the project will evaluate in parallel the value of four different NPBTs (tilling, gene editing using CRISPR/Cas9 for genomic insertion and transient expression, and cisgenesis) with respect to their technical and economic potential, health, and environmental risks, and socio-economic impacts. During the project period the regulatory framework in the EU is likely to be clarified resulting in some NPBTs being considered and regulated as genetically modified plants and others which would not be covered by this legislation. In line with the principles of responsible research and innovation (RRI) project activities will involve stakeholders during the entire R&D process and results will be communicated to interested publics involving also activities by artists. (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/212834_en.html)

G-TwYST (FP7, 2014-2018, partner). GMP Two Year Safety Testing (G-TwYST) is coordinated by the University of Veterinary Medicine Hanover. STS-Unit of TU-Graz is work-package leader for the participation process and task leader for the analysis of the conflicts on animal studies. The project aims

at developing guidance for conducting and interpreting long-term animal toxicity studies with genetically modified maize (NK603, MON810) and analyses the relevance and scientific value of such studies for the risk assessment of genetically modified organisms (GMOs). Animal studies in GMO risk assessment have been at the heart of several controversies within and outside the scientific domain. Although normally a purely scientific endeavour, these studies will, therefore, be opened for stakeholder scrutiny and input by making available to all interested parties research plans, draft results and conclusions, as well as raw data and by engaging stakeholder and external experts in planning and interpreting these studies and in drawing general conclusions. G-TwYST will, moreover, investigate the normative issues linked to the science in these conflicts and will use these results as inputs in the participation process. G-TwYST is linked to other FP7 projects presently ongoing at the STS-Unit of TU-Graz. GRACE conducts toxicity studies on animals in a participative setting, whereas PreSto develops a research agenda and implementation plan for a multinational research programme in the field of GMO risk assessment. This research programme will be implemented as an ERA-Net in the context of Horizon 2020. (<https://www.g-twyst.eu/>)

Computer Modelling for Better Health (Zukunftsfonds Steiermark, 2017-2018, partner). The project was coordinated by Univ.-Prof. Dr. Kurt Zatloukal of Graz Medical University. STS-Unit of TU-Graz engaged health practitioners in order to analyse the acceptability of medical avatars as an interface technology of comprehensive medical computer models. The project's overall objective was to assess the development of a computer-based health avatar. Such a "digital twin" is designed to simulate bio-physiological processes on the basis of medical parameters, environmental conditions and behavioural variables. Integrating a variety of parameters, including sensor data, clinical data, molecular data, etc., computer simulations aid the efficacy of treatments and preventive measures. Drawing on visions of "Healthy Ageing and Assisted Living" the advancement of comprehensive medical computer models raises questions regarding privacy and wider ethical and social implications of such technologies. In order to allow for a more reflexive innovation processes health practitioners and stakeholders were invited to share their views on health-related computer modelling. The participants of expert workshops and focus groups assessed specific user profiles in a variety of scenarios of application. In such a way, they contributed to a socially more robust knowledge basis for the advancement of research and innovation of computer-based health technologies.

(<http://www.zukunftsfonds.steiermark.at/cms/ziel/129884213/DE/>)

FAAN (FP7, 2008-2010, coordination). Facilitating Alternative Agro-food Networks: Stakeholder Perspectives on Research Needs (FAAN) is a project designed to engage civil society organisations (CSOs) in a "co-operative research" (CR) activity and in agenda-setting on "Alternative Agro-Food Networks" (AAFNs). FAAN explored new ways in science governance through trans-disciplinary engagement of civil society actors in research at the earliest stage in the process. Applying an upstream approach, the project contributed substantially to the evidence base and the understanding necessary to foster more desirable types of agricultural innovation within the European Community, pointed out how policy frameworks could better facilitate such improvements and helped to identify best practises in research methods as well as AAFNs management and policies.

(https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/88615_en.html)

Significant infrastructure/Technical Equipment/Products/Tools

TU Graz hosts an annual STS Conference which is jointly organised by the Science, Technology and Society Unit - Graz University of Technology, the Inter-Disciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture (IFZ) and the Institute of Advanced Studies on Science, Technology and Society (IAS-STs).

4.1.4 Universidade do Minho

Short Name	UMINHO	
Type	University	
Country	Portugal	
Website	https://www.uminho.pt	

Short Profile:

University of Minho (UMinho) is a public higher education institution, founded in 1973 and is one of the so-called "New Universities". A student population of over 18000 together with more than 1100 teaching staff and almost 645 technical and administration staff make the University of Minho one of the biggest Portuguese universities.

University of Minho created its institutional repository – RepositóriUM – in 2003, has established a self-archiving policy of its intellectual output in the end of 2004, and is internationally known as one of the “success stories” on the development of institutional repositories and the promotion of Open Access to scientific literature. In 2008, University of Minho lead the Portuguese national project RCAAP (Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal = Portugal Open Access Science Repository) and has been acting as the scientific and technical coordinator of the project since then. In the last years, University of Minho has been participating in several FP7 and H2020 projects related with Open Science and repositories (DRIVER II, NECOBELAC, OpenAIRE, OpenAIREplus, MEDOANET, OpenAIRE2020, PASTEUR4OA, FIT4RRI), was the project coordinator for FP7 FOSTER (Facilitating Open Science Training for European Research) project and coordinates FOSTERplus.

The previous experience of UMinho on several projects like OpenAIRE and FIT4RRI and its current role as coordinator of FOSTERplus project, as well as its active participation in community lead initiatives and several organizations working on aspects related with Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation demonstrate UMinho’s ability to perform its tasks in ON-MERRIT.

UMinho will lead WP6, which will synthesise knowledge of the extent of the threats posed by Matthew Effects in relation to current RRI and open science policy interventions, and will lead tasks on WP3 (Task 3.3 Uptake of RRI & OS principles in relation to policy and training) and WP5 (Task 5.2 Information seeking behaviours amongst policy-makers in the age of Open Science).

Key Personnel:

Dr. Eloy Rodrigues (male) is the Director of the University of Minho Documentation Services. Eloy has been working on repositories, Open Access and Open Science since 2003, having established University of Minho institutional repository in 2003, and being the scientific and technical coordinator of RCAAP (Portugal Open Access Science Repository) since 2008. At European level, he is member of the European University Association Expert Group on Science 2.0/Open Science and has been coordinating the participation of UMinho in several EU funded projects (like the OpenAIRE projects, and FOSTER and FOSTERplus where he is the project coordinator), related with repositories, Open Access and Open Science. Eloy is currently the Chair of the Executive Board of COAR, the Confederation of Open Access Repositories. He is member of the Working Group for the National Open Science Policy, established by the Portuguese Ministry of Science, Technology and Higher Education. In the last years he has been presenting, as invited speaker, in more than fifty events in Europe (Portugal, Spain, UK, Czech Republic, Germany, Italy, France, Bulgaria, Turkey, Belgium, Hungary, Netherlands, Malta), in Africa (Mozambique, South Africa and Ethiopia), America (Brazil, Argentina, Colombia, México, Chile, Peru and Costa Rica) and in Asia (China, Korea and Japan). He has authored dozens of publications (articles, books and book chapters, etc.).

Pedro Príncipe (male) is Head of Division at University of Minho Documentation Services. Coordinates the Open Science Projects Office, on OpenAIRE2020, FOSTER and RCAAP projects. In OpenAIRE2020 project he is working as support and helpdesk manager and participating in the guidelines team and other technical tasks, as the usage statistics and the funder information services. He also had participation in several FP7 projects related with Open Access and repositories: NECOBELAC, OpenAIRE, MedOANET, OpenAIREplus and PASTEUR4OA, and also in related new H2020 projects, as OpenAIRE2020, OpenAIRE-Advance, OpenAIRE-Connect, FIT4RRI and FOSTERplus. Graduated in New Communication Technologies and with training in information science and documentation, he previously worked during ten years as librarian and web content manager at University of Aveiro. He has been involved in COAR Working Group on Repository Interoperability, and acting as member of the COAR Controlled Vocabularies Editorial Board. He was member of the National Executive Council of the Portuguese Association of Librarians, Archivists and documentalists (BAD) from 2011 to 2016 and in BAD is also Coordinator of the Academic Libraries working Group since 2014. He was recently appointed by the Minister of Science, Technology and Higher Education to integrate the national working group on Portuguese Open Science Policy.

Maria Antónia Correia (female) is currently working at the Open Access Projects' Office of the Documentation Services of Universidade do Minho as information specialist, collaborating in FOSTERPlus and FIT4RRI projects. She has a BA in Anglo-Portuguese Studies by the Universidade Nova de Lisboa and attended two post-graduation courses in Library and Information Sciences (2004) and in Archives (2006) from the Universidade de Lisboa. She has more than 15 years of experience coordinating university libraries, and in recent years has developed support services for researchers in the areas of scientific publication, promotion of the researcher's visibility at a personal and institutional level and researcher's assessment. In this context, she taught several training sessions, including the module on Scientific Publication in the course of Information Literacy, and she designed and coordinated the Research Data Management course at the Universidade Nova de Lisboa's Doctoral School.

Paula Marinho Moura (female), Since October 2017, Paula Moura integrates the Open Science Projects team, in the Documentation Service, at the University of Minho. Between 2002 and 2017 she was an information professional at the Transport and Communications Museum. In 1996 she finished her degree in History (scientific branch) at the University Portucalense. Between 2001-2006 she attended post-graduate studies in Library and Information Science - libraries and documentation centers (2001-2003) and, in archive and record and management (2003-2006), in the same university. In October 2009 she completed a Master's Degree in Information Management at the University of Aveiro, developing the master dissertation in *Information Management in cultural organizations, using digital environment to aggregate and access information*. At the moment she's attending a Master in Information Systems at the University of Minho.

List of relevant publications, and/or products, services

1. Swan, Alma, & Rodrigues, Eloy. (2016). Open Access policy effectiveness: A briefing paper for research institutions. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.35635>
2. Schmidt, B., Orth, A., Franck, G., Kuchma, I., Knoth, P., & Carvalho, J. U. do M. (2016). Stepping up Open Science Training for European Research. MDPI, 4(2). <http://doi.org/10.3390/publications4020016>
3. Grigorov, I., Bjørnshauge, L., Rodrigues, E., Hjubers, L., Orth, A., North, D., ... Carvalho, J. (2015). FOSTER Open Science Learning Objectives. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15603>
4. Rodrigues, Eloy (2014). Open Access to publications and research data in Horizon 2020: what are the requirements and how can institutional repositories and OpenAIRE help to meet them. Institute of Mathematics and Informatics Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Digital Presentation and Preservation of Cultural and Scientific Heritage, Vol. 4. <https://repositorium.sdum.uminho.pt/handle/1822/30521>
5. Rodrigues, E., Boavida, C., Tsoukala, V., & Kalaitzi, V. (2013). Guidelines towards

List of relevant previous projects or activities

OpenAIRE, OpenAIREplus and OpenAIRE2020 - Open Access Infrastructure Research for Europe (Dec 2009 - Dec 2020). OpenAIRE2020 is the third funding phase of OpenAIRE, it represents a pivotal phase for this long-term effort to implement and promote Open Access (OA) and Open Science in Europe. OpenAIRE2020 supports Open Science in Europe by harvesting, enriching and linking information from a range of data-sources, including Open Access repositories, aggregators and OA journals, to produce an information graph of research outputs in Europe and beyond. At the same time, OpenAIRE's community network works to perform outreach and advocacy on a range of Open Science issues in Europe, particularly as they pertain to EC/ERC OA policies. In addition, OpenAIRE2020 aims at strengthening relationships between European OA infrastructures and other global regions, particularly Latin America and the U.S.

FOSTER, FOSTERplus – Facilitate Open Science Training for European Research (2014-2016, May 2017 - Apr 2019). FOSTERplus builds on the achievements of FOSTER and will focus on promoting the practical implementation of Open Science, with activities targeting academic staff, young scientists and policy makers in particular. It will develop more advanced level and discipline-specific material that build capacity for the practical adoption of Open Science and promote a change in culture.

FIT4RRI – Fostering Improved Training Tools for Responsible Research and Innovation (May 2017 – Apr 2020). FIT4RRI aims to bridge the gap between Responsible Research and Innovation and Open Science, in particular through enhancing competencies and skills, and facilitating institutional embedding and creating enabling environments.

MedOANET – Mediterranean Open Access Network (www.medoanet.eu/project) addresses the necessity for coordinated strategies and policies in Open Access to scientific information in Europe. The project will enhance existing policies, strategies and structures for Open Access and will contribute towards the implementation of new ones in six Mediterranean countries: Greece, Turkey, Italy, France, Spain, Portugal. It will also promote national and regional coordination of policies, strategies and structures in these six countries and beyond.

Pasteur4OA – Open Access Policy Alignment Strategies for European Union Research (www.pasteur4oa.eu) aims to support the European Commission's Recommendation to Member States of July 2012 that they develop and implement policies to ensure Open Access to all outputs from publicly-funded research. PASTEUR4OA will help develop and/or reinforce open access strategies and policies at the national level and facilitate their coordination among all Member States. It will build a network of centres of expertise in Member States that will develop a coordinated and collaborative programme of activities in support of policy-making at the national level under the direction of project partners.

Significant infrastructure/Technical Equipment/Products/Tools

RCAAP – (Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal = Portuguese Network of Open Access Repositories). University of Minho documentation services are the technical and scientific coordinators of the Portuguese Network of Open Access Repositories.

RepositóriUM – Institutional Repository of the University of Minho.

4.1.5 Georg-August Universität Göttingen

Short Name	UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN
Type	University	
Country	Germany	
Website	http://www.uni-goettingen.de/	

Short Profile:

Göttingen State and University Library (UGOE) is one of the largest libraries in Germany and a leader in the development of digital libraries. UGOE is one of the leading open science institutions and e-Infrastructure innovators in Germany and internationally. UGOE played a key role in leading the networking activities in the EC-funded DRIVER project (2005-2009), building the digital repository infrastructure for Europe. UGOE acts as Scientific Coordinator of the EU-funded OpenAIRE-Advance project (2018-2020), as it did in earlier project phases (OpenAIRE 2009-2012, OpenAIREplus 2011-2014, OpenAIRE2020 2015-2018), which has built up an infrastructure and support network for the implementation of the European Commission's open access policies across 33 European countries and aims to widen its scope by connecting publications to contextual information, such as research data. Moreover, UGOE contributes to further Open Science related projects (FOSTER, FOSTERplus, OpenUP, FIT4RRI, RDA Europe 4.0, ERC Open Science Study) which to strengthening capacities for the practical implementation of Open Science, in particular targeting academic and research support staff, early career researchers and policy makers. UGOE also hosts the international Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR, www.coar-repositories.org), a not-for-profit association of repository initiatives launched in October 2009, and the secretariat of DINI (German Initiative for Networked Information) which coordinates and supports collaboration across higher education and research institutions in Germany. UGOE establishes dedicated research environments for the humanities in national, European and ESFRI activities; notably, it holds the management (together with France) and technical coordination (together with Austria) within the construction phase of the ESFRI project DARIAH. These and other projects address organizational and technical aspects such as virtual research environments and research infrastructures for scientific data (e-Research), research data management, data curation and long-term preservation (e.g. PERICLES, German Federation for the Curation of Biological Data). At the local level, UGOE together with GWDG, the computing and IT competence centre of University of Göttingen and the Max Planck Society, have established the eResearch Alliance (eRA, <http://www.eresearch.uni-goettingen.de/>) which offers sustainable, long-term support for researchers at Göttingen Campus concerning information/data management throughout the research life cycle from, ranging from storage and archiving of research data to open access publication strategies.

Key Personnel:

Prof. Dr. Wolfram Horstmann (male) has been the director of the Göttingen State and University Library at Georg-August-University of Göttingen since 2014. Prior to his current position he was Associate Director at the Bodleian Libraries of the University of Oxford, UK. He is currently leading several strategic projects in the areas scholarly communication, open access, research data and digital transformation for the University of Göttingen and for the library in Göttingen. He is executive member and Chair of the Steering Group on Scholarly Communication and Research Infrastructure for the European research library association LIBER. In the Research Data Alliance (RDA), he is member of the Organisational Advisory Board and chairs several working groups, e.g. "Libraries for Research Data" and "Long Tail of Research Data". He is also teaching Information science with a specialisation in Scholarly Communication and Open Science at Humboldt-University in Berlin. He acted as advisor to several bodies and initiatives, e.g. the European Commission, the German Research Foundation DFG, or the Nature journal „Scientific Data“. Prior, he was Chief Information Officer for Scholarly Information at Bielefeld University, where he was responsible for strategic development of the institutional services for content, data and tools in research and education between 2007 and 2011. He

has also served as European project manager for the State and University Library of Göttingen and as head of Publishing Services at the Academic Library Centre in Cologne. He is a biologist by training, having worked in the field of computational neuroscience before he actively turned his attention towards scholarly communication and libraries.

Dr. Birgit Schmidt (female) leads the Knowledge Commons unit at Göttingen State and University Library, and coordinates projects and activities with a focus on policies, e-infrastructures and training in support of the implementation of Open Science. She serves as Scientific Secretary and research data management working group co-chair in LIBER's Steering Committee on Research Infrastructures. She contributes to several international committees, e.g. the European Commission's Horizon 2020 Expert Group on the Future of Scholarly Publishing and Scholarly Communication, Knowledge Exchange's Open Access Experts Group and formerly the Belmont Forum's working group on Open Data in the context of the e-infrastructure data management project. Previously, she acted as Executive Director of the Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR). She also teaches on Information Management with a focus on Open Science at the Hannover University of Applied Sciences and Arts. She has a background in Mathematics and Philosophy, and a postgraduate degree in Library and Information Science.

Najko Jahn (male) is working as Data Analyst and is Deputy Head of the Knowledge Commons unit at the State and University Library Göttingen. He studied Library and Information Science and Philosophy at Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. Prior, he acted as project and innovation manager at Bielefeld University Library. From January to June 2016 he visited the Exeter Data Studies group led by Prof. Sabina Leonelli. Moreover, he is actively contributing to open data and open source communities, which includes rOpenSci where he maintains two packages for the statistical computing environment R. He teaches on Information Science topics with focus on quantitative methods and Open Science practices. He contributes as a member to the LIBER's Innovative Metrics working group.

Dr. Jan Brase (male) is head of the Research and Development at the State and University Library Göttingen since 2015. He has a degree in Mathematics and a PhD in Computer Science from the University of Hannover. From September 2006 until 2015 he was coordinating the DOI registration agency at the German National Library of Science and Technology (TIB) and from January 2010 to December 2014 he was Director of DataCite, a global consortium of libraries that focus open data and open science. He is furthermore President of the International Council for Scientific and Technical Information (ICSTI) and Co-Chair of the CODATA Task group on Data Citation. He was on the advisory board of several FP7 projects and is the author of several articles on the role of libraries in research data management. In 2011 he received the German "Library Hi-Tech award".

List of relevant publications, and/or products, services

1. Whyte, A., Schmidt, B., & Banelytè, V. (2018). *Case studies on Open Science in the context of ERC projects - Set 1*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1219037>
2. Schmidt, B., Bertino, A., Beucke, D., Brinken, H., Jahn, N., Matthias, L., ... Bargheer, M. (2018). Open Science Support as a Portfolio of Services and Projects: From Awareness to Engagement. *Publications*, 6(2), 27. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications6020027>
3. Jahn, N., & Tullney, M. (2016). A study of institutional spending on open access publication fees in Germany. *PeerJ*, 4, e2323. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.2323>
4. Tenopir, C. et al., (2017). Research Data Services in European Academic Research Libraries. *LIBER Quarterly*. 27(1), pp.23–44. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.18352/lq.10180>
5. Schmidt, B., Gemeinholzer, B., & Treloar, A. (2016). Open Data in Global Environmental Research: The Belmont Forum's Open Data Survey. *PLOS ONE*, 11(1), e0146695. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0146695

List of relevant previous projects or activities

RDAEurope 4.0 (Mar 2018 - May 2020) – This project acts as the European interface to the global

Research Data Alliance. RDA Europe 4.0 focuses on the need for open and interoperable sharing of research data and the development of social, technical and cross-disciplinary links to enable such sharing on a global scale. UGOE's role is to engage in building up a network of European RDA Nodes and support the process of liaising closely with national and regional nodes in order to activate contributions and to promote collaboration.

Study on open access to publications and research data management and sharing within ERC projects (June 2017 - Febr 2019). The goal of this study is to better understand the current practices and attitudes among ERC funded researchers in relation to the provision of open access to publications as well as research data management, sharing and reuse. Although the contract is still ongoing, the study has already produced some important results, incl. case studies, a survey of attitudes and barriers, and quantification of OA shares and publishing costs. These results, and many other findings, will contribute to improving the ERC's specific approach to the provision of OA to publications and RDM practices.

OpenAIRE, OpenAIREplus, OpenAIRE2020, OpenAIRE-Advance – Open Access Infrastructure Research for Europe (Dec 2009 - Dec 2020). OpenAIRE2020 is the third funding phase of OpenAIRE, it represents a pivotal phase for this long-term effort to implement and promote Open Access (OA) and Open Science in Europe. OpenAIRE2020 supports Open Science in Europe by harvesting, enriching and linking information from a range of data-sources, including Open Access repositories, aggregators and OA journals, to produce an information graph of research outputs in Europe and beyond. At the same time, OpenAIRE's community network works to perform outreach and advocacy on a range of Open Science issues in Europe, particularly as they pertain to EC/ERC OA policies. In addition, OpenAIRE2020 aims at strengthening relationships between European OA infrastructures and other global regions, particularly Latin America and the U.S.

EOSCpilot – The European Open Science Cloud for Research Pilot Project (Jan 2017 - Dec 2018). The EOSCpilot will support the first phase in the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), in particular, it will establish the governance framework for the EOSC and contribute to the development of European Open Science policy and best practice, develop a number of pilots that integrate services and infrastructures and engage with a broad range of stakeholders.

FOSTER, FOSTERplus – Facilitate Open Science Training for European Research (2014-2016, May 2017 - Apr 2019). FOSTERplus builds on the achievements of FOSTER and will focus on promoting the practical implementation of Open Science, with activities targeting academic staff, young scientists and policy makers in particular. It will develop more advanced level and discipline-specific material that build capacity for the practical adoption of Open Science and promote a change in culture.

OpenUP – OPENing UP new methods, indicators and tools for peer review, impact measurement and dissemination of research results (June 2016 - May 2018). OpenUP addresses the review-disseminate assess phases of the research life cycle and aim to provide practical guidance and training as well as policy recommendations and guidelines.

FIT4RRI – Fostering Improved Training Tools for Responsible Research and Innovation (May 2017 – Apr 2020). FIT4RRI aims to bridge the gap between Responsible Research and Innovation and Open Science, in particular through enhancing competencies and skills, and facilitating institutional embedding and creating enabling environments.

Significant infrastructure/Technical Equipment/Products/Tools

UGOE oversees the coordination of OpenAIRE's pan-European network of National Open Access Desks and engages in the building of a European National Nodes network in the Research Data Alliance, both perform outreach and advocacy on a range of Open Science issues in Europe, particularly as they pertain to EC/ERC OA and research data management policies.

4.2 Third parties involved in the project (including use of third party resources)

Please complete, for each participant, the following table (or simply state "No third parties involved", if applicable):

No third parties involved

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the project should not be sub-contracted)	N
<i>If yes, please describe and justify the tasks to be subcontracted</i>	
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by linked third parties ⁹²	N
<i>If yes, please describe the third party, the link of the participant to the third party, and describe and justify the foreseen tasks to be performed by the third party</i>	
Does the participant envisage the use of contributions in kind provided by third parties (Articles 11 and 12 of the General Model Grant Agreement)	N
<i>If yes, please describe the third party and their contributions</i>	
Does the participant envisage that part of the work is performed by International Partners ⁹³ (Article 14a of the General Model Grant Agreement)?	N
<i>If yes, please describe the International Partner(s) and their contributions</i>	

⁹² A third party that is an affiliated entity or has a legal link to a participant implying a collaboration not limited to the action. (Article 14 of the [Model Grant Agreement](#)).

⁹³ 'International Partner' is any legal entity established in a non-associated third country which is not eligible for funding under Article 10 of the Rules for Participation Regulation No 1290/2013.

5 Ethics and Security

5.1 Ethics

The ON-MERRIT project targets an equitable scientific system that rewards based on merit rather than the “Matthew Effect” of cumulative advantage. Recognising this key threat to RRI, ON-MERRIT’s transdisciplinary consortium deploys a cutting-edge combination of qualitative (surveys, questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, case-studies) and computational (scientometrics, social network analysis, machine learning, predictive analytics, text and data mining) methods that use stakeholder participation and co-design to engage researchers, industry, policy-makers and citizens in examining the extent of the Matthew Effect in key RRI elements (Public Engagement, Gender, Open Access/Open Science and Governance). Selected research questions focus on disciplinary contexts of particular importance for the UN Sustainable Development Goals (Climate Science, Agriculture and Health Sciences). ON-MERRIT then synthesises this evidence to make evidence-based policy recommendations on how Research Performing and Funding Organisations should amend policies, indicators and incentives to address and/or mitigate these effects, thus breaking new ground to broaden the “science with and for society” knowledge-base and show the way ahead for equitable RRI.

All partners in ON-MERRIT will adhere to the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and to data protection legislation, as well as overarching ethical guidance such as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. We also expect project researchers to adhere to the ethical commitments contained in their professional and institutional codes of conduct.

The project will undertake coordination and investigations that involve collection and sharing of personal (although not sensitive) data. The overriding principles will be a) active informed consent and b) appropriate ownership of data. The project will manage such data in accordance with GDPR, local laws and institutional requirements. In addition, ON-MERRIT’s partner organisations will be responsible for ensuring all ethical principles relating to their country and institutional context are adhered to. In some cases, this may require additional ethical permission to be sought. Survey and interview instruments that aim to engage human participants will ensure ethical approval in advance via the ethics board of a partner institution.

This consortium involves partners who are experienced academics and experts with a history of conducting research in the kinds of settings described in this research project. The project partners each have a senior researcher lead who will supervise the data collection and analysis process. They will be responsible for ensuring that the ethical rights and responsibilities of our respondents are protected. Special care will be taken to ensure that no documents or outputs in any of the partner countries contain identifying personal information. Wherever dissemination activities might include such material, consent will be gained beforehand.

The data collection in this project are hence not expected to raise any serious ethical issues. However, specific attention will be paid towards addressing the ethics of research throughout different stages of ON-MERRIT. Management of ethical issues will be overseen by the responsible partner, Assoc. Prof. Bernhard Wieser from TU Graz. Any ethical issues that arise during the project will be reviewed by Assoc. Prof. Wieser, in partnership with the project coordinator, and necessary actions taken.

5.1.1 Data-handling & GDPR

All the data gathering activities conducted in the ON-MERRIT project will comply with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (“GDPR”)⁹⁴ and other relevant national laws and regulations, as well as the ON-MERRIT EC Grant Agreement. No sensitive personal data will be collected in ON-MERRIT. By default, all data will be anonymised, though it may identify the partner institution. For any data that identifies an individual, by name or other identifying feature, that individual must give informed consent to its use in advance. Individuals will retain ownership of any data that is created, directly

⁹⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

or indirectly, by them, and have the right to inspect that data. All participants in any ON-MERRIT activity will be made aware in advance of any ON-MERRIT activity in which they are involved, the nature of that activity, the data that will be collected and/or used and how that data will be used.

The data collected and processed within the work packages and activities (described in detail below) cannot be considered as sensitive data. On-MERRIT will not deal with data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade-union membership, healthy or sex life. Only data with a strict connection with the aim of the research will be collected. Despite the rather “non-sensitive” nature of collected data, ON-MERRIT will take into account and address all major principles for data protection related to:

- Quality of data and data processing
- Legitimacy and categories of data processing
- Right of access to the personal data
- Subject’s right of information and objection
- Confidentiality and security of processing

5.1.1.1 Procedures for data handling: collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction

The ON-MERRIT consortium will implement several data collection methods (as outlined in the project description above) that will include recruitment of participants, and gathering their opinions/knowledge related to open science, open peer review, innovative dissemination and altmetrics and related data. The project will adhere to informed consent procedures through which participants will be acquainted with the project, what type of data will be collected, and how the data will be handled. Those are specified in D8.2.

The table below provides information on procedures that will be implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction by the partners of ON-MERRIT consortium during the course of the project.

Element	Explanation
Data Collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data collection activities will be carried out in WP3, WP4, WP5, and WP6. Main data collection methods include surveys, interviews, workshops, focus groups, social network analysis, text and data mining (TDM), and web mining.
Data Storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The raw data collected from surveys will be stored in a suitable format (e.g. Excel files, ODS or CSV files). The documents will be saved in internal servers of the task leaders. The servers will be protected by passwords known only to the researchers. Once processed and anonymised, the data will be published on an online repository (eg. Zenodo) and will be available for third parties. ● The recorded data from focus groups, workshops and interviews will be stored as recordings in a suitable format (MP3, OGG or WMA format) on the internal servers of the task leading organisations. If focus groups, workshops and interviews are not recorded, the written summaries will be saved in a suitable format (Word documents, text files) and will be also stored in the internal servers of the responsible institution. The written summaries will be anonymised and will also be made available on the online repository for third parties’ use. ● All the collected data will be anonymised. The information provided will be analysed and presented in project reports grouped together and will not be used individually.

Data Protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ON-MERRIT partners will make use of local servers and cloud storage solutions to store raw data collected through the various project activities. The consortium will take all appropriate technical and organisational measures to prevent any unauthorised act with regard to the data, implementing authentication and authorisation mechanisms. ON-MERRIT will make sure that no one will access, read, copy, alter, use in any way or process the raw data unless he/she is authorised to do so according to clear access rules. Finally, the raw data processing will be organised in a way that gives complete control and tracking of the procedures followed. ● Crowd-sourced data may be excluded from the policies and measures above.
Data Retention & Destruction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Private data will be stored on the servers of ON-MERRIT partners only as long as it is needed for the project purposes (up to two years after the finalisation of the project). The authentication and authorization policies put in place, will guarantee the protection of personal data during ON-MERRIT's lifetime. After the end of the project, the "Right to be forgotten" Directive will be fully satisfied. Any personal data (such as names, emails, and contact details) of people participating in the interview activities, focus groups, or surveys will be destroyed. ● The anonymised focus group, workshop and interview summaries, as well as the survey data will be retained at least for 3 years after the end of the project. Whenever possible, in line with the EC's open data policy, suitably anonymised data will be made available via an online repository so that third parties can access and use it.

5.1.2 Informed consent procedures

The ON-MERRIT consortium will implement several data collection methods (as outlined in the section above) that will include recruitment of participants and gathering data (including demographic data, e.g. age group, area of work, gender) and their opinions and experiences related to the uptake of RRI and Open Science resources and methods in domains like research, industry and policy. Through informed consent procedures participants will be acquainted with the project and its objectives, planned research activities, what type of data will be collected, and how the data will be used and handled. This information will help potential participants decide about their participation.

5.1.2.1 Implementation of informed consent procedures

The procedures of informed consent here outlined will be used and applied by all partner organisations and their staff working in ON-MERRIT. It will be the responsibility of the organisation's contact persons (as listed in the Project Handbook, D1.1 delivered in Month 2 of the project) to ensure that their staff conduct research activities in accordance with the procedures outlined in the current document.

All the data gathering activities conducted in the ON-MERRIT project framework will comply with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 ("GDPR")⁹⁵ and other relevant national laws and regulations, as well as the ON-MERRIT EC Grant Agreement. Personal data collected during the research activities will include age, gender, career stage and discipline. However, no sensitive personal data will be collected in the context of ON-MERRIT project. In addition, researchers will make sure that only data that is strictly in line with the objectives of the ON-MERRIT project is collected.

Several project activities including surveys, interviews, case studies, focus groups, and workshops will involve recruitment of participants. Before recruiting participants to any of the research activities, the consortium partners responsible for the activity will provide written (i.e. the provided project information sheet) and, if necessary, verbal information about the project, its objectives, and how the collected data will be used. In particular, the researchers will inform the participants about:

⁹⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

- Duration of the project
- Research procedures
- Benefits to the subject field
- Where to get more information about the ON-MERRIT project (i.e. references to project website and email contact details of researchers)
- That the participation is voluntary
- How the collected data will be used and handled

This information will be provided in lay terms that are understandable by all potential participants. Also, sufficient time will be given to the individuals to decide on their participation in the research. The individuals will be informed that:

- They are free to withdraw from the research activities at any point without providing reason for their withdrawal
- Their personal data will be treated confidentially and anonymously, with the exception of crowd-sourced data contributed publicly
- The collected data will be analysed for the entire group of participants, rather than individually, thus securing their privacy and anonymity

The individual's informed consent will be obtained by requesting a verbal consent by the individual or the individual's legally authorized representative. This practice will be applied in interviews, case studies, focus groups, and workshops. If requested, the participant will be able to receive interview summaries or focus group minutes to confirm the collected data.

In any online surveys, a field with the information about the study will be included, preceding the actual questionnaire. The participant will be in the position to continue to the questionnaire, only if he / she clicks on the "I agree" button and declares his / her agreement to participate.

If requested by the participant or researcher, written informed consent can be obtained from the individual or individual's legally authorized representative for participation in the study. Then, an information sheet template will be used to provide the information about ON-MERRIT project and informed consent form will be used by the researchers to obtain the written informed consent from the participants.

5.1.3 Draft templates for ON-MERRIT Information Sheet and Informed Consent form

Draft templates that ON-MERRIT will use to:

- a) inform research participants about the aims of the project and the terms of their participation, and
- b) obtain informed consent from participants that they have understood these terms and consent to take part in the study,

are included as "**Optional annex 3: Ethics Supporting Document(s)**," a separate document accompanying this proposal.

5.2 Security⁹⁶

Please indicate if your project will involve:

- activities or results raising security issues: NO
- 'EU-classified information' as background or results: NO

⁹⁶ See article 37 of the Model Grant Agreement. . For more information on the classification of Information, please refer to the Horizon 2020 guidance: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/secur/h2020-hi-guide-classif_en.pdf.